
Preface

This is the first report from the research project “The use of human biobanks – ethical, social, economical and legal aspects.” We are grateful to VINNOVA – The Swedish Agency for Innovation Systems, the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (The ELSA-Program), the National Board of Health and Welfare and the Federation of County Councils for financial support. The project is described in the introduction to the report. Special thanks to Roger Tanner who has translated three chapters and proof read the other chapters. Many thanks also to Josepine Fernow for valuable contributions in preparing the manuscript for printing.

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Introduction

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The use of human biobanks – ethical, social, economical and legal aspects. Presentation of the project.

Objectives

Human biological material – such as cells collected in research projects, biopsy specimens obtained for diagnostic purposes, and organs removed during surgery – has become vital for research in biomedicine and biotechnology. The main purpose of this project is to propose ethical and legal guidelines so that the research, diagnostic and treatment value of these biobanks may be acknowledged without violating the integrity of individual research subjects and patients. As a working definition, “biobanks” are collections of human biological material within the health care system and the medical sciences. Both privately and publicly financed biobanks are included. Within a multi-disciplinary research format, ethical, economical, social and legal problems associated with the use of human biological material are analysed. Ethical rules and guidelines and suggestions for legislation will be proposed. Open seminars are taking place on a regular basis during the project. At these seminars, representatives of the financing parties as well as the industry, public authorities and the academic community are invited to discuss the progress of the project.

The objectives of the project are:

- A. Analysis of ethical problems associated with the use of human biobanks and proposal of information and consent procedures appropriate for treatment, quality assurance and research purposes.
- B. Analysis of how different economical interests associated with the use of human biobanks (primarily those of biomedical firms) can be satisfied without coming into conflict with other important interests (e.g. , ethical and legal).
- C. Analysis of legal questions related to property and disposition claims and proposal of legislation that takes the different interests into consideration.
- D. Analysis of the relevant provisions in Swedish and international public law, and suggestions for legislation that will facilitate an efficient management of Swedish biobanks, while also offering appropriate protection to the human rights, such as privacy and integrity, of individuals and groups concerned.
- E. To stimulate a public dialogue concerning the use of human biobanks.

Project plan

September 1999 – December 1999:

Initiation of the project, fund raising, recruitment of scholars. Hearing with public authorities, scientists, and with representatives from industry and from Iceland.

January 2000-December 2000:

- A. Ethics: Ethical and philosophical analysis of the notions of “informed consent” and the ownership of bodies and body parts. Discussions of conditions for withdrawal of consent.
- B. Economics: Mapping of past, current and planned use of Swedish biobanks for industrial purposes.
- C. Private law: Inventory of existing property and disposition rights regarding till human biological material.
- D. Public law: Inventory of existing Swedish law regarding the taking, storing, use and transfer of human biological material, as well as the management of information derived therefrom.

January 2001 – December 2001

- A. Ethics: Empirical study of the public's, blood donors' and patients' preferences with regard to regulations for information and consent in the collection and utilization of biobanks. Analysis of ethical problems related to using samples that are collected without proper consent and the effect on the family of using genetic information about an individual member.
- B. Economics: Study of commercialization of public biobanks through dedicated genomics companies (such as deCode Genetics, UmanGenomics and Oxagen).
- C. Private law: Analysis of consequences regarding intellectual property law, as well as terms of access to human biological material. Legal analysis of the notion of “donation” and “gift”, as well as of EC competition law.
- D. Public law: Continued inventory of Nordic and international public law, as well as relevant EU legislation. Preliminary analysis and comparative studies.

January 2002 – December 2002

- A. Ethics: Normative analysis of intrinsic and instrumental values. Formulation of ethical guidelines, with specification of different levels of information and consent for different clinical and research purposes. Proposal for the handling of code keys.
- B. Economics: Continued study of different models for commercialization of public biobanks with respect for ethical and legal concerns.
- C. Private law: Proposal for legislation and regulations for property and disposition rights.
- D. Public law: Final analysis and comparative studies, taking into consideration the results from the other sub-studies. Suggestions for legislation and regulations in the area of public law.

The research context

The research conducted within this project is multi-disciplinary and includes collaboration by scholars at several universities. The project is hosted by the Research Program Ethics in Biomedicine at Uppsala University. Participation by scholars from other universities is based on legal contracts with each department. The research program Ethics in Biomedicine was established by the Vice-Chancellor of Uppsala University in August 1998 with the aim of initiating and coordinating research projects in biomedical ethics. Several projects are related

to ethical implications of genome and gene technology research. Of particular interest for the project on biobanks in this research environment are projects related to genetic diagnosis and treatment of hereditary cancer, the handling of genetic information, public perception of gene technology and philosophical implications of behavioral genetics. A characteristic feature of all projects is the close collaboration with natural scientists and clinicians relevant to a specific project.

Partners and collaborators

The following scholars have been employed on a full-time or part-time basis within the project.

Jacob Dahl Rendtorff, Ph.D., *Department of Philosophy, Roskilde University.*

Associate Professor Bengt Domeij, LL.D., *Industrial Economics and Management, Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm*

Stefan Eriksson, ThD., *Research Program Ethics in Biomedicine, Uppsala University.*

Åsa Kettis-Lindblad, PhD, *Research Program Ethics in Biomedicine, Uppsala University* is collaborating with the project and is one of the authors. She is being financed with a research grant from the Swedish Council for Social Research.

Associate Professor Jens Laage-Hellman, PhD, *Institute for Management of Innovation and Technology, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg.*

Lena Lundberg, Ph.D., *Research Program Ethics in Biomedicine, Uppsala University.*

Associate Professor Annina Persson, LL.D, *Department of Law , Stockholm University.*

Associate Professor Elisabeth Rynning, LL.D., *Faculty of Law, Uppsala University*

Li Westerlund, LL.D., *Department of Law, Stockholm University.*

The following scholars are working on the project within the framework of their ordinary university positions.

Associate Professor Mats G. Hansson, ThD, (Project Leader), *Research Program Ethics in Biomedicine, Uppsala University.*

Professor Marianne Levin, LL.D., *Department of Law, Stockholm University*

Associate Professor Christer Sundström, MD, PhD, *Department of Genetics and Pathology, Uppsala University.*

The following scientists are consultants to the project. They take part in seminars, write texts and review material before publishing.

Professor Maria Anvret, PhD, *AstraZeneca AB.*

Lena Jonsson, PhD, *Amersham Pharmacia Biotech*.

Professor Ulf Landegren, MD, PhD, *Department of Genetics and Pathology, Uppsala University*

Bo Lindberg, MD, Former Medical Director, *Uppsala University Hospital*

Associate Professor Kerstin Westermark, MD, PhD, *Swedish Medical Products Agency*.

Funding

Funding has been sought throughout with the aim of financing the entire three-year project. The funds are pooled, and, in accordance with agreements and contracts with the respective financing organizations, funds are requisitioned as needed. Grants have been awarded by: VINNOVA – The Swedish Agency for Innovation Systems (former NUTEK), the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (The ELSA-Program), the National Board of Health and Welfare and the Federation of County Councils.

Progress of the project and publications

The work is proceeding in accordance with the objectives and the timetable of the project. One hearing was held in Uppsala in September 1999. Two public hearings have been held in Göteborg during 2000. This is the report of the first phase of the project and it will be presented at a public hearing in Uppsala on 16th May 2001. Seminars are held regularly. Starting in May 2001, the project group will work together with a group of scientists at Uppsala University and representatives of Uppsala University Hospital and Uppsala County Council in order to establish a model for collecting and using human biological material for research. The individual participants of the project prepare their own manuscripts, the majority of which will be published in scientific journals during and after the final year of the project.

Publications

Domeij, B., 2001, Humanbiologiskt material och vinningssyften, *Juridisk Tidskrift* (Accepted for publication, in press)

Hansson, M.G., 2000, International Aspects: National Profiles, Scandinavia, in: Murray, T.J., & Melham, M.J., (eds.), *Encyclopedia of Ethical, Legal and Policy Issues in Biotechnology*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., pp.731-738.

Hansson, M.G. et al, 2001, *The use of human biobanks – ethical, social, economical and legal aspects*, Reprt I, Uppsala.

Laage-Hellman, J., 2001, Kommersialisering av svenska biobanker: ett näringspolitiskt perspektiv, *IMIT- report*, Institute for Management of Innovation and Technology, (Forthcoming)

Introduction

Persson, A., Westerlund, L., 2000, *Civilrättsliga reflektioner på användningen av mänskligt biologiskt material*, Juridiska fakulteten vid Stockholms universitet Skriftserien nr 64, (70 pages).

Rynning, E., 2000, *Genteknikens användning på människa – rättsliga aspekter med särskild inriktning på Sverige och övriga Norden*. Bilaga 5 till Bioteknikkommitténs slutbetänkande *Att spränga gränser. En svensk bioteknikpolitik* (SOU 2000:103), pp. 405-468 (Partly within the finances of the project).

Storing and using biobanks for research

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Introduction

The successful application of large-scale biological analyses to determine total genome sequences inspires similar grand attempts to understand the function of the encoded molecules in health and disease. Collections of patient samples – biobanks – will play a central role in this work by revealing genetic, other molecular and environmental factors of importance for the development of disease, as well as for properties like personality traits or longevity. It is therefore appropriate to consider some of the technological prerequisites for the use of biobanks. We will briefly discuss the accumulating knowledge base arising from genomic research, the identification of medically relevant molecular indicators, and the development of technologies and procedures to investigate these factors using banks of human tissue samples.

Genomic Progress

The Human Genome Project

The fundamental strategy in genomic research is to establish and utilise effective methods to accumulate extensive, ultimately total information about aspects of genomes, without focussing on specific biological or medical problems¹. After a recent acceleration of data gathering, information on the nucleotide sequence of the human genome is now all but complete. An understanding of the complete complement of human genes is not yet at hand, but should become available over the next few years, probably listing considerably less than 50,000 genes.

Information is also accumulating about the normal variation among human genomes. Most commonly, sequence differences between individuals involve differences in single nucleotide positions. DNA sequence variants with a reasonably high population frequency are observed approximately every 1,000 nucleotides across the genome, and are referred to as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). Information about more than one million variable sequences is already publicly available via the Internet², and more such markers are available from commercial providers of genetic information. There is a strong and widespread expectation that information about genetic variation, along with improved methods to study this in suitable biobanks, will provide invaluable insights into the basis of all major diseases.

It is already becoming apparent that this will prove a challenging proposition, however, and that further improvements in strategy and technology may be necessary to realise this potential. In parallel with sequencing of the human genome, total genome sequences of important model organisms like yeast, *C. elegans*, the fruit fly, the mouse and the rat, as well as of most important infectious agents, have become or are rapidly becoming available. This provides important opportunities for illuminating comparisons between different organisms, and for identification of the sources of infections in patient samples.

Functional Genomics

The focus of research interest is now shifting to the accumulation of global information about how genomes encode the properties of proteins, cells, and organism, through functional genomic research³. Over the next ten-year period these efforts should provide invaluable information about the structure of most or all human proteins, their interaction partners, and the connectivity of all metabolic and signal transmission chains, thereby defining the modules that perform the various cellular functions⁴. Analytical tools will be developed for efficient studies of all these properties; tools that also become available for analyses of biobanked material.

The search for molecular lesions

Current medical research yields an abundance of molecular factors of value as targets for diagnostic investigations. The various types of analyses commonly used to investigate such factors in biobanked samples may be grouped as follows:

Resequencing

Single or small sets of genes are being identified that are typically found to be altered by mutations in particular diseases, and that may therefore need to be scrutinised in individual patients for the cellular equivalents of software bugs. This requires resequencing the relevant gene in individual patients to reveal any deviations from one or a few known normal variants of the sequence. For many genes, information about hundreds or more pathologic alterations that have been observed are already archived in mutation databases available via the Internet.

Genotyping

Many known human DNA sequence variants are known to be associated with particular diseases⁵ or they may influence a patient's response to a particular drug⁶. Genotyping of such markers may therefore be of value to characterise patient populations. DNA sequence variants with no known functional consequences can also be useful in association and linkage analyses.

In association studies, the frequency of variants of individual genetic markers are compared between healthy persons and patient populations, with the hope that an observed difference in frequency may be the consequence of a direct effect by the sequence difference, or due to co-inheritance with nearby, unknown genetic variants having such an effect. Associated markers with no direct effect on the disease are said to be in linkage disequilibrium with the disease-related changes, and they may therefore guide the investigator to the gene, which is directly involved in the disease. If the DNA samples are derived from individuals in families where particular diseases are known to segregate, then the location of

disease-associated genetic changes among the chromosomes may be pinpointed by genetic linkage analysis using the same types of genetic markers. This approach has proven extremely valuable for defining the nature of conditions primarily influenced by single or a limited number of genes⁷.

However, when many genes are involved in causing disease, along with prominent influence by environmental factors, then both association studies and linkage analyses have met with far greater difficulty. This type of more complex disease causation is probably characteristic of most clinically important human diseases.

Transcript Profiling

By measuring how individual or large sets of genes are expressed in the cells of a sampled tissue, a valuable view is obtained of the state of differentiation and activity of the sampled cells. Suitable comparison between healthy and affected tissues can reveal genes whose expression is affected by disease. The analysis provides an important basis for diagnosis in e.g. malignancy⁸, and allows monitoring of the progress of disease or response to therapy. After a phase of analyses of transcription of thousands or tens of thousands of genes, it will probably be feasible to define limited sets of genes likely to be informative for disease diagnosis and follow-up.

Gene quantification

Copy number changes of specific gene regions in malignancy can reflect loss of genetic factors that protect against excessive proliferation, or conversely, gain of copies of genes that can support such proliferation, evident as altered copy numbers of certain chromosomal regions. Regions of the genome present in increased or decreased copy numbers can be demonstrated by comparing genomic DNA samples from normal and malignant tissues through a process called comparative genome hybridisation⁹, allowing genes critically important for the malignant phenotype to be demarcated.

Proteomics

Following in the footsteps of the characterisation of the human genome comes the desire to associate the gene products to functions and roles in biological networks. Analyses of the expression of large sets of proteins, or of rearrangements or secondary modifications of proteins are coming more and more to be seen as promising approaches for monitoring biological processes in patient samples. Such proteomic analyses reflect the biological state of the body fluid or tissue at the time the sample was collected, sensitively influenced by both genetic and environmental factors¹⁰. Samples of any types of tissues or body fluids can be utilised for the analyses, and the generated information adds valuable pieces to the biological puzzle. Identifying protein patterns that are specific for a certain disease can enable the identification of disease mechanisms and the development of new diagnostic and therapeutic tools, and perhaps ways of preventing the development of disease.

And much more

Other classes of molecular analyses are known to be informative about predisposition for, or about the state and progress of disease. For example, gross structural changes of chromosomes can be of diagnostic value in congenital disease and in malignancy.

Cytogenetic analyses of this kind can be combined with in situ hybridisation using specific DNA probes. In histopathology too, analysis of the microscopic location of specific proteins and RNA and DNA sequences provides more specific information. The ability to expand DNA sequence elements at the ends of chromosomes, telomers, is characteristic of a limited number of stem cells but also of many malignant cells, and this activity can therefore betray the presence of malignant cells in tissue samples¹¹. Comprehensive measurements of metabolites, sometimes referred to as metabolomics, can be highly informative in analyses of patient samples. Currently, a rapidly expanding number of analytes are being identified that can be of interest to monitor in biobanked material.

Methods for molecular analyses

One of the factors sparking increased interest in collections of patient samples is the greatly improved techniques that are becoming available for such analyses, enabling far greater numbers of increasingly precise analyses of progressively smaller tissue samples, as well as entirely new forms of examinations.

Analytical technologies

Routine analyses of human genes became feasible in the mid-1970s with the advent of the Southern blot, and the Sanger method to deduce nucleotide sequences followed a few years later¹². The preconditions further improved with the development of the polymerase chain reaction in the mid-1980s, by providing the specificity and sensitivity required to conveniently detect individual DNA sequences among the thirteen billion nucleotides constituting the genome in each human cell nucleus¹³.

Since the mid-1990s an increasing number of genetic analyses have been performed using microprocessor-like chips where large numbers of different probes have been deposited¹⁴. These DNA microarrays permit simultaneous analysis of large numbers of gene sequences in analyses such as resequencing, genotyping, gene expression measurement and so on.

The toolkit for proteomic analysis has also expanded considerably in recent years. Techniques like electrophoresis, chromatography, and mass spectrometry have been scaled to address the need for comprehensive analyses of protein complements. In another important line of development in proteomics, binding by antibodies and other affinity reagents can reveal the presence and concentrations of large sets of specific proteins.

Technological developments at home and abroad

Sweden has a strong tradition of developing methods for analysis of biomolecules. The Svedberg and Arne Tiselius both received the Nobel prize for their work on ultracentrifugation and on electrophoresis, respectively. These methods of protein characterisation were later followed by others like chromatography, isoelectric focussing, and antibody-assisted immune precipitation and ELISA techniques. More recently, a number of techniques for molecular analyses have been established by scientists in Sweden¹⁵. Clearly, the availability of unique detection technologies has played an important role in Swedish biomedical research at universities and in the pharmaceutical industry, and it has provided a basis for a viable biotech industry. Nonetheless, detection techniques continue to be an important limiting factor in the use of biobanks and further dramatic improvements are both required and expected.

Future technologies that may significantly influence the usefulness of biobanks include methods to prepare and handle large numbers of samples in parallel. One existing example of such technologies – tissue arrays – allows multiple representations of a thousand or more tissues to be prepared and accessed for parallel microscopic analysis. It is also foreseeable that far larger numbers of target molecules can be studied at one time. This is of importance both from the point of view of throughput and because it promises to limit consumption of valuable collected samples if one test can answer a thousand questions. Investigations that can report the relative location or fine structure of proteins or precise quantity of sets of proteins are likely to provide important insights into the state of tissue samples. Finally, an increasing range of tests that directly analyse the function of important cellular components will provide valuable information about biobanked samples.

Biobanks

Excellent opportunities thus exist to combine the rapidly growing knowledge about the constituents of our cells and the improved means of analysing them in the course of studies of central biological questions. Such investigations are frequently performed in model organisms that present opportunities for genetic crosses, gene modifications, or other interventions. However, many problems peculiar to human health or specific human properties will require studies of collections of tissue samples from human donors. It is therefore important to make plans for effective biobanks where samples of body fluids and tissues can be received, stored, and made available for research.

By collecting and storing well-characterised sets of patient samples, the same samples can be used in many different investigations, reducing inconvenience to the donors and allowing more effective use of research funds. Studies of banked samples can be continually extended as technology improves or more information becomes available about factors of particular interest in the investigation of specific diseases. In this way comprehensive information will accumulate about collected samples, increasing the value of any subsequent investigation.

Deposits and withdrawals in biobanks

A fundamental problem with biobanks concerns the need to collect samples today, or better still yesterday, for research needs that may arise tomorrow. Accordingly, there is a significant problem in determining which samples should be collected. The use of biobanks presents a related problem, made in that it has to be decided whether the application of a limited sample resource is justified for the study in question. Clearly, more focussed studies could be performed at some later time when more is known about the problem in question. Moreover, at a later time more analyses will be possible with the same amount of tissue, or entirely novel forms of analysis may become possible.

For molecular genetic analyses, the collected samples must include nucleated cells in order to provide a store of genomic DNA. This is commonly obtained by sampling blood or perhaps cells obtained from the lining of the mouth cavity, but a wide variety of tissues can be used. Studies of somatic genetic changes that may have arisen during life, for example in tumour tissues, naturally require nucleated cells from the relevant tissues to be sampled.

What genes are expressed in sampled tissues, and at what levels, can be investigated by mRNA analyses, again necessitating that nucleated cells to be present in the sampled tissues. Due to the proneness of mRNA to degradation, special care must be taken to preserve

integrity, e.g. by storage at very low temperatures or in the presence of denaturants that prevent enzymatic degradation.

Proteins can be analysed in a wide variety of samples of tissues and body fluids and do not require that the samples containing nucleated cells. Like samples collected for mRNA analyses, they also require careful methods for treatment and storage of the samples.

Analyses of low molecular weight substances such as hormones, nerve transmitters and metabolites also provide valuable views on the state of sampled tissues, and on factors directly or indirectly involved in ongoing disease processes. Such analyses are possible using a wide range of tissues.

Some donated samples that include live cells may be preserved by adapting the cells for tissue culture, providing a permanent, renewable record of the genotype and permitting functional assays at the level of the cell. As an alternative, tissues can be stored at low temperature and under conditions where viability is preserved for possible later adaptation for tissue culture. Further progress in the understanding of cellular differentiation and the culture of stem cells may allow widely different tissue types to be derived from stored samples of patient tissue.

The large numbers of serum samples that exist at many clinical departments can be used for proteomic studies and may permit detection of infectious agents or immune responses to such agents, but genetic studies are difficult because of the minimal and variable presence of nucleated cells. Formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded samples are routinely preserved after pathological analyses and very large numbers of such samples are stored at departments of pathology around the country. Future analytic technologies may allow an increasing number of biomolecules to be evaluated in such samples.

The Swedish situation

Sweden has excellent, in some respects unique, advantages for the collection and application of biobanks in large epidemiological studies, as is already reflected in the scientific literature. Several aspects have been of key importance for this work:

- For genetic studies it can be of advantage that parts of Sweden were colonised by a limited number of individuals, since this increases the probability of two individuals who both have a given disease also sharing genetic risk factors.
- An advanced health care system is of importance in ensuring that sampled individuals have been correctly and promptly diagnosed and characterised with respect to relevant clinical parameters.
- Church records and other registers can provide information on the genealogy of sampled individuals, establishing relatedness as required in genetic linkage studies.
- The availability of health care records detailing diagnoses at discharge from hospitals or at time of death or listing twins, provides a potential for rapidly identifying suitable populations to sample.
- The use of personal identifiers (unique national registration numbers) can permit cross-referencing between the large number of registers, subject to permission being granted for such studies.
- Large banks of collected samples are already at hand, for instance serum samples, pathological specimens, cervical smears collected in check-ups, or the PKU-archive containing blood from new-born children, and banks of collected blood samples such as that maintained by the Medical Biobank in Umeå.
- Advanced epidemiological expertise is available, but may nonetheless remain one of several limiting factors for the exploitation of biobanks.

- It is of some importance that the Swedish population is larger than, for example, that of Iceland, where rare diseases will have a more limited representation.
- Finally, the population appears to have a generally positive attitude towards donating samples and providing background information in the interest of furthering scientific understanding of disease. The relationship between patients and scientists is based on a social contract, necessitating that the highest standards are maintained in protecting the integrity of the donors, and that collected resources are optimally stored and applied.

Conclusions

Excellent opportunities thus exist for combining the rapidly growing knowledge about the constituents of our cells and the improved means of analysis of them in the course of studies of central biological questions. Investigations of this kind are frequently performed in model organisms which present opportunities for genetic crosses, gene modifications, or other interventions. However, many problems peculiar to human health or specific human properties will require studies of collections of tissue samples from human donors. It is therefore important to make plans for effective biobanks where samples of body fluids and tissues can be received, stored, and made available for research.

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The biobank resource in anatomical pathology

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Introduction

Activities in a pathology department are mainly concerned with supplying physicians with diagnoses of specimens from their patients. The sample material consists of tissues or cells. These specimens are prepared in a laboratory process whereby thin sections of tissue specimens or cell smears are placed on slides and then stained, so that details of tissues and cells can be studied in the microscope. The pathologist, however, makes his first observations of the incoming material with the naked eye, before attempting, through the microscope, with the background of his experience of samples examined previously and with reference to given diagnostic criteria, to interpret any lesions that may be present in the material received. Examination of the specimen material should normally lead to a statement describing the findings in the material and leading up to a diagnosis or to various possible differential diagnostic options. Although microscopic scrutiny as a form of image interpretation must also be conducted as objectively as possible, that scrutiny nevertheless involves elements of subjectivity. The difficulty of assessment varies from one specimen to another. In some cases diagnosis comes easily and reproducibility is high between different diagnosticians. In others the findings are so hard to interpret that different diagnosticians can arrive at different assessments of the specimen material. If specimens are this hard to interpret, diagnosticians with special experience of a certain type of specimen material or of certain diagnoses are often consulted.

Clinical pathology and cytology

Clinical pathology and cytology span a wide diversity of pathological states, so much so that diagnosticians in the larger pathology departments have had to sub-specialise. Thus we now have specialists, for example, in breast pathology, dermato pathology, endocrine pathology, gynaecological pathology, haemato pathology, lung pathology, neuropathology, urological pathology and gastrointestinal pathology. To optimise their diagnostic service to hospital departments sending material for analysis, pathology specialists with specialist knowledge also take part in recurrent clinico-pathological conferences together with clinicians. At these conferences the pathologist demonstrates specimens for microscopy and diagnosis, differential diagnoses and the subsequent course of examination and treatment are discussed, often resulting in a consensus decision.

Technically speaking, the handling of specimens in the laboratory is very much of a handicraft and is based on the fundamental principle that incoming tissue specimens first have to be fixed so as to curtail all processes of degradation in the tissue. This is followed by a

dehydration process which removes water and fixer from the specimen, substituting a paraffin solvent. The tissue material is then embedded in paraffin, after which the specimen will be preserved in a paraffin block. From this block, thin sections of the tissue are then cut and placed on glass slides. With the tissue section now in position on the slide, the next stages of preparation are deparaffination and staining. The purpose of the staining procedure is to make various details of the tissue distinguishable to the eye, so that cells, cell nuclei and other tissue structures will be made visible in the microscope.

The diagnostic process is basically microscopic, i.e. based on *examination in the microscope* and on an assessment of findings in the specimen material with reference to diagnostic criteria for different diseases. A conclusive diagnosis, however, cannot always be reached solely through microscopy of the specimen material. New techniques have also made it possible for other kinds of information in the tissue material to be revealed. One technique which has rapidly gained ground is *immunohistochemistry*, which means that, by using antibodies, e.g. for various proteins, one can visualise whether or not these proteins are present in a tissue specimen.

Immunohistochemical stainings, then, mean that antibodies to various structures in the tissue are incubated with tissue sections mounted on slides and any antibodies attached to structures in the tissue are then “developed” in a chemical reaction which makes the antibody and its location in the tissue visible through the microscope. For example, in a case of undifferentiated malignant tumour – where microscopy does not enable us to judge where the tumour emanates from – the demonstration of cytokeratine in the tumour cells, by means of immunohistochemical technique, can show the tumour to be of epithelial origin. If instead an undifferentiated malignant tumour of this kind expresses leukocyte common antigen, this means that the tumour emanates from lymphocytes instead.

The panel of antibodies available for these purposes today exceeds more than a hundred, and this possibility of visualising structures not observable with the naked eye has made microscopic diagnosis more certain, with the result that more specific diagnoses can now often be made. In certain special diagnostic situations, *molecular genetic techniques* can also be used for extracting further information from a tissue specimen. In connection, for example, with cervical cell changes, a special examination technique can establish the presence or absence in the specimen of human papilloma virus. Any such virus, if present, can be typed, and in this way it can be ascertained whether the patient is infected with “dangerous” or “harmless” variants of the virus. In addition, for example in cases of infantile leukaemia, these molecular genetic techniques can tell us whether treatment of the leukaemia has eliminated the leukaemia cells from the bone marrow or whether they are still present.

The tissue specimens sent to the pathology department include a certain proportion of surgical specimens, i.e. entire organs or parts of organs which have been removed for purposes of treatment or diagnosis. Material of this kind can, for example, take the form of a inflamed gallbladder, a spleen removed because it is destroying the patients blood platelets, part of an extremity with a malignant tumour, or tonsils which have become enlarged, causing the patient difficulty in breathing or swallowing. Tissue specimens can also take the form of biopsies, i.e. small samples of organs or tissues where the physician treating the patient suspects a pathological process. This may be a suspected malignant tumour which has to be diagnosed in advance of surgery or some other kind of treatment, in order for the right treatment to be started. The material can also come from curettage, e.g. of the womb, in which case the physician treating the patient performs curettage of the endometrium with a view to diagnosis or as treatment for a haemorrhaging condition. Needle biopsy is a relatively new technique whereby samples can be removed from a sick tissue. This minimal material is sometimes all that is needed for a complete diagnosis. Cell specimens consist of cells scraped,

for example, from the cervix, cells isolated from fluid effusions in the thoracic or abdominal cavity, or cells “aspirated” from tissue or organs by a fine needle biopsy technique.

The tissue or cell specimen is accompanied by a referral from the physician treating the patient, supplying anamnestic information and a description of the patient’s symptoms and the clinical findings. The referral information also includes a question which the physician requires an answer to. The information in the referral is often supplemented by a certain amount of laboratory data, as well as particulars of earlier samples examined from the same patient and the diagnoses obtained.

After a diagnosis has been sent to the physician, the sample material, in the case of tissue specimens, consists of stained sections from the specimen mounted on slides, as well as blocks of paraffin wax in which the sections on the slide were previously embedded. The preparations made from incoming cell specimens consist solely of stained cells on slides. The sample material left over after the specimen has been embedded and slides prepared is retained for about a month and then destroyed as biological waste. During the month for which the whole of the macroscopic sampling material is stored in the pathology department, the diagnostician is free to return to the material and, if the examination so requires, to remove additional sections for embedding and microscopic examination. This sometimes becomes necessary if the first sample of pieces examined does not yield a diagnosis or if relevant portions of the diseased parts have not been included in the pieces selected. Sometimes access to the macroscopic preparation is also needed to facilitate the investigation of a mix up of specimens, in which case the physician sending in the specimen may need to be contacted for further information about the character of the material sent in.

Reasons for preserving specimen material

The General Recommendations issued by the National Board of Health and Welfare¹ advise pathology departments for the time being to retain paraffin wax blocks and slides with cytology specimens together with the referrals accompanying sample material of all kinds. The National Board of Health and Welfare recommends at least 15 years’ retention of slides prepared from the embedded material and cell smears from the cervix. There are several reasons for these retention routines. One important reason is concerned with *care of the patient* and the investigation of the illness which the patient may be suffering from. In the event of a relapse one needs to go back to the first samples that were sent in, in order, e.g. when investigating a tumour, to compare the latest specimen received with an earlier one. In this kind of examination it is important to decide whether the patient has suffered a recurrence of a tumour diagnosed previously or has developed a new tumour. Clarification of these matters has an important bearing on the planning of treatment and on the individual patient’s prognosis. In such an investigation it may be necessary to carry out additional examinations of the old sample material in order to refine the diagnosis of that material, e.g. if new and more advanced techniques of diagnosis have been developed in the meantime.

The preserved material is also an important resource for all other *medically related activity* in a pathology department. The embedded material is used to a certain extent in development work on the laboratory process and for testing new methods whereby more information can be derived from the sample material. The immunohistochemical stainings mentioned earlier resulted from comprehensive development work using paraffin blocks. This material will also need to be used in the future as a means of further optimising the technique, so that different structures in the tissue can be visualised in the best possible way in sections from embedded samples. This means that different types of tissue will have to be used in order for different pre-treatments of the material to be evaluated, so as to make the structures

which are to be demonstrated by means of antibodies accessible to those antibodies. Once an immunohistochemical staining technique has been tried out, whenever the technique is used a positive control has to be used on the same slide as a specimen from a patient, so as to make sure on this particular occasion that the staining works. To this end, embedded material with the positive control has to be all the time available for use.

New antibodies are appearing all the time, making it possible for new structures to be demonstrated in tissue and cell specimens, and this development work, accordingly, is continuous and demands access to a comprehensive material of paraffin wax blocks. Similarly, increasing use is now being made of molecular genetic techniques to supplement the microscopic assessment of the sample material. In accordance with this it is becoming increasingly common for *in situ* hybridisation to be used on routine material. With techniques of this kind, chromosomal injuries of different kinds can also be demonstrated in paraffin wax sections or cell specimens by incubating DNA specimens with a connected fluorescent substance in the tissue sections. These DNA specimens identify specific parts of chromosomes, and in this way “translocations” between chromosomes or “amplifications” of parts of chromosomes can be demonstrated. If a technique of this kind is put into service, comprehensive development work is needed to make it viable. This technique also demands constant access to control material, so that one can be sure of the technique having worked properly whenever it is used.

Who uses the sample material?

The material in a pathology department’s biobank is also used in the training of prospective pathologist and cytologists and for developing the specialists’ competence. For this purpose the embedded material may sometimes need to be re-used, by making new sections and preparing different stainings. Slide seminars are a frequently recurrent form of instruction in pathology. They involve producing several editions of a collection of preparations, e.g. from tumours of the lymphatic glands, for distribution to all pathology departments in the country or to the participants on a course. In such slide seminars, pathology departments are often invited to submit suggested diagnoses of the cases included in the seminar box, and at a meeting of specialists from the pathology departments an expert in the field reviews the cases concerned, shows examples of findings made in the preparations, demonstrates special staining techniques and discusses diagnosis and differential diagnoses. On courses, e.g. for residents during their specialist training, the teacher gives a very hands-on presentation of each individual preparation, discusses different findings and how to diagnose different preparations, gives advice on pitfalls and how to avoid them, and discusses various differential diagnoses. This type of training and instruction is always going on within the profession and is absolutely dependent on access to the specimen material held by the pathology departments.

Another medically related use of the sample material concerns occasions when new classification systems are published for different groups of tumours. In order for experience concerning these classification systems and their usefulness to be acquired swiftly, and to give people an opportunity of practising the use of them, it is often necessary to compile and review large corpuses of material from several patients with tumours coming under the new system of classification. New sections and stainings from the preserved material may then be needed. Retrospective reviews like this of collections of preparations are also made necessary when clinical treatment programmes come up for evaluation. On such occasions, the sample material from the patients whose treatment is to be evaluated has to be reviewed by an experienced pathologist on one and the same occasion. Before such a review can take place,

new sections and stainings often have to be prepared in order for the sample material to be processed as uniformly as possible.

A further important reason for the retention of sample material and referrals at pathology departments, as remarked in the General Recommendations of the National Board of Health and Welfare, concerns the use of the material for *research*. This combined research resource of all Sweden's pathology departments has been estimated at between 40 and 80 million paraffin blocks. The material represents a host of different diseases with morphological expressions, including diseases which are already well known and those which have yet to be identified or fully described. In future, then, this material may provide answers to important questions about the nature of diseases, their origin and development. This type of research based on tissue and cell specimens has been going on for over a century now, and the material accumulated by the pathology departments has been a very great asset in the overall advancement of medical science. Previous studies based on this archived material have mostly been confined to morphological descriptions, both macro- and microscopic, of diseases. But, in addition to morphological details, which identify different diseases in many ways, the sample material also conceals other information which is tending more and more to become a subject of research. This type of research has been made possible by new techniques which in various ways have been capable of revealing hidden information in the tissue material, above all by indicating different proteins and other components in cells and tissues which cannot be made visible by traditional staining techniques. Immunohistochemical stainings use antibodies to various proteins and other structures in cells and tissues. By incubating sections with antibodies marked with a stainable substance, the presence of such proteins can be demonstrated in the sections and their location in the sample material described. In this way, changes in the diseased tissue can be described more closely in relation, for example, to the behaviour of other tumours under consideration, and also in relation to the way in which normal tissue expresses the protein investigated. This type of research has yielded many new results which have simplified and refined morphologically based diagnosis, making groups of tumours, for example, more easily distinguishable from each other and for tumours with an undifferentiated morphological expression to be traced back to their origin. Other techniques, e.g. chemical methods, may also be applicable to the embedded material.

Conclusion

The introduction of molecular biological techniques has opened up a new dimension in the retrieval of information hidden in the preserved sample material. These techniques make it possible to reveal specific changes in the genetic material. Changes thus demonstrable include, for example, various kinds of chromosomal damage such as translocations, deletions and mutations. The presence of foreign DNA material – virus, for example – can also be demonstrated by these methods. In this way chromosomal changes predisposing for the occurrence of a certain kind of tumour or other diseases can be mapped and studied more closely. Thanks to the retention of large numbers of samples in various pathology departments, large bodies of material can be composed for particular diseases. One limiting factor in these molecular biological studies of the sample material has been that the DNA extracted from the paraffin wax blocks is inferior in quality to DNA isolated from fresh tissue. During processing of the tissues, the DNA is often affected in such a way that chromosomal fractures appear, impeding the use of the material. This is one of the reasons why the sample material sent to pathology departments often arrives nowadays in the fresh state and is partly

deep-frozen for future studies of different kinds, both medically motivated and research-related.

It is impossible to predict the new techniques which research may come to employ in the future and the needs this will generate for sample material from the pathology departments. Clearly, though, the length of time for which sample material needs to be stored is infinite, i.e. future preservation will have to be for an indefinite term.

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¹ SOSFS 1995:9 (M)

The industrial use of biobanks in Sweden: an overview

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Introduction

This chapter deals with economic and industrial policy aspects on the use of biobanks in different research contexts.¹ The main question that constitutes the starting point for this study is how different economic interests can be taken account of without coming into conflict with other vital interests held by individuals and the society at large. “Actors” with economic interests are primarily companies within the pharmaceutical, diagnostics and biotechnology industries and those health care and research institutions that administer biobanks. Given the fact that Swedish academic researchers, unlike the situation in many other countries, own the property rights to their inventions, individual scientists might also have economic interests related to biobanks.

Background

The bio industries, dedicated to satisfying the needs of the health care sector for such products as pharmaceuticals, diagnostics and medical devices, are by nature research-based. Their product development is to a large extent based on knowledge generated in research, carried out either in-house or externally by universities, institutes and other companies. By tradition, the bio industries have always been strongly dependent on academic research – preclinical as well as clinical. There are many different ways in which research results can be exploited by companies, including the use of scientific publications, acquisition of patent rights, contract research, recruitment of PhDs, and collaboration between industry and academia.

The pharmaceutical industry, in particular, has a long tradition of commercialising scientific discoveries and inventions. In Sweden, the two leading manufacturers, AstraZeneca and the Pharmacia Corporation (and their predecessors), have longstanding, fruitful co-operation with Swedish academic researchers. This has led to several product innovations that have achieved commercial success in the world market. The co-operation has been both formal and informal. In recent years, research-based biotechnology companies have acquired an important role in the development of new drugs and diagnostics. These companies, many of which are spin-offs from universities, further develop scientific discoveries and product inventions and subsequently sell the results, often in the form of a licence, to large firms. It is the latter who have the resources necessary to complete the product development and bring the final product to the market. In Sweden, a rapidly growing and internationally successful biotechnology industry has emerged during the last 10-15 years. As a rule, these firms have

close contacts with academic researchers in Sweden as well as abroad and offer their services to the international pharmaceutical industry. Besides the typical research companies, the Swedish biotechnology industry includes a number of successful manufacturers of research tools (equipment, chemicals, software...).

Human biological material has long been used in medical research. However, thanks to the great advances in molecular biology and other “modern” disciplines within the life sciences, the need for using cell and tissue samples from human beings has increased dramatically in recent years. In particular, the new knowledge about DNA sequences produced, for example, by the Human Genome Project, constitutes a starting point for intensive research efforts directed at identifying genes and their function. By studying relationships between the DNA sequences in different genes (and their variation among individuals), the molecular and cellular mechanisms in the body, and clinical information about individuals, new knowledge can be gained about the causes of different diseases and their development. In the next step, this knowledge can be used in the development of new diagnostic and therapeutic products. For example, the proteins coded for by identified “disease genes” can be made targets for drug development.

In conclusion, genetic analyses on human cell and tissue material stored in various biobanks will be an important activity in much of the research that follows in the wake of the human genome projects. Therefore, the increasing interest in biobanks demonstrated by both academic and industrial researchers is no surprise. It is a question of using already existing biobanks, which have been created for clinical or research purposes, and building up new biobanks within the frame of specific research projects. As discussed in more detail in other parts of this book, this interest may partly conflict with other vital interests, above all the wish of individual citizens to protect their personal integrity and receive guarantees that sensitive information (e.g., about hereditary disposition for disease) cannot be accessed and improperly used by unauthorised people. Another interest that may possibly come into conflict with commercial exploitation is the need of researchers and health care providers to use the biobanks in their own activities.

The industrial use of biobanks can take place in two different ways. One is for firms themselves to collect samples and build up proprietary biobanks that are used in internal research and development (R&D) projects. The other way is to co-operate with academic researchers or biotechnology firms that have their own biological material, or can get access to such material through a third party. In the latter case, companies can use information extractable from the material without having to build up their own biobanks.

There are several reasons why it is important that industrial firms should be able to utilise efficiently the information that can be gained through research on biobanks. First of all, it is evident that the industry plays an important role in the innovation process whereby research results are transformed into practically useful products that can be made available to the large mass of users and customers in the health care sector. No other actors have the resources and competencies necessary to perform this task. The new scientific advances in biotechnology open the way to completely new methods of diagnosing and treating diseases. In order for humanity to benefit from this progress, companies must be allowed to commercialise this knowledge. This includes the information embedded in the samples stored in biobanks. If the involvement of industry is rendered difficult, for example as a result of excessively rigid regulations, there is a great risk that the scientific discoveries, and the related opportunities to improve health care, will not be used to the best advantage.

Furthermore, from a national perspective there is also an industrial policy argument why it is important that Sweden-based companies are offered good opportunities to use biobanks, either directly or indirectly via co-operation with academic researchers. As explained in other chapters, Sweden seems to provide favourable conditions for conducting

this type of research and development. Thus, if the industry is given the possibility of using, in a reasonable way, the biobanks and related research resources at Swedish universities and health care institutions, this can help to increase corporate development capability and lead to new, innovative products. If in addition these products prove commercially successful, positive effects can be achieved on employment and economic growth.

Purpose and research questions

The overall objective of the project is to create conditions that support an effective and ethical use of Swedish biobanks. Within the frame of this goal the purpose of the present study is to analyse, from an industrial policy perspective, how different interests (economic and others) associated with human biobanks can be balanced. There are several economic and industrial political issues that need to be highlighted in order for us to work out a proposal for legislation and guidelines that take into account the different public, private and commercial interests.

There are at least two types of “actors” that have a direct economic interest in biobanks. First, there are firms that for commercial reasons want to have access to the biological material itself or the information that can be extracted by analysing the samples. Second, the biobanks represent a value to the academic and health care institutions administering them. First of all there is a value linked to the original purpose of collecting and storing the samples. This is normally scientific or clinical. But in both cases there is also a potential economic value, given the fact that others (i.e. researchers or companies) might be interested in using the material, and might be prepared to pay for it, or for the information that can be extracted. The high costs associated with building and managing biobanks constitute another economic aspect.

As mentioned previously, there is a third category of actors that might have an economic interest, namely the academic researchers who make patentable inventions based on biobanks and want to participate in their commercialisation. In this study, however, we have chosen to concentrate on the two first-mentioned types of actors.

As a first step in this study, we need to map the extent to which biobanks are used by Swedish firms.² Some important questions are: Which firms in Sweden actually use biobanks? For what purposes? Have they built up their own biobanks? Which external biobanks do they use? How do they use them? How are the ethical issues handled? What are the results? It is also of interest to find out what kind of plans the companies have in regard to biobanks and related R&D, and furthermore, how they look upon the industrial use of publicly administered biobanks. For example, what problems and opportunities do they see in this connection? What are their opinions on and wishes regarding the coming regulation of biobanks? How does co-operation with universities and health care institutions work?

Other important questions have to do with the effects deriving from industrial use. For example, how can the development and growth of the individual firms, and the industry as a whole, be affected? In what ways can the universities and the health care sector benefit from industrial involvement in biobank-related research?

In addition to the above questions focusing on the companies that use, or plan to use, biobanks, we are also interested in (related) questions pertaining to the administration of public biobanks. In this study, we do not attempt to map the existence of biobanks in Sweden. But we do also want to highlight the commercialisation issue from the viewpoint of the academic researchers and the health care institutions. For example, how are biobanks currently used for research, and in particular industry-related research? What interest has the industry shown in the biobanks and related research activities? How does possible co-

operation with industry proceed? Of special importance in this context is how the ethical problems have been solved.

Furthermore, against the background of the growing interest in using biobanks for various R&D purposes, important questions can be raised regarding the organisation, management and financing of public biobanks. This issue is relevant both for the county councils (i.e., the authority responsible for the health care) and for the universities. Given the value of biobanks for research, their high management costs, and the ethical and legal constraints, to what extent and on what conditions should the samples be made available for external use, e.g., for commercial purposes? How should biobank activities be organised and managed so that the samples can be used by external actors without coming into conflict with other vital interests, such as the protection of personal integrity and the need to use the material for internal purposes?

A short note on the methodology

The first year's work has mainly concentrated on making an overview of the industrial use of Swedish biobanks. Personal interviews, focusing on the questions discussed above, have been carried out with the two large pharmaceutical firms – that is AstraZeneca (or rather its research unit in Mölndal) and Pharmacia & Upjohn (today the Pharmacia Corporation) – and with a number of other firms that were known to use or be interested in using biobanks. These are Amersham Pharmacia Biotech, Arexis, Eurona Medical (today Gemini Genomics), Pharmacia & Upjohn Diagnostics (today Pharmacia Diagnostics), Sangtec Medical and UmanGenomics. In addition, two clinical research organisations (Clinical Data Care and Quintiles) and some of the larger biotechnology firms in Sweden have been interviewed by telephone.

On the biobank side, personal interviews have been carried out with the heads of two pathology departments at university hospitals, and with representatives of three research units that have created biobanks and have had co-operation with industry. These are the so-called Medical Biobank in Umeå, the Swedish Twin Registry at the Karolinska Institute, and the Geriatric Unit at Uppsala University. Finally, interviews have been carried out with a few other people having expert knowledge in fields relevant to the study (e.g., clinical testing).

The names of all the people interviewed personally are listed in Appendix 1. Most of the interviews were conducted during the second half of 1999 and the first half of 2000. However, contacts have also occurred later, for example in order to follow up on the development of the respective company or institution. It can be added that a lot of valuable information has been obtained by other means. For example, the project has arranged several “hearings” with representatives of different interest groups, and the author has participated in several seminars and conferences where biobanks have been discussed.

The biobank actors

To give the reader a feeling for the kind of “environment” in which the industrial use of biobanks takes place, the most important categories of “actors” involved in the creation, management and use of biobanks will be presented in this section. Figure 1 illustrates the current situation, including key relations among the actors. It should be noted, however, that the field is very dynamic, which means that the picture may look different in the future.

Figure 1. Different types of actors involved in biobanks

As a first step, two main types of public biobanks can be distinguished, viz. the health care-based and the research-based. The biobanks can be perceived as “actors” in the sense that there is always some organisation or person who, officially or unofficially, is responsible for the administration of the biobank. The biobank receives samples and connected information either from health care institutions (e.g., the treatment-responsible physician) or directly from the donors themselves, who can be healthy or sick persons.

In Sweden, large health care-based biobanks exist at 35 different pathology departments (altogether approximately 80 million paraffin blocks collected since the 1940s). The material, originally received for diagnostic purposes, is used in research carried out by the pathologists themselves and by researchers from other clinics. Other health care-based sample collections can be found, for example, at the hospital’s blood centres and clinical-chemical laboratories, and at clinics for oncology, immunology and medical genetics.

Within the universities, many research-based biobanks have been created by individual or groups of researchers. In most cases, these collections are study-specific and concern a certain type of disease. In recent years it has become more common to collect and store samples that can be used for DNA analysis, for example in connection with future studies on the importance of hereditary factors. Another type of research-based biobank is “population-based”. This consists of a large sample collection that is representative of a

whole population (i.e., there are no socio-economic differences between those individuals who have donated samples and those who have not). One such biobank investigated in the present study is the Medical Biobank in Umeå. In the southern health care region in Sweden, with 1.5 million inhabitants, it is planned to build up a new biobank consisting of samples from 50,000 randomly chosen citizens. The intention is to use it, for example, in studies comparing susceptibility genes and diseases.

As indicated in figure 1, there is some overlap between the health care- and research-based biobanks. The borderline is not always clear, since for example many research-based biobanks get help from health care personnel with collecting samples. Moreover, physicians working at university hospitals often have dual appointments. In the case of the Medical Biobank in Umeå, the university and the county council have agreed to share responsibility for the biobank. At the University Hospital in Lund there are plans to create a central organisation for all biobanks regardless of origin.³

Beside the public biobanks there are private firms, though not in Sweden, that collect biological material (and some information) from voluntary donors for commercial purposes. Samples coming from these commercial biobanks are then offered for sale to companies.

Needless to say, the university researchers using the biobank constitute a central actor category. As mentioned above, many of them are also involved in the collection of samples. Given the mapping of the human genome, which is almost finished by now, and the consequent opportunities for studying the relations between genetics, environment and disease, biobanks are of potential interest to practically all clinically oriented researchers. We do not know how many researchers in Sweden are actually using biobanks. There is no doubt, however, that genetic analyses are being included in more and more studies. This implies a growing need for co-operation between researchers and health care providers.

There are different kinds of funding actors involved in biobanks. While health care-based biobanks are normally financed internally by the county councils, special funding is in most cases needed in order to build, administer, and use research-based biobanks. In Sweden, experiences show that funding of the research activities, including sample collection, can often be obtained.⁴ But it is more difficult to get funding for the creation, organising and maintenance of the biobanks themselves.

In most countries, Sweden included, all research projects involving human subjects must be evaluated and approved by a local or regional committee for research ethics. These committees influence the conditions for using biobanks (e.g., whether renewed informed consent from the donors is required). In Sweden, the Medical Research Council in 1999 issued new ethical guidelines for biobanks.⁵ These are intended for the research ethics committees as well as individual researchers and companies.

There are, as one can imagine, many regulating authorities that in different ways influence biobank-related activities. In Sweden, two of the most important ones are the National Board of Health and Welfare and the Medical Products Agency. The former is the supervisory authority for the health care sector and by consequence concerned by the activities around the health care-based biobanks. The task of the latter authority is to safeguard the safety and quality of pharmaceutical products. It must give its approval before clinical trials can be carried out. For example, they would not allow collection of biological samples for DNA-testing unless ample justification can be shown for doing so. Sweden has not had any special legislation on biobanks, but in May 2000 the National Board of Health and Welfare submitted a draft bill on the subject.⁶

Given the focus of this chapter on the industrial use of biobanks, the companies constitute key actors in the network of biobank-related exchange relationships that (for analytical purposes) can be defined. The companies carrying out research where biobanks are used can gain access to the material in different ways. They can build up their own collections

by getting samples from health care institutions, directly from individuals, or by purchasing them from commercial biobanks. As we will see later on, though, Swedish firms rarely have their own biobanks. An alternative used by some firms is to get access to biological material via contacts with academic or health care institutions. The predominant pattern, so far at least, is that firms establish research co-operation with academic researchers, who in turn use biobanks in the sponsored studies.

Figure 2 illustrates the most important categories of firms involved in biobanks. They are found within four different industries: pharmaceuticals, diagnostics, biotech, and contract research. The biotechnology industry is not very uniform, but is made up of firms with quite varying operations. Here, three sub-categories have been distinguished. One is research companies using various biotechnological tools. The second sub-category, genomics companies, also have research as their core activity, but due to their focus on genomics we have chosen to separate them here. Suppliers of biotechnological R&D tools make up the third sub-category. Contract research organisations (CRO), that specialise on providing clinical research services, may also be involved in biobanks, for example, if they carry out trials where biological samples are collected for the purpose of DNA testing.

Figure 2. Different categories of firms involved in biobanks

For the last twenty years, the Swedish pharmaceutical industry has been dominated by two companies. They have now merged with foreign corporations and are parts of large international groups, viz. AstraZeneca and the Pharmacia Corporation. Besides these two, there are just a few smaller established pharmaceutical firms. Also the established diagnostics industry is highly concentrated. The dominant manufacturer of immuno-diagnostic products is

Pharmacia Diagnostics (previously Pharmacia & Upjohn Diagnostics). Of special interest from a biobank perspective are companies active in the field of DNA analysis. The undisputed leader here is Sangtec Medical, which already has a commercial product on the market. There are a few others, but they are quite small.

As mentioned in the introductory section, Sweden has a rather successful and rapidly growing biotechnology industry. This includes an increasing number of research companies focusing on drug development.⁷ As elsewhere, many of these companies pursue a strategy, which implies a linking role between the established firms and the academic world. Based on research findings they develop new products, which are sold off, often on a licensing basis, to “big pharma”.

Genomics research is not only carried out by universities and governmental research institutes. Especially in the USA, a number of private genomics companies have been established. The most well-known is Celera Genomics, which, partly in competition with the publicly funded Human Genome Project (HGP), is working on the mapping of the human genome. Most genomics companies, however, concentrate on more applied fields, such as the search for disease or risk genes and the identification of targets for drug and diagnostics development. In Sweden, there are as yet very few companies of this type. One possible explanation, offered by one of our interviewees, is the previous sceptical attitude to gene technology within the research community and the unbalanced ethics debate during the 1980s and 1990s. Erona Medical, with focus on pharmacogenomics, was the first company to be formed (in 1994). Last year, it was acquired by British Gemini Genomics. In 1999, UmanGenomics was established with the purpose of commercialising the Medical Biobank in Umeå. The exclusive access to this important resource is expected to give this company strong competitive advantages in the world market. Arexis is a newly established biotech company, that specialises in functional genomics.

The last category in figure 2 is the suppliers of biotechnological R&D tools. It is a field where Sweden, thanks to many years of excellent academic research and a small number of innovative firms, holds a leading position. Amersham Pharmacia Biotech (“AP Biotech”) is one of the world’s largest suppliers of products for biochemistry and molecular biology research. Biacore, a leading manufacturer of biosensors, is a spin-off from AP Biotech. PyroSequencing is a new company, which is now commercialising a unique method for DNA sequencing. The technique is especially well suited for analysis of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and therefore of great value to applied genomics. There are approximately ten other firms, but they are quite small. Some of them work with bioinformatics. That is an area that has not had a strong position in Sweden. Current investments in bioinformatics research aim to change this.

Finally, it should be emphasised that the bio industries are strongly international. It means, for example, that even the small firms go international early. The high degree of internationalisation is also reflected by the fact that many of the Sweden-based firms have foreign owners. This holds not only for the large corporations, but also for many of the small ones.

Some biobanks and their industrial contacts

The ethics debate on biobanks has to a large extent focused on the so-called pathology archives. The reason is probably that these tissue banks contain very large amounts of samples, which in addition have been collected and stored for health care purposes. Now, there is increasing interest in using them for a different purpose – research. Most of the

donors are unaware that the samples might be used in research, and that there might even be commercial interests involved.

By tradition, the pathologists have assumed that they have the right of disposal of the samples stored in their archives. When it comes to the question of ownership, though, the situation has been perceived to be unclear. It seems that the ongoing ethics debate has contributed to increase the uncertainty around biobanks.⁸

Within both of the pathology departments investigated, human tissue is often used in research projects. Some of the projects are in-house, others are carried out in co-operation with other researchers at the same hospital or other Swedish hospitals. In some projects, the pathologists collaborate with molecular geneticists. It is estimated that today DNA analyses are used in more than half of the studies. So far, the industry has shown limited interest in the biobanks. A few years ago, The Uppsala University Hospital co-operated with Eureka Medical. However, the company came to the conclusion that the pathology archives were of no great use to them. They preferred using study-specific research-based biobanks, one of the advantages being that the material is better characterised. Both departments have collaborated with AP Biotech. Some years ago, this company was developing molecular biological methods for tumour screening. As one type of activity, a number of collaborative studies were carried out together with clinical research groups in Sweden and abroad. The samples were sent, in coded form, to AP Biotech, which performed the genetic analyses in its own laboratories. The results were subsequently transferred to and used by the academic partners.

One of the physicists interviewed believes that the pathology archives have a limited commercial value, the reason being that they are too fragmented (few samples and patients for each disease) and that the samples and the information have not been collected in a systematic way (compare Eureka). AP Biotech, however, say they have obtained useful knowledge through the above-mentioned studies. Given their focus on cancer, major cost and time savings can be achieved by conducting retrospective studies where existing biobanks are used. They see the public biobanks as an important national resource that should be made available for research and industrial development.

Some brief information on the three investigated research-based biobanks will now be given.⁹ Let us start with the Medical Biobank in Umeå. It was in the mid-1980s that researchers at Umeå University began to build up this biobank in co-operation with the county council in Västerbotten (in connection to health screenings). The biobank is population-based and currently consists of some 105,000 blood samples from approximately 80,000 individuals. For each donor there is also clinical and other information.

Since the beginning, each individual has been asked to sign a donation form, which says that the sample is donated for “future disease-preventing research”. Today, the existence of this written consent is seen as a very important asset, since it facilitates the use of the samples for research. In the mid-1990s, the idea to commercialise the biobank began to take shape. At first, there were plans to establish joint ventures with large industrial firms. There were some discussions with AP Biotech, but the idea of creating a joint “service unit” for carrying out contract research did not materialise. Instead, the university and the county council decided to establish UmanGenomics AB (February 1999). This company has been granted the exclusive right to commercialise the knowledge about disease-related genes and genetic and biochemical markers that can be gained by using the samples and associated information. The agreements made among the different parties do not impede academic researchers from using the material, but other companies cannot get access to the biobank unless UmanGenomics gives its consent.

UmanGenomics has recently started up its operations and got its first customers. The samples and the information are transferred to the company in coded form and only after

approval by the research ethics committee. The analysis results are fed back to the Medical Biobank, which after a reorganisation is now part of the county's health care organisation.

ULSAM is a longitudinal study on mortality in different age-related diseases, which in the 1970s was started by Uppsala University's unit for geriatric research. When the cohort (2,300 subjects) was examined for the third time around 1990, samples for DNA analysis were collected. Some years later, the existence of this biobank drew the attention of Eurona. As a result, a research co-operation on the regulation of cardiovascular diseases was initiated. Eurona saw a potential in using the biobank, and related information and research competence, in its development of pharmacogenomic tests. A first product has been developed, but it has not been launched into the market due to Gemini Genomics' acquisition of Eurona.

The DNA analyses have been carried out by Eurona, which also has been entrusted with storing the samples in its premises. The reason given for this was that the company had better resources and systems. All samples and information have been coded, and the code key has been kept at the university.

According to the research leader at the university, the advantage of co-operating with the industry is that the company can add valuable resources. The main disadvantage is that the publication of the research findings may be delayed due to the patenting process. Another complication, illustrated by the Eurona case, is that strategic changes in the company can have negative effects on the project.

The Swedish Twin Registry, administered by the Karolinska Institute, dates back to the 1960s. Today, it contains data from more than 140,000 twins, which makes it the world's largest. The registry is used for research on the relative importance of heredity and environment. The data collection is carried out both continuously and project-wise. Biological samples have been saved since the mid-1980s. Owing, however, to funding constraints large-scale and systematic collection and storage of samples has yet to be realised.

The first industrial co-operation took place in 1996-97. Astra and Pharmacia & Upjohn financed a pilot study for a large screening project (some 60,000 subjects). Besides the interview data, blood samples were collected for genetic analysis. The main study is now ongoing, with public funding. The Twin Registry, however, has failed to get money for the biobanking activities. Later on, consequently, the researchers will have to get back to the twins and ask for samples.¹⁰

Both Astra and Pharmacia & Upjohn have shown interest in continuing the co-operation and support the registry in its attempts to get funding for the bigger biobank. At present, the level of activity is relatively low, probably as a consequence of the merger processes that both companies are involved in. The Twin Registry has been in contact with some other companies, which are interested in getting access to information. They are now waiting for the results of the screening study.

The use of biobanks in Swedish industry

As already hinted, the industrial use of biobanks in Sweden is so far quite limited. There are only a few companies that actually use biobanks and in most cases it is only done on a small scale. Some other companies have plans to start up research activities.

Table 1 shows with which companies personal interviews have been carried out. Apart from these, four other biotechnology firms (Active Biotech, Karo Bio, Medivir, and PyroSequencing) were interviewed by telephone. None of them have used biological samples of the kind dealt with in our study. A couple of them believe that they will use biobanks in the future and that, probably, it will take place in co-operation with universities. There are more

than hundred other biotech firms in Sweden. The possibility of some of them having used or planning to use biobanks cannot be excluded, but in the course of our study we have not come across any information of this kind.

Table 1. Swedish firms that are using or planning to use biobanks

Company	Category	Has already used Swedish biobanks	Is planning to use Swedish biobanks
AstraZeneca (Mölndal)	Pharmaceutical firm	yes	
Pharmacia & Upjohn	Pharmaceutical firm	yes	
Pharmacia & Upjohn Diagnostics	Diagnostics firm	(yes)*	
Sangtec Medical	Diagnostics firm	no	Yes
Arexis	Biotech firm	no	Yes
Eurona Medical/ Gemini Genomics	Genomics firm	yes	
UmanGenomics	Genomics firm	yes	
Amersham Pharmacia Biotech	Supplier of biotech R&D tools	yes	

* The biobank consists of blood serum only.

The use of external biobanks

With one exception, Pharmacia Diagnostics (with a collection of serum samples which cannot be used for DNA analysis), the companies investigated have not invested any resources in building up their own biobanks. Instead, the dominant pattern so far is co-operation with academic researchers. The latter have relevant research questions. They also have access to existing biobanks or can collect samples. The pharmaceutical firms have used biobanks primarily in exploratory research projects, for example with the aim of finding susceptibility genes and identifying drug targets. Most commonly, as it seems, the practical work is carried out by the academics. The sponsoring company is only interested in gaining access to the results and being able to make patent applications on possible inventions. There are other cases where the company not only formulates the questions but also carries out the research, with the help of samples received from the university. One of the companies says that in future they might be interested in also purchasing samples from commercial biobanks. In such a case, there would be no uncertainty with regard to ownership.

Outside Sweden as well, co-operation with the academic world seems to be the dominant mode in the pharmaceutical industry. There are, however, a few large companies – such as Roche, SmithKline Beecham and Glaxo Wellcome.¹¹ – which have built up their own biobanks. Some others, e.g. Pharmacia, have samples that they have collected in connection to clinical trials. In future, this material might be used for genetic analysis. It can also be mentioned that recently AstraZeneca in Sweden has begun to bank some tissue samples – so far, though, on a very limited scale.¹²

Besides the academic co-operation it is not unusual for pharmaceutical firms to buy R&D services from genomics companies. Pharmacia, for example, has linked up with Celera Genomics and Exelixis Pharmaceuticals in the USA and with Genset in France. AstraZeneca has made agreements with Millennium Pharmaceuticals in the USA and Oxagen in the UK. This last-mentioned co-operation is aimed at identifying the underlying causes of arteriosclerosis.¹³

Besides the drug discovery phase, pharmaceutical firms may also use biological samples for DNA analysis in clinical trials, e.g. for the purpose of identifying “genetic signatures” related to a drug’s effectiveness or side-effects. Up till now, pharmacogenomic studies of this kind have been rare (approximately one per cent of all clinical trials world wide, at one interviewee’s estimate). That the industry’s interest in genotyping patients in connection to clinical trials is rapidly increasing was shown by a study presented in the USA a couple of years ago.¹⁴ This picture tallies with the information we have obtained about Sweden. Nowadays, it is not uncommon for industrial researchers to want to take “an extra tube with blood” for future DNA analysis. That is not allowed by the Medical Products Agency, however, unless the company can give a good reason why the sample should be taken. None of the two CROs have been involved in building biobanks for the pharmaceutical industry in Sweden. One of them has good hopes that in the future such assignments will come, especially from biotech firms.

Sangtec Medical and AP Biotech are both interested in molecular diagnostics. Like the pharmaceutical firms they have chosen to co-operate with academia. As already mentioned, AP Biotech has carried out a number of studies with university groups in several European countries. Sangtec has established contacts with several Swedish groups, but the actual work has not yet started, since they are waiting for the regulatory situation to become clearer.

The genomics companies are in a somewhat different situation than the previous categories. Both Eurona Medical/Gemini Genomics and UmanGenomics are among those firms whose business idea is to sell information based on studies of human biological material (many genomics companies use model organisms). Accordingly, they need samples that they can work with in their own laboratories. Eurona has gained access to samples through co-operation with researchers at several Swedish universities. As mentioned already, UmanGenomics has access to samples stored at the Medical Biobank in Umeå.

Even if it is true that the actual use of biobanks for commercial purposes is still limited, the interviewees agree that biobanks will be increasingly used in the genomics and medical research following on the human genome projects. Regardless of whether the applied research is carried out in academia or industry, the outcome will provide the basis for developing new therapeutic and diagnostic products. Also when it comes to clinical trials, it can be expected that genetic analyses and biobanking will become more common.

Type of biobank

In most industry-related projects, existing research-based biobanks are used. They can be either disease-specific or population-based. The latter category is of particular value in the kind of hypothesis-testing studies where there is a need for large numbers of samples in order to verify suspected relations between genotype and phenotype.

Thus, health care-based biobanks have not been used to such a very great extent. There are several reasons for this, as has already been remarked. Collection has not been systematically and uniformly carried out, which reduces their usefulness in many of the studies that the industry is interested in. Moreover, the pathology archives are mainly cancer-based and therefore of interest mainly for companies working in that particular field (such as Sangtec and AP Biotech).

Swedish vs. foreign biobanks

The international character of the bio industries leaves its mark also on the use of biobanks. The large companies, i.e. AstraZeneca, Pharmacia, and AP Biotech, all have, or have had, biobank-based co-operation both in Sweden and abroad. Sangtec plans to establish co-operation with Swedish universities, but if the regulatory issues are not satisfactorily solved, going abroad is seen as a feasible alternative. The two genomics companies are more locally anchored. It is part of their business ideas to commercialise Swedish biobanks. It can be noted that the newly started Arexis has established its first biobank-related co-operation with an Italian university.

All the industrial representatives maintain that there are important advantages associated with carrying out biobank-related research in Sweden. The main arguments build on the availability of high-quality collections of biological samples, the excellent possibilities to get clinical information about the donors, the high epidemiological competence, and the fact that Swedes in general tend to trust the health care system, the authorities and the medical community. Thus, it is not only a matter of using existing biobanks. More important, perhaps, are the general characteristics of the Swedish health care and medical research systems, which facilitate clinically oriented research. This might give Sweden a chance to build up a strong position in the area of applied genomics. It is widely believed that if this happens and the impending legislation on biobanks is not too restrictive, there will be positive effects on the development of Swedish industry. Likewise, foreign companies can be attracted to establish co-operation with Swedish academic researchers. Whether this will also lead to foreign investments in local industrial R&D activities, is an open question. For example, there are people at Pharmacia who maintain that effective co-operation can be well achieved without local presence.

Another common opinion is that Sweden needs to substantially expand its research on applied genomics, if the country is to take advantage of the favourable conditions mentioned above. Given the large sums spent on genomics in other countries, especially in the USA, there is otherwise a risk that Sweden instead will lose ground, it is said. This concern may prove to be unjustified. The Swedish government and private foundations have recently decided to support major research programmes aiming at building up functional genomics research at several universities.¹⁵

The possibility of buying samples

In countries such as England, Scotland, Italy and the USA, samples can be purchased from commercial biobanks. In general, this is not considered to be a good alternative by Swedish firms, mainly because the clinical information is insufficient. The buyer may, for example, get information on what disease the donor is suffering from, but not how the patient has been treated and the results. The samples offered for sale may also vary a good deal in quality. The advantage, as perceived at least by one company, is that there is no problem of ownership.

Some viewpoints on the ethical issues

A majority of the interviewees, both from the industry and the universities, express dissatisfaction with the current uncertainty regarding the ethical rules and legislation. They would like to see a clear and national regulation that is equal for companies and academic researchers. Some feel that a new regulation is urgently needed, while others say that they can go on living with today's de facto rules. There is widespread concern that the coming regulation will be too detailed and may therefore soon become outdated. Given the rapidity of

technological changes and the tendency of ethical opinions to evolve over time, broad recommendations or guidelines are called for, based on fundamental and stable ethical judgements.

What many interviewees are particularly concerned about is that the demands on renewed informed consent, when stored samples are used in new studies, will be too far-reaching. If, when the sample is taken, its intended use has to be specified too narrowly, this will be perceived as very troublesome and as a barrier to effective research.

The current system of committees on research ethics is perceived to be a good one. But there seems to be a need for educating the members in the fields of gene technology and genomics. With better-trained committee members, the discussions could to a larger extent be based on grounds of fact, it is said. Among certain industrial representatives there is a suspicion that a “double standard” is applied by the committees, i.e. that the requirements for industrial projects are higher than for pure academic projects.

The company interviewees also tend to believe that the ethical problems are taken less seriously by universities and hospitals than in industry. It could be, for instance, that samples are used for research purposes without consent from the patients or without coding the information. Industrial representatives also maintain that many within the public sector are not fully aware of the strict standards and rules that are applied to industrial R&D (such as, e.g., the international rules for Good Clinical Practice).

As an illustration, it can be mentioned that AstraZeneca has formulated a special policy for handling the ethical issues related to biobanks. It can be summarised as follows: (1) informed consent should always be asked for when the samples are taken, (2) there should always be an approval from the research ethics committee, and (3) the company employees should never get any information about the identity of the donors. It is believed that most other pharmaceutical firms have adopted similar policies.

Another standpoint that has come up in many interviews is that the ethics debate on biobanks has been characterised by a great deal of ignorance. For example, it has sometimes been suggested that transfer of samples to other countries should be prohibited. Such a rule would not only prevent the use of scale-advantages, it would also to a large extent be inoperative, since what matters is the information, and that can easily be transmitted, e.g. by the Internet. Furthermore, the debate has focused too much on DNA testing. In many cases, protein analysis can yield similar information on heredity.

To conclude, our interview data indicate that the enactment of a bill that renders the use of biobanks for research too difficult might have negative effects on the possibilities of carrying out applied genomics research in Sweden. This would not only affect the scientific production (and possibly the development of medicine) but also influence the companies' location of R&D activities. The latter is illustrated by the Sangtec case. Unless the present regulatory uncertainty is solved in a satisfactory manner, the company will start searching for academic partners abroad. As a consequence, future product development and manufacturing activities may also end up in a foreign country.

Concluding remarks and plans for continued research

Without any doubt, biobanks and other human biological materials will become increasingly important for medical research. For example, the new knowledge about disease mechanisms generated by molecular genetics and molecular epidemiology will provide opportunities to develop new products for diagnosis and treatment. In other words, much of the product development in these areas will take its starting point in biobank-based research. A large part of this research will be carried out at academic institutions. It is a fact that more and more,

clinically oriented researchers are focusing their interest on the importance of genetic factors. But, as a result of the industrial relevance of this research, and the high costs involved, it can be expected that an increasing share of the applied genomics and proteomics research will be carried out in industrial laboratories. During the last five years, molecular biology and genomics have come to play an increasingly important role above all in the pharmaceutical industry's exploratory research phase. The aim is to identify biological targets and substances that bind to these targets.

Thus, many of the large pharmaceutical firms have added resources for genomics, bioinformatics and other new biotechnological platforms to their organisations for pre-clinical research. At the same time, however, there is a trend towards "outsourcing" of the exploratory research. It means increasing co-operation both with universities and biotechnology firms. The latter especially have come to play a key role in modern drug development. In the USA, but in Europe too, there are several leading biotechnology firms that have built up considerable resources for genomics and proteomics. This is a very expensive activity, which, coupled with the high commercial potential and the abundance of venture capital, is probably one of the reasons why this research is to such a high degree being carried out by industry.

Unfortunately, Sweden is lagging behind in this development. It is true that AstraZeneca and Pharmacia have incorporated molecular biology in their R&D strategies, and there are several successful drug research biotech firms in Sweden, but the genomics industry has been almost non-existent. There is today an embryo consisting of Gemini Genomics, UmanGenomics, Arexis and maybe a few others. On the diagnostics side, there is Sangtec Medical.

We have also seen that Sweden offers favourable conditions for conducting the type of medical research where biobanks are used. The advantages are the existence of high-quality biobanks and, above all, the entire complex consisting of the health care system, the research tradition, the national registration numbers etc., that facilitate the research activities. From an industrial policy point of view, an important question is how Sweden as a nation can exploit these advantages. How should the relevant research investments be realised? And how should the findings be applied to industrial R&D and transformed into commercial products? The latter is, normally, a prerequisite if the results are going to benefit the public. If, furthermore, Swedish firms take care of the commercialisation, there will be positive effects on the industrial and economic development. Obviously, biotechnology is a key industry for the future. In a long-term perspective, it is therefore important that Sweden, as an advanced industrial nation, should succeed in creating an internationally competitive biotech industry. The industrial use of biobanks can be one of several means to such an end.

The first phase of the present study has involved a broad survey of the industrial use of biobanks. In the next phase, the main focus will be on the forms of the industry's involvement in and exploitation of public biobanks. A number of important questions can be identified, such as: Which forms of co-operation between industry and health care/universities exist? What are the pros and cons from the different parties' perspectives? What specific solutions for handling the ethical and legal aspects exist, or can be developed? How should the regulatory system be designed so that it does not bring about unnecessary barriers to effective forms of co-operation? How should the biobank activities be organised at hospitals and universities in order to facilitate co-operation with industry, without causing undesired consequences that cannot be accepted by individual subjects or the society?

These questions will provide important starting points, when in the next phase some specific cases will be more thoroughly investigated. The focus will thus be on the organising of the industrial use of biobanks. The main alternatives are illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3. Different ways of commercialising biobanks

Alternative 1 is the traditional, direct co-operation between a product-developing company, e.g. a pharmaceutical firm, and a university department or hospital. As we have seen, the typical pattern in Sweden is that it is the academic researchers who have the samples, perform most of the work, and subsequently share the results with the sponsoring company (alt. 1a). In some cases, it is the latter that carries out the DNA analysis. Alternative 1b is a variant where the company, within the frame of a co-operative agreement, gets access to samples, which are subsequently used in the company's internal R&D activities.

Some of the genomics firms act as some form of middleman/intermediary between the established industry and the public sector. Eurona/Gemini and Arexis represent alternative 2a,

i.e., the company gets access to biobank-based research results and/or samples through co-operation with academic researchers. These resources are further refined and then sold to the pharmaceutical and diagnostics industry. UmanGenomics pursues the same strategy within the area of rare, hereditary diseases. But with its core business, on common diseases, UmanGenomics illustrates alternative 2b. It means that the genomics company gets access to samples that are used internally without the academic researchers being directly involved. Thus, when UmanGenomics gets research assignments from its customers, samples obtained from the Medical Biobank are used to carry out the work. The Icelandic deCode Genetics and Oxagen Ltd in the UK are two other genomics companies commercialising information and samples coming from the public sector. The former was established in 1996, through a private initiative, to exploit genetic, clinical and genealogical data about the relatively homogeneous Icelandic population. The latter is a spin-off from Oxford University. It receives samples through co-operation with scientists from different universities in the UK and on the continent.¹⁶

There are also, as illustrated by alternative 3, genomics companies with biobanks of their own. One possibility is to get samples directly from sick or healthy individuals. DNA Sciences is an example from the USA. It uses the Internet to recruit donors (www.dna.com).¹⁷ Other options are to buy samples from commercial biobanks or get them from hospitals. Also in the USA, Ardais Corporation, specialising in clinical genomics, has made agreements with leading medical institutions that will enable them to collect, process and utilise clinical samples that would otherwise be discarded as waste¹⁸. According to what we have heard recently from people in the business, however, the company will be abandoning this approach to sample collection.

The fourth alternative is that the product-developing companies, like in the previous case, build up in-house biobanks. Some of the large pharmaceutical firms have done this, although not in Sweden so far (other than on a very small scale).

As this discussion has shown, the use of biobanks for industrial purposes can take place in a variety of ways. It can be assumed that the different alternatives have different advantages and disadvantages as seen from the different interested parties' point of view. For the present project it would be of great value if we could obtain a better understanding of the various commercialisation forms. Alternative 2 above is of particular interest to us. Judging by initiatives already taken and the ongoing discussion in industry and academia, this type of indirect co-operation between the public sector and the established industry seems to emerge as an important complement to (or sometimes substitute for) the traditional, direct co-operation. It might be that the creation of one or several internationally strong genomics companies is a prerequisite for a successful commercialisation of Swedish biobanks and related research.

The ongoing development in Umeå around the Medical Biobank and UmanGenomics is an interesting case that we intend to investigate further. In fact, several of the interviewees have pointed to UmanGenomics as a possible role model for other parts of Sweden. But there are also those who call into question if the resource base in Umeå is sufficient to achieve international competitiveness. Instead, they call for a more large-scale investment, for example on a nation-wide level.¹⁹ Nevertheless, UmanGenomics provides a good opportunity to study the commercialisation of a public biobank through the establishment of a dedicated genomics firm. Also outside Sweden, genomics companies have been founded for similar purposes. deCode Genetics and Oxagen have already been mentioned. Since the business models as well as the environmental conditions may differ, we believe that it would be fruitful to compare these two ventures with UmanGenomics.

References:

¹ This chapter is a shortened version of a more extensive report in Swedish (Laage-Hellman, J., *Kommersialisering av svenska biobanker: ett näringspolitiskt perspektiv* IMIT-report, Institute for Management of Innovation and Technology, 2001, forthcoming).

² By “Swedish firms” we mean companies carrying on R&D and/or production activities in Sweden. They can be partly or wholly owned by foreign corporations. In fact, a growing proportion of Sweden-based biomedical companies belong to foreign industrial groups.

³ *Biobank vid Universitetssjukhuset i Lund*, The University Hospital in Lund, 1999.

⁴ For example, from various governmental research-funding organisations (such as the present Science Council and VINNOVA), various private foundations, foreign research granting authorities and industry.

⁵ *Forskningsetiska riktlinjer för nyttjande av biobanker, särskilt projekt innefattande genomforskning*, Medical Research Council, 1999.

⁶ The legal aspects of biobanks are dealt with in other chapters of this book.

⁷ According to a report from NUTEK (i.e., the Swedish Board for Technical and Industrial Development) there were in 1998 some forty companies of this kind. Some of them, such as Active Biotech, Biora, Karo Bio, Medivir and Q-Med, were relatively large (more than 40 employees). (Backlund, A., Markusson, N., Norgren, L. och Sandström, A. *Det svenska biotekniska innovationssystemet: drivkrafter och hinder för innovationer och tillväxt* arbetsrapport, NUTEK, 2000.)

⁸ The issue of who possibly owns or has the right of disposal of the biobanks is thoroughly dealt with in the chapter written by Li Westerlund and Annina H. Persson.

⁹ These biobanks are described in more detail in the more lengthy report in Swedish (see note 1).

¹⁰ In 2000, the Swedish Twin Registry was scientifically evaluated. One of the conclusions was that the biobank activities were important and should receive long-term support by establishment of a central facility for handling and storing of samples. (*Scientific Evaluation of the Swedish Twin Registry* FRN-Report 2000:10, Swedish Council for Planning and Coordination of Research, 2000.)

¹¹ The two last mentioned have now merged to form GlaxoSmithKline.

¹² Personal information from Professor Maria Anvret, Director of Molecular Sciences, AstraZeneca R&D Södertälje.

¹³ Astra’s annual report for 1998, p. 30.

¹⁴ Silber, M. *Importance of Pharmacogenomics – Response to 1998 Survey* Paper presented at the conference Pharmacogenomics – commercial developments and practical applications in Philadelphia August 1998.

¹⁵ For example, a 5-year national programme in functional genomics has been granted MSEK 800 by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation. At the same time, the government is expected to spend SEK 1.1 billion during three years. (See, e.g., *Historisk satsning på forskning Svenska Dagbladet*, 27 March, 2000.)

¹⁶ In the USA, Framingham Genomic Medicine was formed last year to commercialise data from the famous Framingham Heart Study in Massachusetts. However, the company will be disbanded since Boston University and other funding organisations for ethical reasons decided to not grant the company access to the data (Genomics company formed from Framingham heart study *Nature Biotechnology*. Vol. 18, August 2000, p. 818, and *Framingham Genomic Medicine to Disband after Denial of Heart Data* article published 29 December, 2000 on the site <http://www.genomeweb.com/articles>).

¹⁷ DNA Donation Site Draws a Crowd *Science*, Vol. 290, 6 October 2000, p. 7.

¹⁸ Teaching hospitals to share tissue with industry *Nature Medicine*, Vol. 6, No. 10, October 2000, p. 1072; *Ardais Corporation and Leading Medical Centers Launch Initiative to Accelerate Genomics-Based Drug Discovery* (<http://www.fkpi.com/Releases/Ardais>, 9 September 2000).

¹⁹ As described in more detail in the Swedish report (see note 1), a group of Swedish business people has presented a proposal for a national structure for commercialising Swedish tissue banks. The idea is to create a company, Svenska Vävnadsprover AB, that will build up a big, centralised database with genetic and clinical information. Another company, GenostiX AB, will get exclusive rights to commercialise the information by selling analytical services to the pharmaceutical and diagnostics industry.

Appendix 1. Personal interviews

Industry:

Per-Gunnar Bengtsson, head of the biobank, Pharmacia & Upjohn Diagnostics

Jan Brundell, Deputy Managing Director, Sangtec Medical

Mats Inganäs, staff scientist, Amersham Pharmacia Biotech

Ann-Cathrine Jönsson-Rylander, Associate Director Cell Biology and Biochemistry,
AstraZeneca R&D Mölndal

Johan Kördel, project Portfolio Director Metabolic Diseases Research, Pharmacia & Upjohn

Gunnar Olsson, Director Cardiovascular Management & Strategies Clinical R&D,
AstraZeneca

R&D Mölndal

Sune Rosell, Managing Director, UmanGenomics

Torbjörn Schröder, Deputy Managing Director, Eurona Medical

Vidar Wendel-Hansen, Managing Director, Arexis

Universities/health care institutions:

Gunnar Bjursell, Professor of Molecular Biology, Gothenburg University

Nils Conradi, Head of the Department of Pathology, Sahlgrenska University Hospital

Göran Hallmans, Professor of Nutrition Research at Umeå University and head of the the
Medical Biobank, County of Västerbotten

Gerd Johansson, responsible for quality and information, the Medical Biobank, County of
Västerbotten

Hans Lithell, Professor of Geriatrics, Uppsala University

Stefan Lohmander, Professor of Orthopaedics, Lund University

Nancy Pedersen, Professor of Medical Epidemiology and head of the Swedish Twin Registry,
Karolinska Institute.

Christer Sundström, Head of the Department of Pathology, The Uppsala University Hospital.

Others:

Torbjörn L. Möller, consultant, Five plus Five Management

Berit Westberg, consultant (formerly of AstraZeneca, Mölndal)

In the interests of efficiency and integrity

Mats G. Hansson

Research Program Ethics in Biomedicine, Uppsala University

The dual interests of the citizens

As can be seen from interviews in Jens Laage-Hellman's study in this project, there is a great deal of interest among scientists, pharmaceutical companies and public authorities in proposing legislation regarding the storage and use of human tissue samples. However, before this can be done it is necessary to identify the values at stake, values that the new legislation is expected to protect. The balancing of values has to acknowledge that different values are at stake for different parties. There is a pluralism of values as regards what patients, research subjects, authorities, the medical profession, scientists and the general public believe to be at stake. For some individuals, the most important values at stake are privacy and integrity. They would accordingly prefer legislation which strongly protects these values. Other individuals believe that biobanks should be used in the most efficient way possible, in order to generate new knowledge for diagnosis and medical treatment. For them, legal and ethical measures made too rigidly may actually be detrimental to the values, such as health and wellbeing, that they want to protect or promote. Overprotection could damage the public interest.¹ The legislator and the ethical review boards must find a solution to how threats to integrity should be balanced against risks of not gaining new scientific knowledge and new medical treatment.

From the perspective of actual and future patients and from the perspective of scientists engaged in the sampling of tissue material and the use of biobanks for research purposes, there is a dual interest in efficiency *and* integrity which I will outline briefly in this chapter. Patients want better, more individualized treatment with better control of side-effects. This is what research using biobanks in combination with DNA-tests and medical information about patients promises. From the perspective of patient concerns about efficiency, it is important that individual scientists or companies do not get full exclusive rights of access to the biobanks. Such a policy will exclude other scientists and companies to approach the material with other questions of relevance to patient health and wellbeing. However, the efficiency concern is not enough. The information attained and used is powerful and is a concern not only of the individual who has been diagnosed but also of all genetically related individuals. There may also be third parties such as insurance companies and employers with an interest in gaining information about the diagnosed individual and his or her relatives.² Accordingly, both actual and future patients may have interests in controlling who will have access to information about them. They have integrity concerns as well as interests in efficient procedures governing the storage, use and sharing of samples.

From the perspective of the individual scientists and the scientific community there are also efficiency concerns that should be taken into consideration before a model for storage and sharing of samples and associated information is selected. With regard to retrospective material that has been collected in association with ordinary diagnosis and treatment of patients or for

research purposes, there is a finite quantity that should not be wasted on research that is of poor quality or is jeopardized by inefficient storage and documentation procedures. With regard to prospectively collected material, interests of efficiency include a concern for quality and completeness of data and selection of appropriate storage procedures. This also comes as a reminder to the scientific community of the need to find appropriate models for sharing of samples and information. Developing and facilitating collaborative research among scientists and different biobanks is in the interest of scientific efficiency and in the interest of patient needs.³ It is also crucial that researchers ask well-defined research questions and that the biobank is used as a basis for formulating as many such questions as possible.

A scientist and his group have normally the exclusive rights to the material they have collected and organized.⁴ To violate this right is to disrespect the integrity of the individual researcher. However, this is a right the creators of a biobank should not stand on too firmly, since they are also dependant on other biobanks and data produced by other groups in order to get ahead in their own research. In the long run each scientist has an interest in defending openness within a framework of acknowledging the original contribution.⁵ The Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare has in a recent report suggested that an individual has a right to have his material withdrawn from the biobank and destroyed.⁶ However, such a right would seriously endanger the quality of the biobank. An efficient use of the biological material and the to this material associated information requires that the bank and the data are as complete as possible. An option to withdraw material or information would also conflict with accepted ethical and legal procedures for the use of medical registers in research, in many respects a parallel case.

In the interest of integrity

In the recent report on biobanks from The Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare already referred to it is stated that the “integrity” of the individual must always be protected in connection with research on human biological material. The term “integrity” is not defined, however, and therefore the requirement of protecting this value gives no concrete guidance to research ethics committees or researchers organizing human biological material into biobanks. We need to know more precisely what is really at stake when the “integrity” of blood or tissue donors is at stake. The concept “integrity” is complex and forms the subject of a comprehensive study of mine in another project. However, a brief outline will be useful here as part of an ethical analysis concerning the use of biobanks.

Within the context of research ethics a first distinction should be made between a principle of protecting or respecting integrity (hereafter the principle of integrity) and the well-established principles of beneficence and non-maleficence. In planning a research project the researcher and the ethics committee try to calculate and balance the expected utility of the project against potential risks of physical and mental harm to the research subject. The researcher must do his best to control all possible short- and long-term harms associated with participating in the research project. The rule of informed consent is applied in order to let the research subject make a voluntary and informed decision whether he is willing to accept the remaining risk and participate in the project or not. The principle of integrity may be related indirectly to the interest of protecting research subjects from physical and mental harm. A third party who gains access to medical information about an individual can use this information in a way that is damaging to this individual or to his property. Indirectly, though, it is two other basic interests that the principle of integrity is designed to protect.

To be in control of access of information about oneself

Different individuals set different limits to other parties' access to knowledge about oneself, and there can be great differences in this respect between different cultures. Even within a nuclear family, spheres of integrity may vary in size. One individual may feel that his integrity has been violated when he learns that he has been observed through the window by a stranger outside. Another individual exposes himself voluntarily, even as regards intimate details of his private life. Thus, even within a given culture it is difficult to define certain standards as to what should be counted as an infringement of the integrity of individual members of this culture. It must be up to each individual to define for him- or herself where the limits should be drawn concerning other people's access to information. The principle of integrity means in this first sense that it is always the individual who shall be in control of access to information about him- or herself. This principle may be negotiated in order for the individual to take part in social life, but in striking this balance, the principle of integrity in the second sense, as described below, should be taken into consideration.

Taking the principle of integrity in this first sense into consideration, one immediately realizes that the use of biobanks in association with genetic research and the use of personal medical information involve great risks of infringement of the integrity of the parties concerned. Genetic information about one individual is by definition also a concern of genetically related individuals. In connection with a DNA-test, an RNA-test or a protein analysis, the individual examined will receive information about his genetically related relatives at the same time as he receives information about his own genetic constitution, often without their knowledge or consent. Those concerned have no control over access to the information that is handed out, and so their integrity is violated. To obtain a voluntary informed consent from all parties concerned seems very impractical, and such a procedure may also come in conflict with the right of these individuals not to know about their genetic constitution and vulnerability, if that is what they wish.

If the examining doctor instead chooses to show respect for the integrity of an individual examined who, for various reasons, does not want to communicate the information to his relatives, he will have a problem in balancing the principle of integrity against the principles of beneficence and non-maleficence. The following imaginary example will serve to illustrate this genuine ethical dilemma. Imagine a patient who visits his doctor in order to get the results from a genetic test for a cancer. He learns that he is suffering from a malignant tumor and that unfortunately the disease has now progressed beyond any possible cure. At the same time he realizes that it was this form of cancer that his brother died of five years ago. He and his brother did not have any contact for many years. Had he been tested five years ago he could have been given effective treatment, now it's too late. It does not require much empathy to see that this situation is morally reprehensible.

It is difficult to say when and how, but it is evident that a doctor's primary duty to his patient must be expanded so as also to include those whose health and wellbeing is directly concerned by the genetic information available from genetic tests on individual patients. The ethical analysis must investigate different ways of balancing the integrity principle against the principles of beneficence and non-maleficence. In most cases the problems may be handled within the ordinary bounds of family morality. Different members of a family have contact with each other and communicate vital information to each other. Especially concerning disorders with a dominant pattern of heredity, the individual members have extensive knowledge about the disease and the family history. Genetic relatives in these cases often approach the clinical team on their own initiative. However, the problem is more acute when it comes to recessive disorders

where the individuals have no such knowledge to rely on. Even with regard to dominant disorders, the situation may be very complex.⁷ The development of genetic medicine implies a closer focus on the genetic family. However, in society of today, with new family structures and a blending of different cultures, this family may be hard to locate. The social family and the genetic family seem to be out of phase in modern society and, hence, the conflict between the principle of integrity and the principles of beneficence and non-maleficence more acute.

Respect for integrity as social recognition

The principle of integrity in the first sense as a recognition of each individual's interest in having control of other people's access to information about him- or herself must also be balanced against a principle of respecting integrity in a second sense: as social recognition. It is in particular Hegel who has discussed respect for integrity in this sense.⁸ Each individual has an interest in being socially recognized and respected as a moral agent. This includes appropriate recognition of one's contributions in society and an insight into the social norms and legal rules that, directly or indirectly, influence one's ability to play the social role one wishes to. In all social contexts, whether great or small, there must be room for compromise on individual concerns but the individual member must be in a position to understand and influence the underlying considerations and the rules that govern these compromises. Hegel described in detail three different forms of social recognition: the state, civil society and the family. Many people may today be skeptical of the Hegelian version of the individual's subordination to the interests of the state, but the element of social recognition in his political philosophy has been well accepted.⁹

The two versions of the principle of integrity protect two different interests: i) the interest in controlling other people's access to information about oneself and; ii) the interest in being socially recognized as an agent and a member of a moral community. That these two interests may come in conflict with each other is evident from the experience of the research ethics committees regarding applications in the area of pharmacogenomics. In order to protect integrity in the first sense the committee may want to select a very strict procedure for information and consent with requirements of written informed consent from all research subjects. However, these requirements may in practice constitute a violation of the principle of integrity in the second sense. The conflict is apparent to anyone trying to apply the rules in the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine drawn up by the Council of Europe.¹⁰ Article 22 in this convention states that: "When in the course of an intervention any part of a human body is removed, it may be stored and used for a purpose other than that for which it was removed, only if this is done in conformity with appropriate information and consent procedures". Strictly interpreted, this article requires explicit informed consent to be obtained from the original donor of the sample whenever there is a new purpose .

It is well known that the response rate in association with collection of data from any larger population is 70-80 % at best. Irrespective of how skilled the researcher is in formulating questions and regardless of how many reminders he sends out, the response rate will rarely exceed these figures. If explicit consent is required for each new use of material already collected, the effect will be to reduce the scientific value of the study, since not everybody will respond. The researcher will, furthermore, not know if those not responding might have been of particular interest in the study. If the research subjects learn to know that, in order to protect their integrity (in the first sense), a research ethics committee demands such a rigid interpretation of the duty to inform and obtain consent that the scientific value of the study decreases and, accordingly, endangers the potential for providing new treatment, they may feel that their

integrity (in the second sense) is violated. They would find it too costly to exercise a right of self-determination in a decision they would gladly delegate to the members of the committees, especially in cases when the risks are of a minor nature. To be recognized as an agent in a moral community is to be able to form the social systems in a way that implies an optimal balancing of risks and benefits. Perhaps they would like an organization similar to what has been accepted in association with research using different medical registries. In these cases it is an accepted procedure to allow the Swedish Parliament to make decisions concerning the establishment of a registry of great interest for the citizens.

A responsible ethical balancing implies that the requirement of efficiency must not without good reasons triumph over the requirements of integrity. The same holds for integrity concerns. They do not represent any absolute values that can escape an ethical deliberation. Regardless of selection of information and consent procedures the researcher and the committee is responsible for the values that will not be fulfilled as a consequence of the decision.¹¹ In balancing the different interests at stake the researchers and the committees may have good use of an elaborate system of different information and consent procedures.

Three information and consent procedures

The rule of informed consent is complex as such and involves several components that must be taken into consideration when seeking approval by patients and research subjects.¹² In addition, there are difficult philosophical problems pertinent to the task of suggesting appropriate information and consent procedures in relation to the use of biobanks. First, there is the plurality of values at stake in connection with different uses of biobanks. Information and consent procedures must take into consideration the kind of use in question: i) diagnosis for treatment; ii) quality assurance; iii) clinical research and; iv) epidemiological research. Different risks and benefits are at stake for patients and research subjects in relation to these different uses depending on i) the possibility and desirability of anonymizing information; ii) the seriousness of the disease; iii) the degree of heredity and penetrance associated with a specific kind of genetic information. In some cases it is not at all possible to secure approval.

The selection of appropriate information and consent procedures must take into account the different values that are at stake in association with different research protocols. It is not reasonable that the rule of obtaining an informed consent should be the same regardless of desired level of confidentiality and estimated benefit-risk ratio. The kind of information, the way it is given, the degree of voluntariness and the format of authorization should be adjusted accordingly. What should be considered appropriate information and consent procedures may then vary along a continuum with written and oral information and a signed consent at the one end, while at the other end of the scale it should just be a matter of making relevant information available.¹³ In a separate study of this project, Lena Lundberg and Åsa Kettis Lindblad will conduct an empirical survey focusing on information and consent procedures developed in order to test the accuracy of people's understanding and perception of the risks and benefits that are associated with individual research protocols. The respondents will be asked to choose between different versions of information and consent procedures, as judged to be appropriate in relationship to the different research protocols, i.e. i) making information available; ii) informed refusal and; iii) written informed consent. In the study by Stefan Eriksson in this project, the questions about informed consent is discussed in more detail. It is our aim to suggest procedures for information and consent that are sensitive to the values at stake and of practical use for researchers and ethics committees.

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Informed consent and biobanks

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Introduction

This is a philosophical study of the *normative* question as to how regulation of informed consent should be constructed with reference to biobanking. In this first interim study I shall try to answer three questions. Firstly, *what* does a person consent to when permitting a tissue specimen to be taken for use in research? In order to assess procedures of information and consent, we have to be clear in our minds concerning *what happens* when somebody takes part in research of this kind. Secondly, we have to know what informed consent *is* and what its *function* is to be. In the following pages I propose a model of informed consent and formulate three principles which can be used in working out guidelines. Thirdly, I shall be addressing the more specific question of what possibility donors should have of withdrawing their specimens and having them destroyed, my purpose being to test the possibility of giving a preliminary answer compatible with these principles.

Donation of biological specimens

It is sometimes claimed that specimens delivered to national authorities or institutions become State property. An alternative idea is that researchers own the specimens they collect. The National Board of Health and Welfare, for example, wrote in its general recommendations on routines for the preservation of sample material in pathology departments (1995:9), that “unless otherwise agreed, ownership of the sample material formally accrues to the party that has taken it”.¹ The question of whether the ownership model is suitable for biobank material is exhaustively addressed in a legal perspective elsewhere in this project, where it is answered in the negative. I would like, however, to say a few words on this subject without bringing law into it.

To many people, the thought comes naturally that their body belongs to them and that, accordingly, a state, a business enterprise or a researcher cannot claim to own part of it. Is it not fair to say that this is *my* blood and no one else’s? The newspaper Aftonbladet wrote that scientists are experimenting on parts of “*your body*” and that “they’re after *your DNA*” (my italics).² On closer reflection, though, this idea seems peculiar. Do we as a general rule lay claim to our blood, our body tissue or our body fluids? When somebody says, “This is my blood,” can we, for example, imagine the statement being made in the following setting? Some friends are seated together. When the dinner is being got ready, one of them suddenly notices blood on the floor. Someone of the company says: “That’s my blood.” Now the

important thing here is the fact that he or she is performing an act of reference – pointing out that the blood is really his and no one else's. In other words, he says that it *comes from* him and not from any of the others. Perhaps while saying this he holds up a hand which he has cut. Nothing is said concerning who *owns* the blood. I imagine the same to apply concerning body fluids and tissue. In normal circumstances there is no talk of ownership. When I go to get my hair cut, I don't decide what the hairdresser is to do with the clippings, any more than I tell the doctor what to do with the skin sample from my birthmark after he has examined me. Possession simply isn't an issue.

Now of course, this is not to say that the hairdresser or the doctor are entitled to do whatever they like with parts of my body. But the questionable things they could *conceivably* do would not inspire misgivings because of my right of ownership being infringed but rather, for example, because they did not show proper respect, because they disregarded a symbolic value (the placenta, for example, may be of great value to someone) or because they violate cultural taboos (especially as regards research among foreign civilisations). Arguably, then, scientists and doctors are entitled to use human biological material for research so long as the person supplying the material or people close to them are not harmed as a result. Arguments for this are easy enough to find. Either you can maintain, on grounds of consequential ethics, that, considering how greatly we all benefit from this research, we should do everything to encourage it so long as it does not entail risks or injuries of unjustifiable magnitude. Or else we can express ourselves in value terms. Scientific research has an intrinsic value, and so long as human biological material is of interest to no one but the research scientist, the latter ought clearly to have access to it. The circumscriptions to which this right should be subject are concerned more with matters of personal privacy and integrity than with questions of ownership.

This, of course, does not entirely settle the complex issue of ownership. If someone actually has an interest in their biological material, perhaps a court of law will have to decide the matter, and perhaps it will even choose to make reference to property rights. It would not, however, be a good idea to make this a dominant model, because that would imply a right on the owner's part to do all sorts of things which would prejudice vital interests. Is a scientist, a hospital or a state to have property rights in sensitive information about me and people close to me? As a general rule, whatever is owned can be freely sold, which in the case of biobanks would be disastrous. Attaching over-much importance to the waste character of the material would not be so felicitous either. The problem, above all, is that where abandoned material is concerned, findings is normally keepings, which brings us back to the difficulties already remarked on.

Non-ownership of the specimen one provides does not, of course, mean that one should have no say in the subsequent handling of that specimen. If a specimen contains potential information (information extractable from the material) about me and about my nearest and dearest – which, in principle, is the case with all biological samples – my rights and interests ought still to be acknowledged in some measure. This is what informed consent is meant to provide for. But this begs the question: *what* does a person consent to? To answer this question, one can either search descriptively for knowledge of what people actually consider themselves to be doing when they donate a sample, or else one can constructively design a suitable model. My purpose being normative, I shall be opting for the latter. The purpose of this project is to suggest appropriate guidelines for the management of biobanks, and I want to find a model for what the giving of samples implies, a model representing as faithfully as possible the values which are at stake, regardless of what people actually believe themselves to be doing.

One possible model would be *deposition* – entrusting something to another person for a time. The advantages of this variant are that the party in whose hands the material is

deposited does not own it, and it is made clear that what happens is in the nature of an agreement being concluded. One drawback, though, is that material deposited can always be withdrawn, added to which there is the implication of the person depositing the material still having some kind of title in it.

Can the giving of material instead be construed as a *gift*? A gift is a voluntary transfer of something with no consideration expected in return. This model certainly corresponds to a vital feature of certain biobanks; consider, for example, the donation of blood to blood banks. The British Medical Research Council (MRC) has proposed that donated tissue samples be treated as gifts: “This is preferable from a moral and ethical point of view, as it promotes the ‘gift relationship’ between participants and scientists, and underlines the altruistic motivation for participation in research.”³ The main problem with this proposal is that we generally give our samples on certain conditions, which is not the case with a gift. One such condition occurs when people expect something in return for their gift – perhaps information about illnesses running in the family or about their descent. One specially important condition is that we sometimes reserve the right to request the return or destruction of the biological specimen, which seems to be a highly relevant interest. In connection with the 1997 Council of Europe Convention, the National Board of Health and Welfare has even proposed that this right be guaranteed by law.⁴ Gifts, of course, cannot usually be retracted, so the gift model is not altogether successful either. It needs to be supplemented by a contractual element. Is the *donation procedure* which has evolved concerning the collection of organs for transplant surgery a serviceable model?

Organs may only be taken from a person consenting thereto (see Section 6 of the Transplant Surgery Act, 1995:831). Donation cards have been devised on which the conditions of donation can be indicated, and it is the physician’s duty to check for such conditions by examining the card or by several other means (see Provisions and General Recommendations of the National Board of Health and Welfare. Collection of organs and tissue for transplant surgery or for other medical purposes, 1997:4). A person may choose to donate all their organs and body tissue for transplant surgery and other medical purposes, limit the donation to transplant surgery, exclude certain organs and tissues, or refuse entirely.

The Transplant Surgery Act makes no distinction between biological materials and it also applies to medical research. Yet, for several reasons, perhaps donation would not be an ideal model where biobanks are concerned. Reference to donation in this context is liable to give the impression that biobanking can be regulated exclusively through the above mentioned statutory texts, which would not be without its problems. The donation procedure governs an activity whereby organs are collected mainly from deceased persons, whereas biobanks are mainly interested in specimens from living donors (preferably from initially healthy persons, a biobank with specimens of this kind being judged more interesting for research purposes than banks containing specimens from sick persons only). So the ethical issues at the centre of attention are somewhat different. Another difference between the donation procedure and biobanks is that discussion in the former instance has primarily focused on affective material (material charged with a special emotional significance and importance, which for present purposes means such large and vital organs as the heart), whereas the biobanks often deal in “leftovers” or comparable material. And whereas the ethical problems attending the removal of such large organs have generally concerned respect for the views of the individual on the subject of donation, it is above all questions of integrity that have been the moot point where biobanks are concerned. From this it follows that when the General Recommendations of the National Board of Health and Welfare (1997:4) state that next-of-kin cannot oppose the wishes of the individual donor, this is not fully applicable to biobanks. Genetic information from banked specimens *can* have a highly critical bearing on the privacy and integrity of next-of-kin, in which case it seems vital that they should have

some say in the matter. What is more, several burning issues with regard to biobanks – the possibility of withdrawing specimens and the feasible obligation of obtaining renewed consent before using the specimen for a new purpose – never arise where donation is concerned.

Thus there are palpable differences, but it is sufficient to observe that in the donation procedure we have a parallel to biobanks which, for all the differences involved, points to the possibility of biological material being conditionally donated. To avoid confusing the donation procedure with the giving of samples to biobanks, we can refer to the latter as a *conditional gift*.⁵ As the MRC remarks, it is part of our understanding of the nature of a gift that the making and reception of it confirm a special relationship between donor and donee. Accordingly, the person accepting a gift has certain obligations towards the person making it – above all, the obligation of using the gift in a way which will not harm the giver, which brings us back to the previously noted requirement of the rights and interests of the donor of the sample being acknowledged in some measure. The donor can also make stipulations, just as he may decide not to state any conditions in a particular instance. Our model, then, can incorporate both instances of specimens being given subject to vital reservations, and instances where someone makes it clear that the gift is unconditional. It should, of course, be noted that it is the task of the biobank and the examining committee on research ethics to formulate the conditions applying in a particular instance. It is the donor who *makes* conditions, but not necessarily the donor who formulates them.

The institution of inter-personal gifts, however, differs from the giving of biological specimens for research, in that gifts of this latter kind do not establish a relationship between individuals. True, the MRC writes that a relationship exists between the providers of specimens and *scientists*, but donation here most often takes place on a more abstract level, from an individual to what can best be termed the welfare state.⁶ In this respect the donation of biological specimens for research resembles the giving of blood: the ultimate beneficiary of your gift is not directly present but exists as an anonymous recipient beyond the institutional intermediary. And the relationship which can be said to exist in connection with the giving of biological specimens for research has as much to do with that remote individual as with the person who is the direct recipient.

Now it may be objected: Surely you can't give away what doesn't belong to you? But this is not necessarily true. Consider the following example, which comes quite close to the actual case (supposing that the gift can be said to comprise information, no less than it comprises the tissue carrying that information). If I entrust somebody with a secret, perhaps I am giving them something which, like a biological sample, has a delicate bearing on personal privacy. Before imparting the secret, perhaps I assure myself of the other person's discretion and stipulate certain conditions. But it would be absurd to maintain that I *own* the information which I then, of my own free will, entrust to the other person. It seems, then, as if in the *conditional gift* we have a model which can avoid all mention of ownership but can incorporate the elements of free will, assumption of responsibility and contract which seem to be of importance when discussing biological specimens.

Informed consent

To answer the question of the role and structure of informed consent in relation to biobanks, we need to define our view concerning the nature of informed consent and its role in relation to biobanks. Informed consent can be briefly termed an autonomous act by a patient or experimental subject (for present purposes, the donor of a specimen) who expressly permits a

professional person (in this case, the person taking the sample) to perform a medical action on the patient or to include the patient in a research project. The use of “expressly permits” instead of “consents” is prompted by the following observation. A person can consent to something without expressly permitting it. For example, a child can consent to a punishment without thereby accepting the actual introduction of the punishment. The same applies, of course, in medicine. For example, Robert M. Veatch maintains that the act of extending one’s arm in order for a blood sample to be taken is, if not explicit consent, then at any rate an adequate form of consent.⁷ But a patient thus consenting to a doctor’s authoritarian proposal is not exercising his autonomy. That requires something more, namely *express permission* for what is to happen.⁸

This, then, is what informed consent *means*. But from this meaning we can separate what informed consent is *good for*. In the latter case we enquire after the *values* which informed consent exists to safeguard, and those values bear a direct relation to the stipulations made concerning the process which exists to guarantee informed consent. Participation in the making of decisions, for example, is a value expressed in stipulations of this kind. Those stipulations may, for example, concern the *elements* to be included in procedures of information and consent. Stipulations of this kind are made with a view of attaining or protecting the value concerned. If the stipulations made are satisfied, we can say that informed consent *actually exists*.

What values is informed consent meant to safeguard? Ethicists writing about informed consent have defined it in many different ways, according to which values they find important. The literature includes, for example, the following views. Informed consent is a procedure or mechanism which⁹

- prevents damage from occurring,
- maximises the benefit which should accrue to the patient/experimental subject,
- respectfully provides an individual or a group with knowledge concerning risks/benefit, with a view to protecting them from exploitation,¹⁰
- expresses the freedom of the individual to decide matters relating to his own person,
- gives effect to the right of the patient/experimental subject
 - to responsibly decide his own concerns,
 - to be treated as a person,
 - to autonomously consent to measures affecting his own person,
 - to have a private life.
- expresses the relationship of credibility and mutual loyalty which should characterise medical practices,
- is meant to bridge the difference in power and knowledge between the physician/scientist and the patient/experimental subject.¹¹

All this amounts at the same time to a *legitimation* of informed consent. Because informed consent gives effect to these values, fulfils these functions, it is a mechanism which we find it important to implement and defend.¹²

Three principles of informed consent

In order to discuss the difficult ethical issues surrounding biobanks, it is not enough to say that consent must express autonomy and to identify the general values which consent defends. Those values must also be *concretised* in the context in which they are to be promoted, and *defined* in a number of more manageable principles. In this section I shall propose three concrete principles which together encompass the values enumerated above. They function in

the main heuristically. Thus, through them informed consent acquires a more manageable form. Insofar, then, as stipulations of informed consent exist, it is according to these three principles that our procedures and guidelines should be tested. Similarly, exceptions to these three principles should always be specifically justified.

Principle one: Each individual is *entitled* to decide for himself whether, by furnishing a biological specimen, he is to undergo an examination or take part in a study. This rests on the more general principle that no person should be used for any purpose formulated by others without himself having consented thereto. If we take the *conditional gift* model as our starting point, then of course no one should be forced to make a gift but should always be allowed to decide for themselves when the gift is to be made, to whom and subject to what conditions. In this respect, participation through the giving of samples clearly amounts to entering into a contract or agreement.¹³

This is a so-called negative right which cannot be lightly overridden by reference to another benefit. A cure for cancer would, it is true, be of inestimable benefit, but the researching of a cure is nobody's right.¹⁴ In ordinary circumstances, the negative right of determination over one's own person overrides the benefit which various common projects are capable of producing.

This first principle also means that the person should be allowed to decide the form in which the sample is to be used. By permitting researchers or others to use the sample together with identifying data means that I as a person am actually taking part in the research. If, then, a person is only willing to permit research using coded or depersonalised samples (or the corresponding data), this is to be equated with the same person setting a limit to what she is prepared to take part in *as a person*. Every person should be allowed to make this decision for herself.

The right of the individual, however, should not be automatically viewed in contradistinction to the public interest or to various social projects, for the self-same individuals said here to be invested with rights can also obtain provision for their interests indirectly, through social institutions. The prime distinction to be made, therefore, is between a direct and an indirect *form* of individual interests. As an individual, I can directly assert my interests by exercising my autonomy in various ways, but I can also obtain provision for them indirectly, through elected or appointed representatives. When a law thus impinges on my right as an individual to influence a particular matter, this need not necessarily be deemed prejudicial to my interests. After all, as a democratic subject I have elected a certain order of things in order to bring about legislation which provides both for my interests and for other people's. But this is no reason for denying the possibility of conflicts between the two levels.¹⁵

Three basic limitations of principle one are conceivable. Firstly, this principle does not address the question of every kind of material. Principle B21 of the Helsinki Declaration lays down that "[e]very precaution should be taken to respect the privacy of the subject, the confidentiality of the patient's information and to minimize the impact of the study on the subject's physical and mental integrity and on the personality of the subject".¹⁶ But who exactly is a subject in a DNA study? Research ethics attempts to safeguard the privacy and self-determination of individuals, but who is the person subjected to an experiment when the research scientist studies a genetic sequence? The newspaper Aftonbladet wrote that "nobody knows who owns *you*," but is it really *me* they see in the experiment?¹⁷ So long as a material is identifiable, there is a question of me being a subject in a more palpable sense. When on the other hand the material lacks any identifying information, the fact remains that I am the *source* or the *origin* of the material, but it seems far-fetched to say that it is *me* the experiment is being performed on. The question is, what sort of facts can emerge from the processing of the material. The research scientist can elicit a fact about me from the material he or she

possesses, but it may also be a fact about me and my family or relatives, just as much as a fact about my ethnic group, my sex or the human race in general. From this point of view, describing genetic research as the concern of the individual is an over-simplification. Thus it is not really surprising that several organisations have chosen to speak of genes as belonging to “the public domain” or of the human genome as being “common heritage of humanity”.¹⁸ Let us conclude that not all research using biobank material can be automatically equated with research on persons.

Secondly, just as in other research contexts, situations may arise when, for example, the interest of the general public or groups of patients in the materialisation of a certain kind of research may be so great as to justify restrictions on the scope of direct individual influence. This can be instanced with register research of the kind which is actually based on a statutory duty of reporting to registers, whatever the individual person’s attitude to the research in question.¹⁹ Research using biobank material, of course, can also be of such dignity that a research ethics committee sanctions a project dispensing with a consent procedure so extensive and expensive that the research would otherwise be rendered impossible or its scientific value seriously jeopardised.

Thirdly, and finally, sometimes it is not even in the individual person’s interests to be contacted. The risk that person is exposed to may be greater in the event of contact than when taking part in the study. In the assessment, for example, of a study of later consequences of legal abortion, contact was judged to be such a psychological strain on many women that the research ethics committee appraising the study judged it unethical to ask the women for their consent.²⁰ If the rights of the individual are to be infringed in any of these ways, it should be done with great restraint and following careful ethical assessment (by both researchers and research ethics committee).

Principle two: If a person is exposed to more than a *minimal risk*²¹ as a result of his banked sample being used for some purpose, he should be apprised of this and allowed to decide for himself whether or not he wishes to take such a risk. A person who takes a risk by making a gift – and therefore wishes to make conditions – must of course know about the risks involved in order to be capable of stipulating conditions which are adequate in relation to the risk. The risks can be of various kinds. The nature of them is more precisely expressed in the stipulations made concerning informed consent, i.e. the stipulations regarding what is to be included in information and may possibly be a subject of choice make clear which risks have been identified and perceived as significant. The risks included in principle two are those which a research ethics committee can foresee and can balance against the benefit or the gains of which research holds out a prospect. This means that the donor of a specimen is presumed to accept that certain information will not be communicated and that, for example, an ethics committee can make certain decisions in her stead. (On this point, see what Hansson in his contribution terms the “second meaning” of “integrity”.)

Thus the term “risk” presents us with a difficulty. It is often pointed out that many laymen and members of the profession have different ways of judging risk, not only in the sense of frequently rating the degree of risk differently, but also as regards *what* constitutes a risk. In this respect, “risk” is a value-charged concept. It is possible that documents of consent etc., will above all reflect the professional interpretation of risk. Close attention should therefore be paid to current ethical and political debate and to what pressure and interest groups have to say. This can help us to identify the values which are liable to be infringed and to initiate a discussion of ways in which these risks can be balanced with a maximum of moral sensitivity.

Principle three: One should always supply the kind of information which a rational person²² could normally be presumed to require concerning the use of a biological specimen. This principle is based on respect for people’s *integrity*: a person’s opinions, wishes and

values should be respected by those who interact with him. The principle also acknowledges the privileged situation in which the sampler's knowledge and power place him in relation to the donor. Like principle two, this principle expresses a positively formulated right, in that a balance should be struck between the importance of supplying information and the cost and trouble which this entails. A rational person, after all, will probably agree that a certain kind of information does not justify unlimited effort.

Referring back to the contractual nature of the gift model, this principle means that you can require "the contract" to contain the information which has an essential bearing on your desire to sign it and which it is practically feasible to include. In this way, principle three, like principle two, is contextual in a way which our first principle is not. That which a "rational" person would like to know is of course not the same in every context, depending as it does both on the person herself and on the circumstances.

The information which principle three refers to is of course frequently, though not exclusively, information about risks. But the term "risk" here has a wider meaning. Not all risks are of such a kind that one can predict whether individual sample donors will experience them as risks. A sample can, for example, be used in a type of research which the donor finds morally reprehensible, even if she is not directly harmed by it. This can be the case with research in a field which the donor, as an animal rights sympathiser, cannot accept. And yet, through the sample she has given, she becomes a party to the research. Another example is the case of her specimen being delivered to a business enterprise of which she disapproves and whose work she does not wish to support. In addition, there are conditions attaching to research which can interest individuals or groups but not primarily because they entail risks. The point at issue may, for example, be the role of research in social change or matters which, scientifically speaking, cannot be confirmed as risks but which, for various reasons, are nevertheless open to question. Information capable of shedding light on conditions like these may also be of interest to participants in research.

These principles ought primarily to be considered complementary. All three indicate *when* informed consent should be obtained, namely when the question is one of individual participation, when the person concerned takes a more than negligible risk by participating or if there are other reasons for supposing that the individual or the group to which she belongs would like to know what use their specimens are going to be put to. In this way, all three have something to say concerning the *content* of the information: each individual is informed concerning her participation, the risks she is taking and other relevant matters. How, then, are these principles to be balanced against each other? This is a hard question to answer *a priori*. Principle one has a logical head start on the other two: a non-participant cannot take risks or desire information concerning his participation. Otherwise I see them as mutually supportive. Should an experiment with biobank material mean that a person can be said to take part in the experiment, and then take a risk and, for other reasons, desire information, then there will have to be very good reasons indeed for not obtaining informed consent for the experiment.

Can the sample donor ask for the sample to be returned or destroyed?

The Medical Research Council²³, the National Board of Health and Welfare²⁴ and the Biotechnology Committee²⁵ all wish to make the donor fully entitled to revoke her consent. Their standpoint tallies with Section 12 of the Personal Data Act (1998:204), which provides that in cases where processing of personal data is only permitted when the person registered has given consent as the Act provides, the person registered is entitled at any time to revoke the consent he has given. On the other hand, a right of this kind runs contrary to the established practice of research ethics in connection with register research. If individuals

could recall the data/samples they had supplied to registers, this would detract from the scientific value of the register concerned. This unfortunate consequence is not only negative in itself: setting up a good-quality biobank, with adequate security etc., costs large sums of money, and so failure to use it as effectively as possible would be a waste of resources. It should further be noted that, if the specimen has been made a subject of research, destruction of the specimen eliminates the possibility of subsequently verifying and otherwise following up the research, which without doubt is a palpable deficiency.

How can we resolve the dilemma of desiring for the future both to safeguard the individual person's power of decision over his participation in research and, on the other hand, to make effective use of biobanks? Let us first of all distinguish between (1) revoking consent to further research and (2) retrospectively asking for samples, data and results to be destroyed or returned. When, in connection with (1), we are referring to unidentifiable material, then of course revocation/recall is impossible, and so in a case of this kind the question is irrelevant. (The legislation proposed by the National Board of Health and Welfare refers solely to biobanks containing biological material whose origin is traceable to a certain individual.) If instead we mean coded or identified specimens, then the first part of the dilemma outlined above will come into play (no research yet having taken place, there can be no problems of verification in this instance.) As a starting point we can observe that the possibility, in keeping with our principle one, of revoking consent to further research using coded or identified specimens, is an important right for donors. One should be able to choose whether or not to participate in research. And since not all the undesirable consequences enumerated above apply to this instance, that right carries considerable weight. But, as was stated in our discussion of principle one, that right cannot be absolute: there are occasions when good reasons can be given for departing from the principle. So even though, in the great majority of instances, it is natural for a donor to be entitled to revoke his consent and ask for the sample to be destroyed or returned, there seems to be a problem involved in denying the possibility of situations where exceptions would be ethically desirable.

The dilemma is still more forcibly manifested in relation to (2), above. Here the person has already taken part in the research and still greater values are at stake. The natural solution is to be very careful indeed as to what is agreed on through the informed consent procedure. Hopefully the majority of participants, on the strength of information supplied to them concerning these values, can accept the passing of control over the specimens to the biobank. From an efficiency viewpoint this should be the normal course of things. It is also perfectly possible to anticipate this in the conditions but to give anyone wishing to do so the possibility of making a written proviso. Otherwise, of course, it may sometimes be possible to only take specimens from those accepting the biobank's full right of disposal, without prejudicing the success of the research. In other cases, perhaps the possibility of verification does not require the specimens to be retained, and the donor's right of recovering the samples or having them destroyed can be part of the initial conditions. The circumstances of the individual case should be allowed to decide this. But the proposal from the National Board of Health and Welfare, in which revocation of consent includes destruction of the tissue specimen, has the effect of establishing by law the donor's right to have the specimen destroyed, an arrangement which, in the light of our previous discussion, seems rather ill-advised and ought not to be recommended. There is no precedent for any such inalienable right. As we have already seen, it is abandoned in the statutory requirements, imposed previously by the National Board of Health and Welfare and other authorities, concerning the supply of data to various registers. Research with the aid of these registers has been judged so valuable as to warrant a circumscription of the individual person's right of direct control over her participation. Similarly, research with the aid of biobanks appears to be of such great

interest to broad groups of patients and to society as to make it reasonable for donors at least to be able to consent to control over the specimens in this respect passing to the biobank.

Finally, a problem of demarcation. Both in case (1) and case (2) it appears reasonable that special circumstances and the donors' preferences should be allowed to influence the possibilities of revocation agreed on. Arguments in favour of control for the biobank appear to carry slightly more weight in case (2), while the donors' right is more accentuated in case (1). So where should the line be drawn between the right of deciding on one's participation in further research and retrospective requirements? There may be cause here to observe the stipulations concerning registers in Section 9 of the Personal Data Act (1998:204). That section lays down that the personal data protection official shall among other things see to it that personal data are collected only for special, expressly indicated and justified purposes, that the personal data processed are adequate and relevant in relation to the purposes of the processing, and that no more personal data are processed than are necessary having regard to the purposes of the processing. Insofar, then, as the samples supplied to a biobank are to be regarded as or equated with personal data, these stipulations are a safeguard against excessive conferment of rights on the biobanks. This, in other words, is a possible definition of "further research" as referred to in (1), above. So long as Section 9 of the Personal Data Act is complied with, there is no question of "further research", only of "special, expressly indicated and justified purposes". Research within these frames should be able to proceed on the conditions agreed on by donor and researcher, while research which can be termed "further research", i.e. is no longer confined within the original, expressly indicated purposes, should normally (a) be preceded by the procurement of fresh consent, with specific indication of the control which the donor is to have, or (b) be based on the premise of the donor in future being entitled to recall consent and specimen (for possible exceptions, see the discussion concerning principle one).

References:

¹ In this paper words of Acts, rules and regulations are unofficially translated to English, and the wording of the translations is not in any way to be regarded as authoritative.

² Aftonbladet carried a series of articles on biobanks between 10th and 15th April 1999. The authors, journalists Maria Trädgårdh and Magnus Ringman, were later rewarded with *Stora Journalistpriset* (a prestigious journalist prize).

³ *Human Tissue and Biological Samples for use in Research*, Interim Operational and Ethical Guidelines issued by the Medical Research Council. 1999. Section 2.1.

⁴ *Biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.* (including a draft special enactment on biobanks in medical care etc. – *en särskild lag om biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.*), Socialstyrelsen, 2000, published exclusively on the Internet, see <http://www.sos.se/sos/publ/REFERAT/0077-011.htm> (010106). See Section 3 of the draft legislation. See also the Council of Europe *Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine*, Article 5, <http://conventions.coe.int> (010301).

⁵ A proposal of this kind will be found in Knoppers, B. M., Human Genetic Material: Commodity or Gift? in Weir, R. F. (ed.) *Stored Tissue Samples. Ethical, Legal, and Public Policy Implications*. University of Iowa Press. Iowa City 1998, pp. 226–235.

⁶ This point is made in an unpublished lecture by Richard Tutton (Lancaster University) entitled *Participation in Human Genetics Research: Gifts, Identities, and Genetic Difference*. 2000.

⁷ Veatch, R. M., Abandoning Informed Consent in: Kuhse, H. & Singer, P. (eds.), *Bioethics. An Anthology* Blackwell, Oxford 1999, p. 524.

⁸ Faden, R. & Beauchamp, T., *A History and Theory of Informed Consent*, Oxford University Press, New York 1986, pp. 278. They, however, use the expression “actively authorizes”.

⁹ Several of these possibilities are stated in Dworkin, G., *Autonomy and Informed Consent*, in President's Commission for the Study of Ethical Problems in Medicine and Biomedical and Behavioral Research *Making Health Care Decisions, Volume Three: Appendices (Studies on the Foundations of Informed Consent)*. Washington, D.C. 1982, pp. 63-81.

¹⁰ This, more or less, is how informed consent is construed in the Human Genome Diversity Project, see HGDP North American Regional Committee. Proposed Model Ethical Protocol for Collecting DNA Samples. *Houston Law Review* 1997. vol. 33, pp. 1431-1473.

¹¹ Freeman, W. L., *The Role of Community in Research with Stored Tissue Samples in: Weir, R. F. (ed.) Stored Tissue Samples. Ethical, Legal, and Public Policy Implications*, University of Iowa Press. Iowa City 1998. p. 281.

¹² This legitimisation also applies to the three principles derived from these values and elaborated in the next section. This legitimisation can be termed *initial*. As Dworkin observes, the ensuing *test* of a proposed general principle is for it to be accepted in practice by other well-informed, rational and free agents. From Dworkin's (contract-ethical) viewpoint it makes no difference whether they justify their acceptance by utilitarian, deontological, virtue-ethical or care-ethical deliberations. Dworkin, G., *Autonomy and Informed Consent. in President's Commission for the Study of Ethical Problems in Medicine and Biomedical and Behavioral Research Making Health Care Decisions, Volume Three: Appendices (Studies on the Foundations of Informed Consent)*. Washington, D.C. 1982, p. 76.

¹³ An argument for the great advantages of a contractual model for biobanking will be found in Sass, H-M., *Genotyping in Clinical Trials: Towards a Principle of Informed Request. Journal of Medicine and Philosophy*. 1998. vol. 23, pp. 288-296.

¹⁴ Naser, C. R., *Researcher Obligations to Tissue and DNA Sample Sources. in Robert F. Weir (ed.) Stored Tissue Samples. Ethical, Legal, and Public Policy Implications*, University of Iowa Press. Iowa City 1998, p. 170.

¹⁵ These conflicts, of course, can be of various kinds. It may sometimes happen that an individual's personal interests are incompatible with that same individual's interests at societal level. If so, we have a conflict which, in a sense, takes place within that person himself. In other cases the conflict may be between my interests and the rightful interests of other groups or individuals.

¹⁶ World Medical Association, *Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects*. October 2000, see http://www.wma.net/e/policy/17-c_e.html (010301) .

¹⁷ See *Aftonbladet*, Saturday 10th April, p. 6.

¹⁸ Cf. The Danish Council of Ethics. *Ethics and Mapping of the Human Genome*, 1993; Hugo Ethics Committee – Statement on Benefit Sharing, *Eubios Journal of Asian and International Bioethics*, vol. 10. 2000, pp. 70-72; UNESCO, *Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights*, 1997.

¹⁹ The *Epidemiology Centre of the National Board of Health and Welfare* maintains a number of such registers, e.g. the Abortions Register, the Cancer Register and the Patients Register. The importance of register research is discussed in Smedby, B., Westin, C-G., Adami, H-O., *Forskningens behov av centrala register, Rapport till utredningen om informationsstrukturen för hälso- och sjukvården, in SOU 1991:17, Forskning och utveckling – epidemiologi, kvalitetssäkring och Spris utvecklingsprojekt*.

²⁰ Information booklet by Medicinska forskningsrådet. *Registerdata i forskningen*. Stockholm 1987, p. 15.

²¹ “Minimal risk” being taken to imply approximately the risk which people normally take in their everyday lives and which is then deemed acceptable.

²² The definition of a rational person is best described in a formulation which has several times been used by the ECJ. Concerning, for example, the supply of information on packagings, it has spoken of considering “the presumed expectations of an average consumer who is reasonably well-informed and reasonably observant and circumspect” (European Court of Justice 16 July 1998, Case C-210/96). Unlike the ECJ, however, I would rather not stress the “average” aspect, one point of the principle being its contextuality, i.e. that it is meant to draw our attention to the wishes which this particular person may conceivably entertain when approached, in a concrete situation, on the subject of taking part in research.

²³ Medicinska forskningsrådet, *Research Ethics Guidelines for Using Biobanks, Especially Projects Involving Genome Research*. 1999.

²⁴ *Biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.* (including a draft special enactment on biobanks in medical care etc. – *en särskild lag om biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.*), Socialstyrelsen, 2000, published exclusively on the Internet, see <http://www.sos.se/sos/publ/REFERAT/0077-011.htm> (010106).

²⁵ Bioteknikkommitténs slutbetänkande SOU 2000:103: *Att spränga gränser. Bioteknikens möjligheter och risker*, Stockholm 2000.

Empirical research on informed consent and biobanks

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Introduction

Obtaining the informed consent of patients and research subjects is now an expected part of clinical medicine and research. Offering the individual the right to refuse participation, or revoke an informed consent without risking any negative consequences on subsequent care, protects the autonomy of the individual¹.

The rapid development of biotechnological research has stimulated the establishment of new biobanks, and the use of existing biobanks. The Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare suggests that informed consent must be present when collecting information for new biobanks². However, the situation is more complicated in relation to already existing biobanks, since it is often uncertain whether previous consent exists or not. The Swedish Research Council recommended in their guidelines that the use of existing biobanks should be accompanied by approval by the research ethics committee, which may lead to practical and methodological problems³. It is of immense concern to balance the possible conflicts of interests that may come up, i.e., sample donors' and their relatives' integrity/autonomy versus altruism. Up until now, no empirical studies have explored these issues in the context of biobanks. Knowledge of potential sample donors' perceptions regarding the use of biobanks is valuable in developing appropriate informed consent procedures for use in clinical practice and in research settings.

The overall aim is to empirically identify perceptions of the general public, blood donors and patients regarding i) risks and benefits of the use of biobanks, and ii) informed consent procedures in relation to the use of material from biobanks.

Material and methods

The study is based on a self-administered questionnaire that will be sent to a random sample of i) the general public; ii) blood donors; and iii) patients. In the questionnaire, the respondents are asked to rate the risks and benefits that they believe are associated with different uses of biobanks. A number of realistic examples will be presented for this purpose. The examples cover use of material from biobanks in a variety of research settings and in clinical practice, e.g. screening for phenylketonuria, development of pharmacogenetic tests, and routine diagnostic procedures. For each example, the respondents will be asked to grade perceived risks and benefits to themselves, their relatives and, actual and future patients on a Visual Analogue Scale. Next, the respondents are asked to state whether they would consent or refuse to participate in the examples given. In a second part of the questionnaire, the respondents will also be asked to tie a preferred consent procedure to each example. The options include i) no consent required, ii) informal consent procedure with access to

information up on request, and iii) extensive written informed consent procedure. The questionnaire will also include demographic variables and, for example, risk attitudes/behaviour and sense of coherence.

Results and implications

This design will make it possible to identify efficiency-pleaders and integrity-pleaders. Efficiency-pleaders would be those who choose informal consent procedures, even though the risks are considerable and the benefits are limited. Integrity-pleaders, on the other hand, are those who require extensive written consent procedures even though the benefits are substantial and the risks limited. There may be several intermediate “pleaders” between these two extremes. The results will form the basis for recommendations of how informed consent may be obtained in relation to the collection/use of material in biobanks.

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¹ Faden, R. R & Beauchamp, T. L., *A history and theory of informed consent*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 1986.

² National Board of Health and Welfare: Biobanks in health care etc (Biobanker i hälso-och sjukvården mm). 2000.

³ The Swedish Research Council: Research ethical guidelines for biobanks (Forskningsetiska riktlinjer för biobanker). 1999

Biobanks and the Rights to the Human Body

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Introduction

This article will investigate how to protect the rights to the body in the perspective of the Western legal, ethical and religious tradition. The new commodification of the human body represents a major challenge to this tradition¹. On this basis I will discuss who has property rights over the human body and the individual's rights to dispose over body parts.

Modernity and commodification of human bodies

In a historical perspective the use of the human body as medical resource or research object is not new but a part of the social and cultural life of the Western world. According to cultural anthropology our conceptions of the body are characterized by the tension between “the grotesque and the sacred”. Western culture is marked by the conflicting conceptions of the body. It distinguishes between the dead body, independent body parts and the lived body that is an integrated part of the human person.

The French legal philosopher Jean-Pierre Baud has argued that instead of only focusing on the lived body of the person we should examine the cultural status of the dead body². The dead body can both be described as 1. an object and a material thing. 2. a sacred object indicating the spirituality of the human person. The feelings of the grotesque and the sacred in the dead body are determined by the fact that the dead body expresses the presence of mortality in human existence. The grotesque character of body parts reminds us of the fact that the lived body in reality is a thing and that the person is an abstraction from this objectified way of being.

In modernity, medical technology and science are no longer restoring the body to a natural condition. Today we are also remodeling the body³. However, the tension between person and thing remains central in the industrial use of human bodies and body parts. Medicine does not teach us how to die. Death seems to be something very strange and far removed from human existence. In an increased technological culture, the body might be seen as “La part maudite”, the inescapable other of human personal existence. In technoscience the body is considered as a machine that we in principle could repair and change indefinitely. We live in a close interaction between humans and machines. The body has become an object among other objects⁴. Many of the visions connected with biobanks are based on this idea of the human body as mere object of production.

This can be illustrated by the famous case of John Moore, the man with the golden cells⁵. John Moore who lived in Alaska had been treated for a very rare leukemia. His physician lived in California, and he continued to come for check-ups by his doctor. After a number of years he realized that the physician was very interested in his cells and that they

had been used to create a medical product. Moore discovered that he had become MO-cell-line and that the physicians had earned millions of dollars on his cells, but they refused to give him a share of the earnings.

Accordingly, Moore sued the physicians at the California Court. The Court judged that he had the rights to his own body and should have a share in the economic gains. The physicians appealed the decision to the Appellee Court. This Court came up with the opposite judgment. It stated that it should be considered as contrary to the dignity of Moore to sell his own body. However, he should have compensation for malpractice because the physician had not informed him about the use of his cells and he had had no possibility of refusing the development of the cell-line.

The John Moore Case is interesting because it displays many of the central problems with regard to biobanks. It illustrates the possibilities of commercial gain and profit when using human biological materials. It raises the difficult problem of whether the human body should be subject to scientific patents. But the case also shows the vulnerability of research being dependent on Moore's informed consent in order to use the cells for research and development of new medicine. The dilemma of commodification of the human body is a tension between individual rights to dispose over bodies and respect for freedom of research and commercial production.

Ethical principles and protection of human individuals

Classical principles are the ethical ideas of protection of autonomy, dignity, integrity and vulnerability. These principles are founded on philosophical and anthropological theory of the human body.

i) Autonomy should not only be interpreted in the liberal sense of "permission", instead five aspects of autonomy should be put forward⁶: i) the capacity of creation of ideas and goals for life, ii) the capacity of moral insight, "self-legislation" and privacy, iii) the capacity of rational decision and action without coercion, iv) the capacity of political involvement and personal responsibility, v) the capacity of informed consent. However, autonomy remains merely an ideal, because of the structural limitations given to it by human weakness and dependence on biological, material and social conditions, lack of information for reasoning etc.

On this basis, autonomy defends the rights of the individual to dispose over his own body. This includes a right to refuse a certain use of body parts. However, autonomy as an ethical requirement excludes individuals who do not have this capacity, dead bodies, including minors, incapacitated persons, fetuses etc. In these cases it is necessary to find alternative representatives for making the decision.

ii) Dignity should not be reduced to autonomy⁷. Although originally a virtue of outstanding persons and a virtue of self-control in healthy life – qualities which can be lost, for instance by lack of responsibility or in extreme illness – it has been universalized as a quality of the person as such. It now refers to both the intrinsic value of the individual and the intersubjective value of every human being in their encounter with the other. Dignity concerns both oneself and the other person: I must behave with dignity, and I must consider the dignity of the other person; I must not give up civilized and responsible behavior, and the other person should not be commercialized and enslaved. Defined as an intrinsic value and as an intersubjective dimension of respect for the living person, the dignity of the human body mainly refers to what it can be dignified to do with human beings.

We should recognize the respect for the dead as an essential requirement. This limits the use of dead bodies in biobanks. Here religious traditions, the ethical worldview of the deceased and his or her family might play a role in their decision-making. But dignity in

general demands respect for the person in using the material. This means that confidentiality, respect for autonomy etc. is a part of the treatment of tissue from dead bodies.

With regard to living persons, respect for their dignity implies the use of their material for medically and scientifically justified purposes. This might mean that certain purely commercial uses are contrary to the dignity of the person. Some research aims, such as genetic enhancement, creation of human animal hybrids and cloning have been mentioned as contrary to human dignity.

Moreover, there is an important responsibility with regard to use of human tissue of fetuses for therapeutic purposes. Here, the intrinsic value of human life is at stake and we have to acknowledge that there are some things a society, due to respect for human dignity, simply will not do.

iii) Integrity accounts for the inviolability of human beings⁸. Although originally a virtue of uncorrupt character, expressing uprightness, honesty and good intentions, it has, like dignity, been universalized as a quality of the person as such. Thus it refers to the coherence of life that should not be touched and destroyed. It is coherence of life that is remembered from experiences and therefore can be told in a narrative. Moreover, respect for integrity is respect for privacy and in particular for the patient's understanding of his or her life and illness. Integrity is the most important principle for the creation of trust between physician and patient, because it demands that the physician listens to the patient telling the story of his or her life and illness.

With regard to integrity it is clear that personal privacy should be respected in the use of human material in biobanks. This involves respect for the individual identity of the person when using biomaterial. There is a close connection between the personal understanding of bodily harmony and the use of body tissue that would be permitted by the individual. The reference to the individual's integrity means that tissue must not be used in a way that violates the connection between personal identity and integrity.

iv) Vulnerability concerns integrity as a basic principle for respect for and protection of human and non-human life⁹. It expresses the condition of all life as prone to be hurt, wounded and killed. Vulnerability concerns animals and all self-organizing life in the world, and for mankind it must be considered a universal expression of the human condition. The idea of the protection of vulnerability can therefore create a bridge between moral strangers in a pluralistic society, and respect for vulnerability should be essential to policy-making in the modern welfare state. Respect for vulnerability is not a demand for perfect and immortal life, but recognition of the finitude of life and in particular the suffering presence of human beings.

The idea of vulnerability, being of a different nature from the other principles, challenges the rationality of the developments of biobanks. The question is whether the distribution and storage of human tissue is a legitimate medical use of resources. To use vulnerability as an ethical idea means fighting both mortality and disease, but it also includes an awareness of the additional human vulnerability that might be created in the biobanks project.

Ownership of human bodies

Contemporary biotechnological developments are accompanied by the fear that commodification of human tissue and DNA will lead to exploitation of dignity and integrity of innocent individuals. Ethical principles and historical traditions can constitute powerful arguments against direct commodification of the human body. The main problem is if we can understand ownership in terms of rights to disposal over the human body, that is rights to make the decisions over the use of the body.

Historically, it is the liberal philosopher John Locke to whom the view of the body as property is ascribed. He argues that the principle of autonomy provides a basis for ownership of the body¹⁰. The foundation for the social contract is that individuals own their own bodies and products of the body because the latter come from their labor or other activities. The basis of a free society is the individual's right of ownership. This liberal position has many adherents today. It is often combined with utilitarian arguments to the effect that ownership is the most efficient way of ensuring individual disposal over the body. Utilitarians think that ownership based on autonomy gives individuals the most extended rights over their bodies. This theory does not state that ownership is in conflict with ethical principles of dignity and integrity. According to the liberal position, these ideas are based on autonomy and respect for these principles will automatically include respect for these other ideas because they can be reduced to autonomy.

The Lockean and utilitarian view is, however, criticized. With Immanuel Kant we can argue that commodification of human beings as moral agents is a violation of human dignity. If the body is the person the result of commodification there is a reduction of human beings to mere objects. The connection between person and body means that bodies cannot be considered as a commodity. However, the difficulty with this position is that some parts of the body, even those in a special sphere between person and thing (e.g. compensation for blood or sperm donation), are sold without this seeming to be a violation of human dignity. The answer to this objection is to suggest that body parts but not the whole body might be regarded as "special commodities" situated in a special sphere of social exchange. We would of course never permit a market of whole persons, but within strict rules of compensation it might be possible to establish a room for exchange of particular body products.

This kind of argument may be supported by the phenomenological tradition in Western philosophy. Edmund Husserl distinguishes between "Leib" and "Körper", between the lived body, the body from the perspective of the person and the body seen from the outside as an object in time and space¹¹. Maurice Merleau-Ponty points to the lived experience of human individuality, to the close connection between person and body, and he refuses to reduce the body to an object.¹² In a somewhat different manner, Jean-Paul Sartre insists on the fact that the body is an ambiguous foundation of the lived human existence¹³. The body is the basis for sensation, life, freedom and desire to exist. But human beings transcend their bodies and relate to themselves as mere things. The experience of the body is simultaneously a perception of subjectivity and objectivity. This ambiguity is also a tension. From this perspective we can understand why commodification of the human body always runs the risk of violating the lived experience of humanity, considering the human person as a mere object in a world among other things.

Moreover, taking into account the tension between person and thing in the experience of the body, a widely used alternative to commercialization of the human body is to conceive the notion of biobank in the perspective of an economy of the gift¹⁴. This third logic of the gift is an alternative to a pragmatic utilitarian logic on the one hand, and on the other hand the economic logic of the gift implies principles separating the body from the intimacy of the person. The logic of the gift is based on the idea of the body as something between person and thing. Basic principles in such an economy of the gift in order to organize a system of distributions of tissue and body parts are the ideas of informed consent, anonymity, generosity, solidarity, respect for dignity and acknowledgement of dependence on community. This organization of distribution of body parts is based on the fundamental ethical principles of autonomy, dignity, integrity and vulnerability.

Another major challenge to the concept of ownership in biobanks is the right to decide over the body in public or private storage of bio-information. There is a difference between administrative storage of information in medical treatment and storage of information in order to use it for scientific research. Scientific use of bio-information is very different from

administrative use of information, because it has no immediate impact on medical treatment¹⁵. However, storage of information for medical purposes involves major ethical issues. It is possible for outsiders to acquire new knowledge about the issue, and this might involve a major violation of individuals' right of privacy.

In this context the researcher might claim the right to dispose over the body, and this is very close to ownership: There will be no change in the ownership of the tissue, but the researcher in the private or public sector will use the tissue for different purposes. The traditional concept of ownership is difficult to apply, because the information can so easily be used in different treatment or scientific contexts. One could argue that some information cannot be subject to ownership, for example anonymous information used in different scientific investigations as a basis for medical treatment.

However, the researcher might still insist that his intellectual property rights should be protected. The researcher can state that rights of the inventor of a cell line or a genetic structure prevail over the rights of the donor. The argument is that researchers have made a significant effort in order to construct a new product and this effort should be rewarded. Researchers should be allowed an award for their labor. In Lockean terms it might be said that they are entitled to the products of their own work.

The argument is valid, but does not mean that the whole human body can be subject to patents. The primacy of human embodiment represents an important argument against patenting. In the perspective of general principles of rejection of ownership of the human body, the human body as such, as raw material delivered from the individual, in whatever form, cell, organ, gene etc. cannot be patented. But when there has been an intervention in the human body, using technical devices made by the researchers, and this has transformed the body parts into another product, a different situation applies. As long as the original removal of the body parts has taken place by agreement with the donor -with his informed consent – and as long as the removal does not violate basic ethical principles, the scientific process can be patented because it is no longer identical to the human body but has been subjected to scientific innovation and transformation. It is now a technology, a scientific intervention that can be a subject of intellectual property rights.

Conclusion

Summing up, the status of the human body between person and thing makes us reject total commodification, ownership and commercialization of the human body and body parts. Instead, we propose alternative logics of exchange; including establishing distribution of body parts inside a system based on donation, informed consent and extended rights of disposal by individual donors. This logic of exchange does not exclude patenting of scientific inventions or incomplete commodification of certain body parts within strict rules of basic ethical principles within a particular sphere of distribution.

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Civil law reflections on the use of human biological material

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Introduction

Recently there has been an upsurge of commercial interest in the activities of biotech enterprises. This has been reflected on the world's stock markets, where biotech enterprises have been numbered among the star performers, but economic and medical successes have given rise to a number of legal problems, one of the most important legal issues being who should derive economic benefit from the successes of biotech development. Is it only biotech companies and shareholders, society and its institutions, or could it possibly be that the person originally providing the biological material is also entitled to a share in the economic benefits? This latter question is connected with the question of who is entitled to the material and, accordingly, has free disposal of it. Who, for example, is entitled to the millions of tissue and cell specimens which are stored in special "biobanks"¹ in our Swedish hospitals?² How is this material being collected and how will it now be used?³ Can the material change hands? What are the possessor's possibilities of disposing of it? Can the possessor carry out any research whatsoever on the material, and if so, how will the information obtainable from the material be used? Does it make any difference whether the biological material comes from a living or a dead person? What about the right of use and disposal where embryos and zygotes are concerned? Can a person whose material is used without his consent sue for damages?

The legal position on biobanks does not seem altogether clear. This is due to the absence of a uniform, coherent regulation of permissible procedures for the collection, storage and use of biological material.⁴ In addition to the problem of ownership/right of disposal of this material, there are many unresolved questions, e.g. the question of whether it is possible for private undertakings to set up biobanks and if so what happens to corporate tissue banks in the event of bankruptcy.⁵ This latter question is especially acute, since privately owned biobanks already exist.⁶

Purpose and extent of the analysis

The purpose of this study is to investigate some of the questions mentioned above.⁷ In particular we shall be considering who can be deemed entitled to the products derived through biotechnology from human material. The analysis will take as its starting point the laws variously dealing with different kinds of biological material and the rules of civil and penal law in general. The analysis will also include an account of the legal position in the light of the Council of Europe Convention on human rights and biomedicine.⁸ That convention, it is true, has yet to be ratified by Sweden, but this may happen within the not too distant future.⁹ In this connection it is also of interest to consider the Convention specifically linked to this European Convention on biomedicine, especially the 1950 European Convention for the

Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)¹⁰, hereinafter called the European Convention.

In the event of biological material being deemed property in the sense of the European Convention, the legal assessment of the question of ownership in Swedish law will be affected. The shaping of future legislation on biological material and its handling will then be an urgent task for the legislator, given that the European Convention already acquired the status of Swedish law on 1st January 1995.¹¹ This incorporation in itself makes the provisions of the Convention directly applicable by Swedish courts and, accordingly, makes it possible for an individual person to have his case tried. If, then, the biological material in the biobanks mentioned above should constitute property in the sense of the European Convention, the legal position on the material collected in the biobanks will have to be defined as soon as possible, so that afterwards it can be decided what regulatory measures may need to be taken concerning utilisation of that material.

The right as such, viewed separately from the actual right of use

When discussing the right to biological material, it is important to distinguish between the right as such and the purely factual possibility of exercising the right, which may be limited, e.g. by legislation regulating use for various reasons. Limitation of the exercise of the property right need not, for example, come into conflict with the European Convention if prompted by a public interest. Thus the line of demarcation is of importance when analysing whether biological human material can be deemed to constitute a property right under the European Convention or a right of ownership as construed by Swedish law. Legally speaking, rights of this kind may conceivably exist in spite of the material, purely as a matter of fact, not being allowed to generate an economic return, owing to rules based on considerations other than those of ownership. For the purpose of the analysis, a distinction has to be made between a potentially basic economic value and a purely factual economic value. A heart may have an economic value in the sense of persons in need conceivably being willing to buy one for transplant purposes, at the same time as such transactions are prohibited under rules basically intended to protect the well-being of the country's inhabitants. The actual occurrence of trade in human organs is a fact pointing in favour of this argument.

Collecting the material

As remarked earlier, there are millions of tissue and cell specimens stored in our hospitals. This material can have been removed from a human being in order, for example, to make a diagnosis, to treat the patient or for transplant donation.¹² Pathology Departments all over Sweden have been saving tissue specimens from human beings ever since the 1940s, and in some cases longer still.¹³ In some places in Sweden there are tens of thousands of blood samples which have been donated for various projects. Tissue specimens from post-mortem examinations are also stored in these biobanks.¹⁴ Sperm banks and banks containing fertilised eggs are other examples of human biological material kept in store. All these biobanks contain material which has been gathered over a long period of time, frequently without consent being obtained from the donor.¹⁵ The donor has perhaps assumed that the material would be destroyed after the treatment was concluded, and is thus unaware that the material was meant to be saved and perhaps used in further research. Thus there may be people who have supplied human biological material without being sufficiently informed about the purpose and nature of the specimen. Possibly they also failed to receive the information that

should have been given to them concerning the consequences and risks which the taking of the specimen would entail. If, on the other hand, the donor received this information and consented, without further specification, to the sample being preserved for future research, one may ask whether he understood what he was consenting to, since no one at the time of the specimen being taken could predict the course of biotechnological development and, accordingly, the potential use of the specimen.¹⁶

Material from a living donor

The first thing to investigate is the condition under which hospitals and research institutions have obtained biological material, since this has a bearing on the question of who has the right of disposal over it. In principle, the taking of samples has always been subject to consent.¹⁷ The present rules of the law on health and medical care, therefore, are relatively precise concerning the situation requiring consent, also in relation to the type of material. Consent can be written or verbal, depending on the situation involved.¹⁸

In our opinion, the rules imply that, if a person has consented to an intervention and on that occasion has supplied biological material which is later stored, for example at the hospital, for subsequent re-transfer to the patient, then the right to dispose of the material remains all the time with the patient. Thus he can decide whether the material is to be destroyed after the treatment has been concluded, and the right of disposal over the material cannot in this case be transferred to the hospital.¹⁹ Consequently a patient's consent to an organ being taken for transplantation to another person means that the patient consents to the material being transferred to the recipient. Since the donor has no legal possibility of demanding the return of the transplanted organ, he has thus surrendered the right of disposal over the material in favour of the recipient.

This argument, however, is open to some doubt, because biological material is sometimes taken for transplantation without being transferred to the recipient directly. Instead it is stored at the medical institution for a fixed or indeterminate period until the right recipient turns up.²⁰ Even in this case, however, the donor has probably surrendered his right of disposal over the material in favour of the medical institution. If the patient provides biological material for research, the same argument should be applicable. If the patient has consented to the material being used in a research project, then by doing so he has surrendered his right of disposal. Since the consent makes such an important difference to the question of who has the right of disposal, it is of the utmost importance for the patient to know what he is consenting to.

Material from a deceased donor

In the case of an organ or tissue transplant from a deceased donor, it is the donor's attitude to the question of donation before his death which matters. Thus Section 3(1) of the Transplant Surgery Act allows biological material to be taken for transplantation or some other medical purpose from a deceased person if that person has consented to the intervention or it can otherwise be ascertained that the measure would be in accordance with the deceased person's attitude.²¹ Biological material may not be taken, however, if the deceased person has objected in writing to such a measure or has spoken against it, or if there is any other reason to suppose that the intervention would be contrary to the deceased person's standpoint, Section 3(2).²² One interesting point in this connection is that the deceased person can make his donation subject to conditions. He/she can, for example, stipulate that certain organs or biological

material may not be taken. As in the case of living persons, a deceased person, if it is his will, retains the right of disposal over the material. On the other hand the deceased donor can never prohibit or consent to the biological material being given for the benefit of a certain person or group of persons of a particular nationality or particular ethnic origin. In such cases there is an impediment to the intervention.²³ On the other hand, if a deceased person has expressed no objection to biological material being taken, the right to disposal may *ipso facto* be deemed to have passed to another.²⁴

Material from embryos etc.

If the biological material is tissue from an aborted embryo, it is the woman who carried the embryo who must consent to tissue from the embryo being used for medical purposes; Section 11 of the Transplant Surgery Act.²⁵ When the materials are to be taken, the woman may stipulate that tissue from the embryo may only be used for a specific purpose. Thus she can exclude a certain use of the material and thus has the right of disposal over the material. If the woman has consented to the material being used in a particular way, however, she cannot subsequently make the use of the tissue subject to further conditions. Her right of disposal has then passed to another party. If the biological material concerns experiments on fertilised eggs for research or treatment purposes, consent is again required.²⁶ Since fertilised eggs are normally stored to be reinserted in the woman donating them, the right of disposal over the material remains with the donors all the time.²⁷ Thus they must be able to decide whether the material is to be destroyed after the treatment has been concluded.²⁸ It should be noted that the Transplant Surgery Act does not apply to the transfer of gametes or organs producing them.²⁹

The Council of Europe Convention on human rights and biomedicine

Summing up, we may note that the laws which have now been mentioned usually require consent to be obtained whether the biological material is to be used for treating the patient himself or for some other purpose. These provisions, however, should be compared with the corresponding articles of the Council of Europe Convention on human rights and biomedicine.³⁰ That Convention also distinguishes between different situations and between different types of material, and it makes provision concerning both when organs and tissues may be taken and consent to their being taken.³¹ Without going any further into the specific rules on the possibilities of taking biological material, we may note briefly that the above mentioned provisions and articles generally stipulate consent where the biological material is to be used for a purpose other than treatment of the patient himself. Thus the stipulation of consent makes an important difference to a question of who may dispose of the material supplied and how. Neither the Convention nor the above mentioned laws, however, tell us what may be done with material that has been taken without consent.³² Can the material be used for research when the original biological material was taken for the treatment of a patient? ³³ One may further ask what one is allowed to do with material where consent has indeed been given but can hardly be said to include the measure now contemplated. Can consent be revoked? Can material be used if the donor is dead but the donor's relatives may come to be affected?³⁴

The right of disposal over the material

The debate on biological material has included a discussion concerning its ownership. It has been asked who owns the material and the information which the material contains. This debate has proceeded in two different directions.³⁵ Firstly, it has been argued that the public or private medical institution, doctors and others collecting the material are its rightful owners. In the other direction it is argued that it is the patient himself who owns his body and its constituent parts. The fact of the material being in a biobank does not alter this fact, and the bank has only certain rights over the material it possesses. It has further been discussed to what extent the owner of the specimen is entitled to dispose of the material as he himself sees fit. For example, is the possessor at complete liberty to sell the material within the country and abroad? Lastly it has been discussed whether the researcher who has used the material in the biobanks has thereby acquired some right of user over it.

To be able to tell who owns the material and who is entitled to use it, and if so what this right of user implies, one must, in our opinion, begin by asking what this so-called right of ownership amounts to. In addition one should state the criteria whereby a person can be deemed to have a right of ownership to an object of value. In addition, one has to ask whether human biological material is in the first place an objective value which can be owned like any other object. If biological material cannot be a subject of ownership in Swedish property law, then the question finally arises whether the material comes within the scope of any other fundamental right.

The concept of ownership in Swedish law generally

The extent of ownership, the concept and its implication have always been a controversial political issue in Swedish law.³⁶ This has resulted in the ownership concept being variously defined and understood by the legislature and jurisprudence at different points in time. In modern Swedish doctrine, ownership is functional, a utilitarian or purpose-related concept which can be used for resolving various conflicts.

Ownership can only be defined in a negative sense. In other words, the owner may use his property as he likes, in the absence of restrictions entailed by law or by agreements which he himself has entered into.³⁷ There are no direct rules of law describing the meaning or true existence of the right of ownership, except for Chap. 2, Section 18 of the Constitution Act and suchlike provisions defining the powers of the owner. Provisions of this kind decide, for example, the conditions on which an owner can exercise his right of ownership in an object as a basis for his obligations.³⁸ Summing up, the content of ownership is a question of political expediency.³⁹ Thus ownership is invested with the content which, from the viewpoint of legal policy, is judged suitable for the attainment of certain purposes.

One closely related question in this context is when the right of ownership passes from one person to another. In property law one finds that there is no special statutory provision as to when the title to an object passes, for example, from vendor to purchaser. The absence of a statutory provision, however, does not mean that ownership is regarded as something which entirely of itself 'passes' from vendor to purchaser.⁴⁰ Instead attention is made to focus on the many different legal consequences associated with the point in time at which title is transferred, and on trying to determine the commencement of those consequences. It is stated in the doctrine that the transfer of title does not hinge on a particular point in time but on the successive transfer of different components of title from vendor to purchaser.⁴¹ Thus different legal consequences pass at different points of time and in turn are linked to certain legal facts. In the purchase of personal property, certain legal consequences

are always attached to the contract. This applies above all to legal consequences affecting the relative obligations of the parties. Other legal consequences, applying to property relations between the parties, are on the other hand attached to tradition.⁴² Thus the legal consequences materialise at certain specified points of time between the conclusion of the contract and the completion of the purchase.⁴³

Criteria of a right of ownership

Since the implication of ownership cannot be substantially determined, the criteria of a right of ownership are likely instead to be determined according to the visible powers which a person may exercise over an object of value. What, then, are the powers of which rights in general are made up? These powers, according to Hessler, are of three kinds, *viz*:

1. *The exercise*, meaning the material or actual power/s or possibility/possibilities of action which may be termed the content of the right. 2. The power of *legal disposal* of the right, i.e. of transferring it, pledging it and so on, and 3. the 'power' consisting in the right constituting *a basis of obligation* on the part of the entitled party, i.e. being included in his property as an asset and thereby forming a basis of the obligations which he incurs.⁴⁴

If applying, for example, the first power associated with ownership, one finds, in Hessler's opinion, that normally, at least, the object here, quite directly, is the economic benefits. One owns a car, a piece of real estate. And power-wise ownership, in principle, encompasses all the possible causes of action with regard to an object which the legal order permits. Within the framework of what is permitted or not prohibited, the owner of a car may do what he likes with it.⁴⁵ Applying the second power of ownership, one finds that an owner has the most far-reaching right as regards the possibilities of transferring the object. Sometimes the owner is the sole person legally capable of pledging an object. Applying the third power of ownership, one finds that the best and safest way of showing that the right is included in someone's property is possession of the object. Through possession one shows one's ownership of the asset.

Biological material as property

As stated earlier, in order to determine the legal status of human material, we have to analyse the true content of the right, i.e. the individual rights and legal dispositions of which property protection consists. The first question to be answered is whether one can own one's body and its parts.

Ownership can be asserted in both real and personal property. Personal property is taken to include chattels, non-freehold buildings, shares and other securities, intellectual property rights etc. Animals are deemed chattels, i.e. choses in possession.⁴⁶ To what category, then, do human beings or the human body belong? In our opinion, human beings would not seem to belong to any particular category. Instead the literature argues that every person is a legal subject.⁴⁷ A person cannot be the object of any other person's right of ownership.⁴⁸ This also applies to deceased persons.⁴⁹ Then what about the ownership of parts of a person's body? It is asserted that parts of a living person (hair, beard etc.) belong to the person from whom they have been separated, unless that person has abandoned them. The same probably also applies to other material, e.g. blood and internal organs removed in the course of surgery.⁵⁰ In the case of deceased persons it is maintained that just as the ownership of the hair, beard etc. of a living person can pass to someone else, however, the same applies concerning the same kind of biological material from a deceased person.⁵¹ Since an invention can be based on biological material of human origin and then patented, the implications of a

patent right in this respect should be underscored. The object of a patent right is generally of an intangible character. The object of the exclusive right is the technical information, an idea, and not the object in the form of a product or a procedure, even though the exercise of the right means preventing others from making commercial use of the information by manufacturing, offering etc. the patented product or procedure. Comparing ownership with intellectual property law, one finds in both cases that the possessor has an exclusive right of disposal to and over the object.⁵² The difference between the two rights, however, is that the rights of disposal over the intellectual property right can be retained and transferred at one and the same time.⁵³ When discussing the ownership of biological material, one should further remember to distinguish between *the material* as such, its physical existence, and the *information* which the material may contain.⁵⁴ The information in the material is something which all human beings carry about with them. Therefore it would not seem possible to assert a right of ownership in the information as such. The right of ownership – if there is one – could only apply to the material itself, not to the information. The only question is what counts as information and what counts as material. A human gene which all human beings are equipped with can, for example, be patented.⁵⁵ Is, for example, the gene giving rise to certain forms of cancer to be counted as material or as information in the material?

Summing up, the legal position appears to be as follows. Nobody can own a living or dead body. On the other hand, a right of ownership can be claimed in body parts. It follows that the material belongs to the person it has been taken from and, accordingly, that consent is required.⁵⁶ Application of the general principles of property law does not furnish any guidance as to when the ownership of human material passes from one person to another. How, then, does this assertion relate to the general criteria of ownership?

As regards the first power, *exercise*, we can begin by discussing what the possessor of a body may do with it, within the scope of what the legal order permits. True, nobody can own a living or dead body, but in practice it is still the possessor who to a great extent decides what is to happen to the body. As regards the second power, that of *legal disposition*, we may discuss when the possessor can exercise this right. Since body parts are clearly transferable, one naturally asks when this transfer can take place. As regards the third power, *the object as a basis of the obligations which the possessor incurs*, we have to investigate whether the body really is such an asset. If body parts can be sold then they are of course an asset. One asks, however, how body parts can be an asset when current law seems to reject commercial trade in human organs. We shall now turn to investigate these questions.

Exercise

As mentioned earlier, we can discuss what the possessor of a body may do with it, within the scope dictated by the legal order. The basic principle seems to be that the possessor can in principle do what he likes with his body. One may abuse it and torment it without society interfering. One is entitled, by self-mutilation, to make oneself ineligible for military service and one is entitled to attempt or carry out abortion on oneself.⁵⁷ One is even entitled to take one's own life.⁵⁸

Man's right to subject his own body to illness, risks etc., however, has been limited in certain respects. A person committing a serious form of substance abuse can be placed in coercive care. A minor can be placed in care, and for this to happen it is sufficient for the parents to be incapable of providing for his needs; there is no stipulation that the minor should be incapable of looking after himself. Then again, even if one wishes to harm oneself, one may not drive one's motor vehicle exactly as one pleases.⁵⁹ Nor may one use narcotic drugs.⁶⁰ Lastly, one may not take part in competitive matches, demonstration matches or training

matches in professional boxing.⁶¹ Society has also imposed limits on what anybody else can do to a certain person, even though that person has consented.⁶² A woman, for example, may not consent to genital mutilation.⁶³ Nor, for example, may a person consent to being murdered or severely assaulted. Consent, then, does not exempt the culprit from criminal liability. On the other hand, certain medical interventions can be classed as assault. In such cases, however, there is no question of hospital staff incurring liability if the patient consented to the intervention. Nor can the hospital staff be held liable in cases where the patient was unconscious and thus incapable of giving consent, so long as the staff can plead that the intervention was an emergency action.⁶⁴

Thus there are a number of enactments indicating what the possessor of a living body may do with it, but what about a dead body? Initially we may note that Chap. 2, Section 6 of the Constitution Act and Chap. 3 of the Penal Code only apply to living persons. This means that a deceased person can never be assaulted.⁶⁵ Furthermore, no one can commit a crime of property by unlawfully removing a dead body or removing a part from a dead body. On the other hand, the person committing this act can be found guilty of an offence against the sanctity of the grave⁶⁶ or possibly of unlawful dispossession.⁶⁷ From birth to death, every person has legal capacity. Once dead, however, a human being is no longer deemed to be a legal subject, and accordingly he loses his legal capacity. Thus the deceased person can no longer acquire any rights. The rights which the deceased person formerly possessed now pass to another person or cease to exist entirely.⁶⁸ It should be noted, however, that the fact of the deceased person no longer being a legal subject does not mean that he becomes a legal object. Thus neither the dead body nor parts of it can be a subject of ownership, with one exception.⁶⁹

Legal right of disposal over one's own body

The second important question to answer is whether the owner can legally dispose of his right, e.g. by assigning it. Thus, applied to the human body, the question is whether the possessor can sell his body or parts of it.⁷⁰ The Government Commission report accompanying the Transplant Surgery Act, however, states that the notion of part of a living person being regarded as a commodity which can be bought or sold is quite alien to most people in our country.⁷¹ The notion of trade occurring in parts of a dead person's body is equally foreign.⁷² On the other hand the doctrine states that, even though there can be no claim to ownership of the person's body or parts of it, a person has the right to disposal over it within certain limits.⁷³

As has already been made clear, Sweden has a number of laws regulating what can be done with a living and dead body respectively.⁷⁴ Most of these laws deal with medical procedures such as transplant surgery⁷⁵, post-mortem examination⁷⁶, criteria for the establishment of death⁷⁷, artificial insemination⁷⁸, research using fertilised ova⁷⁹ etc. What, then, is one allowed to do with a dead body? All the statutory text has to say on this point is that certain procedures with dead bodies are forbidden.⁸⁰ The possibilities of using a dead body for different purposes are limited insofar as the intervention is unsupported by law or statutory instrument.⁸¹

On the other hand it is rather uncertain what applies outside the area regulated by statute. It is an interesting assertion in this connection that relatives or the estate of the deceased person cannot claim ownership of the dead body or parts of it. The dead body is not included in the estate of the deceased person and obviously no economic value can be assigned to it.⁸² The dead body is not to be regarded as a chose in the legal sense. This being so, a person unlawfully removing a dead body cannot be guilty of any crime against property.⁸³ The same applies in the event of someone unlawfully removing a part of the dead

body.⁸⁴ On the other hand it is conceded that, during his lifetime, the individual person may decide a good deal concerning how his body is to be dealt with after he dies. This applies both to burial etc. and the possibilities, after death has occurred, of collecting organs for transplant surgery and of performing post-mortem examinations. Alternatively, some such power of determination is also vested in the relatives. They, on the other hand, cannot “own” a dead body. A right of this kind is only attributed to museums and medical institutions, which can own entire bodies.⁸⁵

The body and its parts – an asset?

The third and last question to answer is whether ownership of the body and its parts is included in the possessor’s property as an asset and thus forms a basis for the obligations which he incurs. From what has now been said, the answer to this question would, initially, seem to be No. On the other hand there is no doubt that a person can cut off his hair and sell it for a certain sum of money to a wig-maker.⁸⁶ Thus it could be argued that a part which has been separated from the body could be given away just like things – choses – generally.⁸⁷

The *travaux préparatoires*, however, appear to distinguish between the situation where the body part can be recreated – as in the case of blood and hair – and a situation where removal entails a lasting detriment to the individual, as for example with the removal of a kidney.⁸⁸ Concerning this latter incidence, it is maintained that if a contract for the sale of a kidney were to come before a court, the court would probably find the contract to be at variance with accepted practice and would therefore void it.⁸⁹ Whether a body part is an asset to the possessor depends on what kind of a body part it is.

The *travaux préparatoires* of the Transplant Surgery Act also discuss the handling of contracts concerning a body part which are already concluded before the part has been separated from the body.⁹⁰ The possibilities are discussed of the entitled party enforcing completion of such an agreement. From the legal analysis, however, it is noted that no distinction is made according to the body part involved. Asserting one’s right as being entitled to the hair which has been sold, e.g. by cutting the hair off the possessor, entails liability for the infliction of bodily injury and is to be regarded as assault if the injured party has not consented. This same goes, of course, for other types of body parts. It does not seem possible for an attempt to be made to enforce performance by executive measures.

We can only conclude that the general rules of civil law concerning gifts and other forms of transfer are subject to substantial modifications in their application to body parts.⁹¹ The question is, however, whether a donation, like a gift, can be made conditionally. Given what has now been said, this would appear to be possible. If the donor has stipulated that the biological material may not be used for anything but a certain purpose, he should be able to insist on the material either being destroyed or returned if the purpose for which it is now intended does not agree with the donor’s wishes.

Given what has already been said concerning the criteria of ownership, the suitability of the concept is open to question when discussing biological material. Since the legal questions with regard to biobanks are above all concerned with rights and obligations⁹², it is, in our opinion, impossible where biological material is concerned to speak of a right of ownership as defined in Swedish property law. The concept of ownership is not applicable, partly because it focuses on choses/objects with related property dispositions and biological material is not to be regarded as such an object. It should also be noted that the concept of possession as used in Swedish property law is also inappropriate in these connections.⁹³

Protection of property

General remarks on protection of property under the European Convention

The protection of property has caused problems in the drafting of universal Conventions, owing to its complicated legal character, which varies from one legal system to another. The difficulty of achieving concrete regulation of this question stems from the political differences associated with the concept of property and protection of property, but the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁹⁴ contains an Article for the protection of property.

Article 17 lays down:

“Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property.”

No such provision, on the other hand, is included in the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights or the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.⁹⁵ Protection of property was omitted from the 1966 Conventions because the Commission was unable to agree on the text of such an Article.⁹⁶ The European Convention, adopted in 1950, did not contain any provision on property protection either. Despite the great difference of opinion concerning the framing of the provision, one was adopted in the first additional protocol to the Convention.⁹⁷ As mentioned earlier, the Convention provision with its additional protocol on protection of property can have a bearing on the determination of the legal status of biological material directly emanating from the human body. That question, however, has not been the subject of any judicial decision.

Sweden has a large number of biobanks containing material which was taken and stored before the requirement for consent actually began to be applied. As has already been shown, the individual cannot be deemed to have a right of ownership in his biological material as the concept is defined in Swedish law. On the other hand there is cause to investigate whether one may still have a basic title to the biological material emanating from one's own body. Any such right will not necessarily be as far-reaching as a right of ownership where the possibilities of economic disposal are concerned.

Since the legal outcome of an adjudication under the Additional Protocol to the European Convention may be relevant to material in biobanks taken before consent was actually stipulated, we shall examine the criteria for the right to property more closely. As regards material taken after consent began to be applied to sampling, the question is less interesting. There is a purely practical explanation for this. If a property right to the material were to prove to exist for the individual person, such a right would be deemed, by reason of the consent, to have passed to the sampler, at all events in the form of a dispositive right to use the material for research to a varying extent.

Internationally regulated property rights

In addition to a defined universal protection of property, various conventions are declarations containing other provisions which are limited to certain types of property. Rights may be limited both as regards scope and as regards the property rights which can be protected. The right of States to dispose freely of their genetic resources is one such example.⁹⁸ The focus here is on the collective right to certain property. Property rights can also refer to intellectual, industrial and artistic activity, which enjoys special protection under various international conventions.⁹⁹

The right to property and its meaning

The legal basis of the right to property, viewed internationally, has already been presented in general terms. We noted that, both in the UN Universal Declaration and in the European Convention, the right is relatively vaguely and indecisively formulated. For this reason the content of the right cannot be instantly determined. In addition, the European Convention seems to be dynamically interpreted by the Court, which means that new phenomena can be incorporated in a context appropriate to the times.¹⁰⁰

In order to correctly crystallise out the content of the right to property and place it in relation to human material, it has to be analysed in relation to the elements characterising the normative structure of human rights.¹⁰¹ Basically, such a necessary division of the individual elements of the right can be based on subject and object. Every right has a subject, indicated whose right is protected. Similarly, the right applies to an object which stands for the true content of the right, i.e. what is protected and against what.

The question of what is protected has a specially interesting bearing on a potential right of property in the biological material of individual persons. Since the scope of the right indicates the limits of what is protected, it has to be established in order to show whether human material is included or not. In the event of such material being included in the protection of property, the legal status of the right also has to be determined. In such an eventuality, we have to analyse the true content of the right, i.e. the individual rights and legal dispositions which the protection of property comprises. Once again it has to be recalled that a right to property under the Convention is not necessarily the same as ownership in the Swedish legal sense.

Property refers to rights, not to concrete objects (choses), but the importance of the property concept varies from one legal system to another, and this is the basic problem when we come to apply the international provisions. Property consists of property rights, which can be either personal or real property. But property is a more extensive concept than ownership and also encompasses other property rights and interests.¹⁰² No clear definition of the concept has been indicated, and so it has to be interpreted in the light of the case law which to some extent clarifies the boundaries of the property concept. Since the scope of the property concept as such has not been very extensively adjudicated, in order to decipher its content we have to fall back on the Commission's decisions concerning refusal or non-refusal.

Personal property

All property rights which are not real property are deemed personal property. A property right may refer to a chose, but limited rights in real and personal property – mortgage title, for example – are also included. Property rights remotely connected with concrete objects may also constitute personal property. Payment claims and intellectual property rights are two such examples. Property protection under the European Convention seems to be more extensive than the right of ownership in the Swedish legal sense.¹⁰³ Without any doubt, the right to property is a fundamental human right, but what exactly that right includes is unclear, and so is its concrete implication. Human rights have been dynamically interpreted by the European Court, and their concrete meaning is governed by case law.

The observation that human material can have an economic value is of relatively recent date, and the court has not yet had occasion to decide any question of property rights concerning such material. Consequently no actual decision exists on this point. As regards the object of property, the wording refers to property but without defining it more closely. The

European Court case law illuminating the right, however, indicates an extensive construction of the concept, and in certain respects protection of property has, through interpretation, acquired a more extensive meaning than the actual wording suggests. For this reason, and also considering that the protection of property has not been framed in a Swedish perspective but in a collective European perspective, a restrictive interpretation of the property concept in the European Convention, in accordance with a traditional Swedish legal view, need not necessarily be correct.

The property concept and the concept of ownership have always varied in meaning and most necessarily follow the time in which they are applied. The reality is that human material today has an economic “value” or “interest”, which used not to be the case. This calls for an analysis of the ownership concept in the light of that reality. The content of the property concept as it can be read into the European Convention in its broad sense can influence the meaning of the ownership concept in Swedish law. At all events it is bound to affect the way in which Swedish law regards the fundamental legal status of human material. If such material can be referred to property in its broad sense, there is a strong argument for each individual having some form of power of determination over “his” biological material. The interesting question will then concern the character of this right. To take two examples of property differing in concrete substance, ownership of an object in the Swedish legal sense is a positive right of property, whereas an intangible right in the form of a patent is a negative right in the sense of being a right to prevent others from commercially utilising a technical idea.

Thus the actual content of a property right can vary. Moreover it is quite permissible for the States Parties under the Convention to impede economic use in a purely factual sense, and also, with a public purpose in view, to deprive the individual of his right. This is subject to the deprivation not being arbitrary and to its complying with the law. Consequently the right of property under the European Convention is not an absolute right. Instead the States Parties are permitted, subject to certain conditions, to limit the right of the individual.

A further aspect where pre-existing biobanks are concerned is that a “right” to the material possessed by the bank can possibly be deemed to have passed by custom, prescription or occupation. If so, this would mean that the right of disposal of the original individual had ceased that any claims to compensation had been cut off.¹⁰⁴ An individual person’s property right, should one exist, might possibly be deemed to imply solely a right of excluding the use of the material. In other words, the individual would not have any right to the economic benefits of products developed from the material concerned.

The EC Directive on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions

The Biotechnology Directive¹⁰⁵ governs the patentability of inventions in which genetic material is included, it does not regulate the ownership of genetic material itself. On the other hand, certain more general European aspects and deliberations concerning human genetic material can be deduced from the provisions and preamble of the Directive. It can be noted in this connection that work on drafting a Directive in this field began already in 1988. Thus years of deliberation went into the Directive which was finally adopted. One important distinction with regard to patents is that these are obtainable for inventions but not for discoveries, and the Directive contains certain clarifications on that point.

The potential economic value of the human body and its components was observed in relation to the possibility of patenting inventions based on information in such material. The Directive clarifies the difference between the material as such and patentable inventions in Article 5, which lays down that the human body, at the various stages of its formation and

development, and the simple discovery of one of its elements, including the sequence or partial sequence of a gene, cannot constitute patentable inventions. The Directive also makes clear that an element isolated from the human body or otherwise produced by means of a technical process may constitute a patentable invention.¹⁰⁶ Body parts or genetic sequences as they exist in the human body are not patentable. Thus it is the technical aspect and necessary human intervention to obtain the product as such which decide the distinction between patentable and non-patentable elements of the human body.

The relevant question for this study is whether these can constitute property and, if so, who owns or controls them. The deliberations underlying the adoption of the Directive can be deduced from these Articles, but as regards human material in a purely general sense, the relevant deliberations are if anything apparent from the preamble, and so it is from the preamble that, to some extent, the collective European view of human biological material can to some extent be evaluated.

In connection with the basic principle that the human body and its components as such cannot be patented, the importance is underlined of respecting the fundamental principles safeguarding the dignity and integrity of the person.¹⁰⁷ The importance of research and development in biotechnology is emphasised in this connection. Attention is made to focus on the fact that significant progress in the treatment of diseases can be made thanks to the existence of medicinal products derived from elements isolated from the human body or produced by a technical process emulating the human body. It is declared¹⁰⁸ that research aimed at obtaining and isolating such elements valuable to medicinal production should be encouraged by means of the patent system. Situations where the patent system provides insufficient incentive for encouraging research into and production of biotechnological medicines which are needed to combat rare diseases are also referred to, which indicates the importance attached to progress in this field, in that Member States have a duty in such situations to respond adequately to this problem.¹⁰⁹

The deliberations underlying the Directive clearly show that from a societal point of view research in this field is important and has high priority. At the same time it is also pointed out that the dignity and integrity of the person must not be neglected. A properly balanced solution reconciling these two sometimes contradictory interests is thus seen to be desirable and is positively called for. The question of the fundamental right to each individual's own body and its elements should then be viewed in this context. Similarly, in our opinion, the question must be viewed in the light of the legal reality that today, even in practice, consent is required in order for the material to be used for research and development. This requirement of consent is also internationally rooted in the Council of Europe Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, referred to above, which has yet to be ratified by Sweden.

Conclusions

Where biobanks are concerned, there are clearly a number of persons whose interests can come into conflict with each other. It is not yet established how the legislature proposes to balance the conflict of interests¹¹⁰ between the donor, his family, the researchers, the biobank proprietors and industry. The rapid pace of development and the complexity associated with biotechnology also make it difficult to regulate this field effectively by means of traditional legislation.¹¹¹ A person's fundamental right of deciding over their own body is evident from Government Bill 1994/95:148 on Transplants, Post-mortem Examinations etc.¹¹² It is noted that the right of self-determination as to whether a person shall donate his organs can have the effect of restricting the possibilities of carrying out transplant surgery. This highlights the

conflict of interest between individual powers of determination and public interests. This conflict of interests also serves to illustrate the situation whereby, even in the event of ownership being ascribed to the person carrying the genetic material, the State can intervene through legislation and if necessary transfer the right of ownership as such or the right of disposal to another party. The *travaux préparatoires* state that each individual has an interest in being able during his lifetime to decide what will happen to his body after death, and that the focus of attention is on the mental integrity of the person. That interest can be greater still as regards the elements of the body during the person's lifetime, but an economic interest is then added. If it is allowed to operate freely without any rules to restrict the right of disposal over the different elements of the body, the economic interest may be relevant both during a person's lifetime and after their death.

One argument for the right of property viewed from the individual person's perspective is that the individual who has a sought-after genetic material must be entitled to the economic benefits which he can derive from that material in the market. It seems less easy to underpin the argument that as soon as an element has been separated from the body it shall accrue to the party "taking" charge of it. The latter must be separated from the view that the party further developing genetic material or making a commercial product of it shall be entitled to his inventive step. These are two separate questions. This is not to say that the "owner" of a body element shall not be able to share in the economic benefits of an invention, but if so this must be a contractual question between "the owner" and the party using the material, as with all other agreements in property law concerning the transfer of ownership. What is now said applies to the fundamental legal status. In practice, the informed consent, for example, which has to be given before specimens are taken probably means any right of disposal passing to the sampler,¹¹³ who then acquires a legal right of disposal over the sample. Where biological material is concerned, however, it is inappropriate to speak of a right of ownership as defined in Swedish property law. If anything the question is one of a "property right".

Another reflection is that property and ownership are not the same thing. Ownership means that the possessor of this right – which always implies an economic value – is protected from encroachment by other interests. Property and the protection of property as defined in the European Convention mean instead that a person's right to his property shall be left inviolate. Regardless of whether the property has an economic value, a person is entitled to have his property kept inviolate, unless the State finds it necessary to regulate the use of that property out of consideration for the public interest. Consequently one does not own one's body, one has only a right to it.¹¹⁴ This last mentioned right means that a person is entitled to prevent others from using material which comes from that person's body. Thus the right is of a negative kind, namely a right of exclusion. This is supported by the stipulation of consent, which *e contrario* can be interpreted/viewed as the right of each individual to prevent further utilisation of the material.

As mentioned earlier, a person has a right to his body and its elements in the sense of this property having to be left inviolate. This means that individual persons are entitled to exclude, but it does not necessarily imply a right to economic return on the material. Through legislation, however, the State can provide for the material present in Swedish biobanks to be used for research out of consideration for the public interest. How this legislation is to be framed is a political question, but its outermost limits are determined by the European Convention. It should be pointed out that our conclusions concerning ownership and concerning property and property protection imply that only an individualised right can come into question, not a national or collective right to the material present in the Swedish biobanks. Nor is the State, as some kind of proxy for the citizens, entitled to the material as such. But the State can legislate on permissible uses of the material.

As regards the material which is already present in Swedish biobanks and which people have supplied without any proviso concerning its use, we take the following view. The proprietors of the biobanks have acted in the belief that they had a right of disposal over the material. What is more, for a long time nobody has laid claim to the material. Although the main rule is that the donor retains the right of disposal over his body, he can assign that right to another party.

As mentioned earlier, the right of disposal is transferred, e.g. in connection with transplant surgery, to the recipient of the biological material or to the institution receiving the biological material. A rule to the effect that the patient retains the right of disposal over the biological material in all perpetuity implies difficulties with regard to the material which is already present in biobanks and for which no consent has been obtained at all. In certain cases, moreover, consent is unobtainable. Then again, there is the question of how to trace material which has been depersonalised, since it is impossible to find the person who originally provided it.

Summing up, however, our standpoint with regard to the material which is present in the Swedish biobanks and which was collected prior to the stipulation of consent as worded in the Transplant Surgery Act, is that the right of disposal to this material has passed to the proprietors of the biobanks. This conclusion is above all supported by the rules of civil law concerning occupation, since the material has been supplied without any intention of recovering it or disposing of it any further. Thus the individual person cannot be deemed to have any right of deciding or impeding the concrete use of the material. This means that a rule to the effect that consent shall include pre-existing biobanks, so the consent would have to be obtained from donors for every use, is unnecessary and also undesirable because it would create obligations with a retroactive effect. The obligation entailing a retroactive effect is due to a legal stipulation of consent having existed all the time but in certain cases having been ignored when the samples were collected, without any measures being taken by the community.¹¹⁵

Another question concerns the handling of the information which can be associated with the material. Rules exist concerning such information about patients, but this question may need to be reviewed, considering that this type of information nowadays is being set up and systematised in a new way. Problems of integrity occur, especially if information about the patient is connected to the material as such, e.g. in databases, and so do ethical questions, such as the question of whether the patient is entitled to find out what is discovered in the material and may have implications for his health etc.

Actual consequences of a property right

The actual consequence of a property right is that the actual control and use of the biological material is reserved for the individual person from whose body it originates. Accordingly, no one else can lay claim to the material after it has left the body if the property right is not to be deemed to have passed to another or if no one shall be deemed to have acquired a right of disposal in the material. A right of disposal of this kind can be regulated and, for example, made contingent on the extent of consent or on similar legal constructions.

If the stipulation of consent is to be taken to mean that the medical institution storing the material must obtain consent in order to use the material for a purpose other than that for which the material was collected, this can in certain cases impede or prevent the use of the material for research and development. The procurement of genetic information may then be impeded and potentially speaking the possibility of developing future inventions may be adversely affected. It has to be pointed out, in this connection, that in the individual case this

is no “worse” than if the person concerned had never supplied his material in the form of samples, since his genetic material would not then have been available at all.¹¹⁶

As long as the human material remains intact in a person’s body, that person can be said to have a “natural” protection against a third party. It would not seem unfair as a fundamental legal principle to deem that the person whose genetic material is at issue is entitled to decide how it will be used or at all events to prevent its use. What may be debatable, on the other hand, is the right to any economic return on the material. Internationally speaking, we can take the USA as an example where most States have passed legislation forbidding the commercialisation of human organs in accordance with the UAGA.¹¹⁷ Although, then, the right of ownership has powerful status in the USA, the purchase and sale of human organs are to a varying extent prohibited, as are, to a varying extent, the purchase and sale of human tissue.¹¹⁸

It is hard to find tenable basic arguments for the principle that the third person who for various reasons may come by the genetic material shall be entitled to its economic benefit without the person carrying the material having any claim whatsoever. This is not to say that regulation of use cannot be justified for certain public purposes, so that genetic material will be available for research and development in a socio-economically acceptable manner. Genetic material today has a value. In the light of national genetic resources, for example, fundamentally accruing to the State where they occur, and to the possibility of owning real property in the way of choses in possession and choses in action, it is illogical that one’s own genetic material should not basically enjoy such status.

A few practical examples will serve to illuminate the situation. Biotechnical inventions are being patented to an ever-increasing extent, and many of these patents are based on human genetic material. One such patented invention is “erythropoietin”, which is used in the treatment of anaemia. The genetic material needed for manufacturing erythropoietin is present in all human beings, which from a commercial point of view means that the supply is great and the “price” ought to be low or indeed nil. The necessary input material – present in the blood – for manufacturing the product would always be available from somebody. A different situation occurs when, for example, a person has a cell strain which is very unusual indeed and his and perhaps a few other people’s cell strain is needed for manufacturing the product. In a “free market” it can be asked why that person should not be able to negotiate and thus have the possibility of harvesting the economic value of his particular cell strain, just like any other asset, since it is capable of generating great economic values. The extreme instance of a person not consenting to use at all and the material being necessary in order to save present or future patients can always be regulated by means of legislation “expropriating” the material for a certain purpose.

The stipulation of consent before the material is taken could be viewed as a way of streamlining a transfer of a property right/right of disposal, but, as has already been mentioned, consent is fundamentally a problem. It would of necessity precede something, which means that a person with a much sought-after genetic structure would have no chance of knowing his negotiating position in advance. One arrangement is for a person to consent only to research into the sample, while stipulating further consent before the genetic information can be used commercially, e.g. by selling a product in which it is included. The donor would then be able to negotiate for payment. In our opinion, however, it is inappropriate to leave “the market free” for the sale and purchase of biological material. Legislation of the kind occurring, for example, in the USA and prohibiting commercialisation in its true sense may be appropriate. It should be considered whether payment based on the expense to the individual of making his material available for research or to save lives should qualify for compensation.

Summary

1. Where biological material is concerned it is inappropriate to speak of a right of ownership as defined in Swedish property law. The ownership concept does not fit, among other things because it focuses on choses/objects and biological material is not to be regarded as such an object.
2. When discussing intangible rights in the form of patents for biological material, it has been recalled that this is something quite different from the title to an ordinary object. A patent right in human genes, for example, means that one has developed an invention based on the information in the human material. The object of the patent right is a concretised idea, not the right to an individual person's genes.
3. Property and the protection of property as defined in the European Convention means that a person's right to their property shall be left inviolate. This is not to say that one owns one's body, one only has a right to it¹¹⁹ in the sense that individual persons have a right of exclusion. This agrees with the stipulation of consent, which *e contrario* can be interpreted as the right of each individual to prevent further utilisation of the material.
4. Although each individual has a right to his body and its elements in the sense of this property being inviolable, the State, through legislation, can provide that the material existing in the Swedish biobanks may be used for research according to the public interest. How this legislation is to be formed hinges partly on political considerations, but its outermost limits are determined by the European Convention.
5. On the basis of an argument of civil law, we are of the opinion, concerning the material which is already present in the Swedish biobanks and which people have surrendered without any provisos concerning its use, that the right of disposal over the material has passed to the biobank proprietors. From this it follows that retroactive consent is unnecessary.

Legal questions which the legislature should consider

Firstly the legislature must consider whether a right of compensation shall be granted for the use of biological material. We have not found anything in Swedish law to support the view that the person concerned is entitled to compensation for the material being used. In our opinion there are several different standpoints which the legislature can choose from. Either one can adopt the standpoint that compensation shall be paid to "the proprietor" when use takes place. In this way one would permit purchase or sale, lending of the material, temporary encroachment and suchlike on the material, which would entail a right of compensation for the proprietor. The other standpoint is that no compensation at all shall be paid for use. No commercial purchase and sale in return for payment shall be permitted. A variant of this last mentioned alternative would be for the donor of the biological material to permit the biobank to use it freely. The biobank would thus be allowed to use the material in the public interest, i.e. in research for the curing of disease. The biobank proprietors, however, would not be allowed to re-sell the material. On the other hand there would be nothing to prevent the biobank proprietors inventing a product from the material. Then of course they could patent this invention and derive economic benefit from it. The choice of direction is for the legislature to decide, but in our opinion the last mentioned part is probably most in keeping with Swedish legal tradition.

Secondly, the legislature must consider what the stipulation of consent implies. By giving consent, has a person given the use of the right to dispose freely of the material, or does consent mean that the right of disposal exists only within certain frames? As in the above

mentioned case, the legislature has various alternatives to choose from. This question, however, is probably too complex to be answered without a close analysis. The structure of consent will be made the subject of a close analysis within “the Biobank Project”¹²⁰ in the course of work during the coming year.

References:

¹ biobank can be a tissue bank or a collection of blood samples, or the information which has been obtained from such a bank. See Biobankers behandling av personuppgifter, Datainspektionens rapport 2000:1 p. 5, Ahlgren, T., Bankinspektion behövs för biobanker? “Kommersiella intressen skall inte tillåtas inkräkta på etiska värden”, *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 13, 1999, p. 1548, Rynning, E., Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?, *Förvaltningsrättslig tidskrift*, 1998, häfte 6. p. 303. See also *Socialstyrelsens förslag till lag angående biobanker inom hälso- och sjukvården m.m.*, 3 maj 2000, pp. 6, 23, 39, 47, 79.

² See Perkiö, H., Svenskarna har dokumenterats i 80 miljoner paraffinklossar *Landstingsvärlden* nr. 18/99 pp. 14.

³ The material can, for example, be used in a way, which violates the integrity of the person providing the sample. It may also come to be used in a way, which causes the provider to be discriminated against in various respects. See Rosen, E., Genetic information and genetic discrimination how medical records vitiate legal protection, *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, vol 27, nr 3, 1999, pp. 166. See also DS 1996:13, pp. 9.

⁴ See *Biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.* Förslag från Socialstyrelsen, 2000, p. 93.

⁵ See Ahlgren, T., Bankinspektion behövs för biobanker? “Kommersiella intressen skall inte tillåtas inkräkta på etiska värden”, *Läkartidningen* vol. 96, nr. 13, 1999, p. 1548.

⁶ See Rynning, E., *Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?*, 1998, p. 303. It should be mentioned that the Icelandic parliament (Allting), for example, has already decided to sell the right of disposal over data from an Icelandic gene bank to a business enterprise for a fixed term. See Ahlgren, T., Bankinspektion behövs för biobanker? “Kommersiella intressen skall inte tillåtas inkräkta på etiska värden”, *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 13, 1999, p. 1548.

⁷ See also Westerlund, L., & Persson, A., H., *Civilrättsliga reflektioner på användningen av mänskligt biologiskt material*, 2000.

⁸ See Convention for the protection of human rights and dignity of the human being with regard to the application of biology and medicine and Explanatory Report. See [http:// www.coe.fr/eng/legaltxt/164e.htm](http://www.coe.fr/eng/legaltxt/164e.htm) 2000-06-06 and [http://conventions.coe.int/ treaty/en/ Reports/Html/164.htm](http://conventions.coe.int/treaty/en/Reports/Html/164.htm).2000-06-06.

⁹ See Rynning, E., *Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?* 1998, p. 312.

¹⁰ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms FördrS 18-19/1990, adopted 4.11.1950, entered into force 3.9.1953. See also Protocols to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. FördrS 18-19/1990, adopted 20.3.1952, entered into force 18.5.1954. See also Åhman, K., *Egendomsskyddet. Åganderätten enligt artikel 1 första tilläggsprotokollet till den europeiska konventionen om de mänskliga fri- och rättigheterna*, 2000, pp. 15.

¹¹ See *Lag (1994:1219) om den europeiska konventionen angående skydd för de mänskliga rättigheterna och de grundläggande friheterna* (Act concerning the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms). Reprinted in SFS 1998:712.

¹² See Rynning, E., *Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?* 1998, p. 305.

¹³ See Perkiö, H., Svenskarna har dokumenterats i 80 miljoner paraffinklossar, *Landstingsvärlden* nr. 18/99 p. 14.

¹⁴ See Ahlgren, T., Bankinspektion behövs för biobanker? “Kommersiella intressen skall inte tillåtas inkräkta på etiska värden”, *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 13, 1999, p. 1548.

¹⁵ See Holmström, L-G., Det ingen och alla äger, *Landstingsvärlden* nr 18/99, p. 20.

¹⁶ See *Forskningsetiska riktlinjer för nyttjande av biobanker, särskilt projekt innefattande genomforskning*, 1999, p. 2; Ahlgren, T., Nya etiska riktlinjer för biobanker, *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 25, 1999, p. 3051.

¹⁷ See Prop. 1981/82:97 pp. 49, 58, and 188. See also Rynning, E., *Samtycke till vård och behandling, En rättsvetenskaplig studie*, 1994, pp. 174, 177. It should be noted, however, that the consent requirement has not always been observed in practice.

¹⁸ See Chap. 2, Section 1 of *Lag (1998:531) om yrkesverksamhet på hälso- och sjukvårdens område* (the Health and Medical Services Professional Activity Act). Sections 2 (2), 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 of *Transplantationslagen (1995:831)* (the Transplant Surgery Act). Sections 2, 2a, and 2b of *Hälso- och sjukvårdslagen (1982:763)* (the Health and Medical Services Act). Cf. Rynning, E., *Mänskliga rättigheter och biomedicin – om Europarådets konvention och svensk rätt*, Ad studium et ad laborem incitavit Elsa Eschelsson, Juridiska fakultetens i Uppsala årsbok, 1997, p. 320. See Prop. 1994/95:148 pp. 31, 79, Cf. SOU 1997:154 p. 422. Cf. Rynning, E., *Samtycke till medicinsk vård och behandling, En rättsvetenskaplig studie*, 1994, p. 125. Cf. SOU 1989:98 pp. 198.

¹⁹ Cf. Statens helsetilsyn. Vedrørende evaluering av lov av 5. august 1994 nr. 56 om medisinsk bruk av bioteknologi – Regulering av biobanker, point 5.3.1.3. I och III Cf. point 6.2.

²⁰ Cf. Statens helsetilsyn. Vedrørende evaluering av lov av 5. august 1994 nr. 56 om medisinsk bruk av bioteknologi – Regulering av biobanker, point 5.3.1.3.

²¹ See the statutory text and Prop. 1994/95:148 pp. 23, 75.

²² See also Sections 3 (3) and 4 of *Transplantationslagen (1995:831)* (the Transplant Surgery Act). See also *Lag (1995:832) om obduktion m.m* (the Post-Mortem Examinations Act). Under Section 21 of this Act, the body of a deceased person may also be used for anatomical dissection for purposes of research or teaching if the deceased has expressly consented thereto. See Prop. 1994/95:148 pp. 100 and *SOSFS 1996:28 om kliniska obduktioner m.m.* (Clinical autopsies etc.), p. 11.

²³ See SOSFS 1997:4, p. 12. *Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter om organ och vävnadstagning för transplantation eller för annat medicinskt ändamål* (Provisions of the National Board of Health and Welfare on the collection of organs and tissue for transplant surgery or other medical purposes).

²⁴ Cf. Statens helsetilsyn. Vedrørende evaluering av lov av 5. august 1994 nr. 56 om medisinsk bruk av bioteknologi – Regulering av biobanker point 5.4.

²⁵ See Prop. 1994/95:148, pp. 41, 84. Cf. SOU 1991:42 pp. 69. See SOSFS 1997:4, p. 16.

²⁶ See Sections 1 and 2 of *Lag (1991:115) om åtgärder i forsknings- eller behandlingssyfte med befruktade ägg från människa* (the Fertilised Human Ova Research or Treatment Measures Act). See also Rynning, E., *Samtycke till medicinsk vård och behandling*, 1994, pp. 125.

²⁷ It should be noted that Section 4 of *Lag (1991:115) om åtgärder i forsknings- eller behandlingssyfte med befruktade ägg från människa* (the Fertilised Human Ova Research or Treatment Measures Act) lays down that a fertilised ovum which has been used for research or treatment may not be introduced into a woman's body.

²⁸ Under Section 3 of *Lag (1991:115) om åtgärder i forsknings- eller behandlingssyfte med befruktade ägg från människa* (Fertilised Human Ova Research or Treatment Measures Act), a fertilised ovum may be stored in the frozen state for not more than five years or for a longer period as determined by the National Board of Health and Welfare by authority of Section 5 of the same Act. Section 5 empowers the National Board of Health and Welfare, if there are exceptional reasons for doing so, to permit an extension in particular cases of the time limit indicated in Section 3. Under these rules, then, the donor cannot prevent the fertilised ovum being destroyed after five years, unless the National Board of Health and Welfare grants permission for it to be stored longer. See SFS 1998:282.

²⁹ See Section 2 of *Transplantationslagen (1995:831)* (the Transplant Surgery Act).

³⁰ See Convention for the protection of human rights and dignity of the human being with regard to the application of biology and medicine, and Explanatory Report. See <http://www.coe.fr/eng/legaltxt/164e.htm> 2000-06-06 and <http://conventions.coe.int/treaty/en/Reports/Html/164.htm>.2000-06-06.

³¹ See particularly Articles 18, 19, and 20. Convention for the protection of human rights and dignity of the human being with regard to the application of biology and medicine, and Explanatory Report. See <http://www.coe.fr/eng/legaltxt/164e.htm> 2000-06-06 and <http://conventions.coe.int/treaty/en/Reports/Html/164.htm>. 2000-06-06. See Rynning, E., *Mänskliga rättigheter och biomedicin – om Europarådets konvention och svensk rätt*, Ad studium et ad laborem incitavit Elsa Eschelsson, 1997, p. 338.

See also *Socialstyrelsens förslag* (Proposals by the National Board of Health and Welfare), 2000, p. 113.

³² Cf. supra p. 4, note 17.

³³ See Rynning, E., *Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?* 1998, p. 306.

³⁴ See Ahlgren, T., Nya etiska riktlinjer för biobanker, *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 25, 1999, p. 3051.

³⁵ See Statens helsetilsyn. Vedrørende evaluering av lov av 5. august 1994 nr. 56 om medisinsk bruk av bioteknologi-Regulering av biobanker point 5.3.1. Cf. also the legislative proposals by the National Board of Health and Welfare, pp. 30. See also Proposals p. 45. Cf. also Samuels A. JP., *Whose Body is it anyway?*

Medicine, Science and the Law, *The Official Journal of the British Academy of Forensic Sciences*, vol. 39, nr. 4, 1999, pp. 285. See Rynning, E., *Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?* 1998, p. 306, Lindberg, B., Vem äger provet? *Läkartidningen*, vol. 94, nr. 45, 1997, pp. 4083. See also, concerning the debate in other countries, e.g. Medical Research Council, Human tissue and biological samples for use in research, 1999, pp. 5.

³⁶ Further, for example, to the ownership concept, see Strömholm, S., et al, *Äganderätt och egendomsskydd. Centrala frågor i alla samhällssystem*, 1985, pp. 7; Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, pp. 17, Håstad, T., *Sakrätt avseende lös egendom*, 6 uppl., 1996, pp. 23; Malmström, Å. & Agell, A., *Civilrätt*, 16 uppl., 1999, pp. 55, 71, 73, 77, 225; Schmidt, F., *Om ägareförbehåll och avbetalningsköp*, 1938, pp. 84; Sjögren, W., *Anteckningar efter Prof. Sjögrens föreläsningar över den svenska sakrätten*, 1908, pp. 69; Skogh, G. & Lane, J-E., *Äganderätten i Sverige*, 1993, pp. 9; Strömholm, S., *Allmän rättslära*, 6 uppl., 1988, p. 15; Sundberg, J. W. F., *Agges huvudpunkter om den allmänna rättsläran*, 3 uppl., 1980, pp. 78; Undén, Ö., *Svensk sakrätt*, 1995, pp. 57.

³⁷ Restrictions of this kind are contained in *Expropriationslagen (1972:719)* (the Expropriation Act), *Förfogandelagen (1978:262)* (the Emergency Powers Act), *Räddningstjänstlagen (1986:1102)* (the Rescue Services Act) etc. See further, concerning ownership, Undén, Ö., *Svensk sakrätt*, 1995, pp. 57, Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, pp. 17. See also Skogh, G. & Lane, J-E., *Äganderätten i Sverige*, 1993, p. 26, Håstad, T., *Sakrätt avseende lös egendom*, 6 uppl., 1996, p. 23.

³⁸ See Strömholm, S., *Äganderätten i idéhistoriskt och internationellt perspektiv, Historiskt och aktuellt. Studier i allmän rättslära*, 1988 p. 124. See also Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, p. 20, Håstad, T., *Sakrätt avseende lös egendom*, 6 uppl., 1996, pp. 22; Cf. Rodhe, K., *Handbok i sakrätt*, 1985, pp. 1, 15.

³⁹ See Håstad, T., *Sakrätt avseende lös egendom*, 6 uppl., 1996, p. 23.

⁴⁰ See Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, p. 18. See also p. 179.

⁴¹ See Håstad, T., *Sakrätt avseende lös egendom*, 6 uppl., 1996, pp. 209.

⁴² See Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, p. 18.

⁴³ See Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, p. 179.

⁴⁴ See Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, p. 20.

⁴⁵ See Hessler, H., *Allmän sakrätt*, 1973, p. 21.

⁴⁶ See Malmström, Å. & Agell, A., *Civilrätt*, 16 uppl., 1999 p. 59 and p. 76.

⁴⁷ See Malmström, Å. & Agell, A., *Civilrätt*, 16 uppl., 1999 p. 59; Inger, G., *Rätten över eget liv och över egen kropp*, Kungl. Humanistiska Vetenskaps-Samfundet i Uppsala, Årsbok 1985, p. 97. See also SOU 1989:98 p. 68.

⁴⁸ See SOU 1989:98 p. 68. Cf. dock Alexius, K., Något om äganderätt, angrepp på egen rättssfär och en eventuell kriminalisering av prostitution, *SvJT* 1995 p. 599 arguing that a person's right to their own body, generally speaking, is probably of a simple kind, i.e. a non-transferable right of ownership unaccompanied by any unconditional right of disposal over the object.

⁴⁹ See SOU 1989:98 p. 70.

⁵⁰ See SOU 1989:98 p. 68. See also Jareborg, N., *Brotten, andra häftet, Förmögenhetsbrotten*, 2 uppl., 1986, p. 49.

⁵¹ See SOU 1989:98 p. 70.

⁵² See Rehncrona, P. V., *Känneteckensrätt ur ett förmögenhetsrättsligt perspektiv, Variationer på ett obligationsrättsligt tema*, Vänbok till Axel Adlercreutz, 1998 p. 290; Levin, M. & Nordell, P J., *Handel med immaterialrätt*, 1996, p. 19.

⁵³ See Rehncrona, P V., *Känneteckensrätt ur ett förmögenhetsrättsligt perspektiv, Variationer på ett obligationsrättsligt tema*, Vänbok till Axel Adlercreutz, 1998, p. 290, Levin, M. & Nordell, P J., *Handel med immaterialrätt*, 1996, p. 19.

⁵⁴ See Ahlgren, T., Bankinspektion behövs för biobanker? "Kommersiella intressen skall inte tillåtas inkräkta på etiska värden", *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 13, 1999, p. 1548.

⁵⁵ Cf. Olsson, H., Kommersialiseringen av gener – patent på bröstcancer gener pilotfall. *Läkartidningen*, vol. 96, nr. 37, 1999, p. 3920.

⁵⁶ See SOU 1992:16 p. 232, samt Socialstyrelsens förslag, 2000, p. 30.

⁵⁷ See Nelson, A., *Kring födelse och död – några juridiska reflexioner*, Kungl. Humanistiska Vetenskaps-Samfundet i Uppsala, Årsbok 1997, p. 125.

⁵⁸ Cf. 3:1 BrB.

⁵⁹ See Section 1 of *Lag (1951:649) om straff för vissa trafikbrott* (the Penalties Certain Traffic Offences Act).

⁶⁰ See Section 1, point 6 of *(1968:64) Narkotikastrafflag* (the Drug Offences Act).

⁶¹ See Section 1 of *Lag (1969:612) om förbud mot professionell boxning* (the Professional Boxing Prohibition Act).

⁶² See Leijonhufvud, M. & Wennberg, S., *Straffansvar*, 5 uppl., 1997, p. 104.

⁶³ See *Lag (1982:316) med förbud mot könsstympning av kvinnor* (the Genital Mutilation of Women Prohibition Act).

⁶⁴ See Leijonhufvud, M. & Wennberg, S., *Straffansvar*, 5 uppl., 1997, p. 104.

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- ⁶⁵ See SOU 1989:98 p. 70.
- ⁶⁶ See Chap. 16, Section 10 of *Brottsbalken* (the Penal Code).
- ⁶⁷ See Chap. 8, Section 8 of *Brottsbalken* (the Penal Code). See further Holmqvist, L., & Leijonhufvud, M., Träskman, P O., Wennberg, S., *Brottsbalken. En kommentar Del 1* (1-12 kap.) pp. 366.
- ⁶⁸ See SOU 1989:98 p. 69.
- ⁶⁹ Cf., however, note 85 concerning exceptions for museums and medical institutions.
- ⁷⁰ Cf. Sägänger, J., *Organhandel, Kroppsdelar till salu*, 1994, p. 80.
- ⁷¹ See SOU 1989:98, p. 25.
- ⁷² See *ib.*, p. 25.
- ⁷³ See Machado, N., *Using the bodies of the dead, Studies in Organization, Law and Social Process Related to Organ Transplantation*, 1996, p. 170.
- ⁷⁴ See Machado, N., *Using the bodies of the dead, Studies in Organization, Law and Social Process Related to Organ Transplantation*, 1996, p. 166.
- ⁷⁵ See *Transplantationslagen (1995:831)* (the Transplant Surgery Act).
- ⁷⁶ See *Lag (1995:832) om obduktion m.m* (the Post-Mortem Examinations Act).
- ⁷⁷ See *Lag (1987:269) om kriterier för bestämmande av människans död* (the Human Death Criteria of Determination Act).
- ⁷⁸ See *Lag (1984:1140) om insemination* (the Insemination Act).
- ⁷⁹ See *Lag (1991:115) om åtgärder i forsknings- eller behandlingssyfte med befruktade ägg från människa* (the Fertilised Human Ova Research or Treatment Measures Act).
- ⁸⁰ See SOU 1989:98, p. 70.
- ⁸¹ See, for example, *Begravningslagen (1990:1144)* (the Burials Act), *Begravningsförordningen (1990:1147)* (the Burials Ordinance), *Lag (1995:832) om obduktion m.m* (the Post-Mortem Examinations Act). Cf. also JO:s ämbetsberättelse 1973, p. 292, in which the Parliamentary Commissioner addressed a question concerning a pathologist who had shots fired at dead bodies in order to investigate the harmful effects of certain firearms on human beings. The measure thus taken had no statutory support, nor was it prompted by a public interest of such strength that the procedure could be deemed justifiable. The pathologist was therefore considered guilty of a crime against the sanctity of the grave. See also SOU 1989:98, p. 71 and SOU 1992:16, p. 60.
- ⁸² See Inger, G., *Rätten över eget liv och över egen kropp*, Kungl. Humanistiska Vetenskaps-Samfundet i Uppsala, Årsbok 1985, p. 97. See also SOU 1992:16, p. 66.
- ⁸³ Cf., though, the requirement for unlawful dispossession in Chap. 8, Section 8 of *Brottsbalken* (the Penal Code). I Holmqvist, L., & Leijonhufvud, M., Träskman, P O., Wennberg, S., *Brottsbalken. En kommentar*. In Part 1(chaps. 1-12) p. 367 it is argued that The object of the crime can, but need not, belong to another. It is further argued that the provision protects a person's possession irrespective of what right (ownership, user, no right at all) the possessor has to the object. See also Jareborg, N., *Brotten, andra häftet, Förmögenhetsbrotten*, 2 uppl., 1986, pp. 42, 82, and 122.
- ⁸⁴ See SOU 1992:16 p. 66.
- ⁸⁵ See Jareborg, N., *Brotten, andra häftet, Förmögenhetsbrotten*, 2 uppl., 1986, p. 49. There would not, however, appear to be any impediment to private persons occupying skeletal parts. See *Ib.*, p. 49.
- ⁸⁶ See SOU 1992:16, p. 58.
- ⁸⁷ See *Ib.*, p. 58.
- ⁸⁸ See *Ib.*, p. 58.
- ⁸⁹ See *Ib.*, p. 58.
- ⁹⁰ See *Ib.*, p. 58.
- ⁹¹ See *Ib.*, p. 59.
- ⁹² See Rynning, E., *Biobankerna – hög tid för bankinspektion?*, 1998, pp. 310.
- ⁹³ It should be borne in mind that we are addressing the concept of possession in a civil law perspective only. Unfortunately it is not possible here to discuss any further the possible importance of the possession concept for this type of property seen from the viewpoint of other legal disciplines, e.g. criminal law.
- ⁹⁴ General Assembly Resolution 217 A(III), 10.12.1948.
- ⁹⁵ The International Convention on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, FördrS 5-6, adopted 16.12.1966, entered into force 3.1. 1976. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. FördrS 7-8/1975, adopted 16.12.1966, entered into force 23.3. 1976.
- ⁹⁶ See further, for the ins and outs of the negotiations, Krause, C., *Rätten till egendom som en mänsklig rättighet, Institutet för mänskliga rättigheter*, Åbo akademi, 1993 pp. 9-20.
- ⁹⁷ Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. FördrS 18-19/1990, adopted 20.3.1952, entered into force 18.5.1954.
- ⁹⁸ Konventionen om biologisk mångfald Art. 1. Convention on Biological Diversity 5 June 1992. <http://www.biodiv.org/chm/conv/default.htm>.

⁹⁹ E.g. the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, adopted 20.3.1883, entered into force 6.7.1884, revised 14.10.1900, 2.11.1911, 6.11.1934, 31.10.1958 and 14.7.1967. The Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, adopted 9.9.1886, entered into force 5.12.1887, revised 13.11.1908, 2.6.1928, 26.6.1948, 14.7.1967 and 24.7.1971.

¹⁰⁰ One example is the Court's interpretation of the right to a good living environment as a human right, Cf. Case of Guerra and others v. Italy, 116/1996/735/932 and Case of López Ostra 'v. Spain, 41/93/436/515. See further www.echr.coe.int.

¹⁰¹ See further Krause, C., *Rätten till egendom som en mänsklig rättighet*, 1993, p. 50.

¹⁰² See Krause, C., *Rätten till egendom som en mänsklig rättighet*, 1993, p. 73.

¹⁰³ See, concerning claims on the state and suchlike, Krause C., *Rätten till egendom som en mänsklig rättighet*, 1993, pp. 78 ff. Other intangible rights such as licences and permits are also deemed in certain cases to constitute a property right protected under Article 1, First Protocol. See further Krause, op. cit., pp. 83.

¹⁰⁴ Claims may of course have arisen earlier.

¹⁰⁵ Directive 98/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 1998 on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions.

¹⁰⁶ Note that certain inventions whose commercial use is at variance with public order or good conduct cannot be patented, e.g. procedures for cloning human beings, procedures for altering the genetic identity of human gametes, and the use of human embryos for industrial and commercial purposes. See further *Socialstyrelsens förslag* (Proposal by the National Board of Health and Welfare), 2000, pp. 97.

¹⁰⁷ Preamble to the Directive, point 16.

¹⁰⁸ Preamble to the Directive, point 17.

¹⁰⁹ Preamble to the Directive, point 18.

¹¹⁰ See *Forskningsetiska riktlinjer för nyttjande av biobanker, särskilt projekt innefattande genomforskning*, 1999, p. 2.

¹¹¹ See Rosen, E., *De lege delenda*, 1999, p. 48. Cf. the statutory regulation of biobanks in Danish law, Hartlev, M., *Den retlige regulering af biobanker, Sundhedsvidenskabelige informationsbanker – biobanker*, 1996, pp. 9.

¹¹² See Prop. 1994/95:148, pp. 23, especially p. 25.

¹¹³ The identity of the sampler is a debated point. The reference can be both to the individual researcher and to other natural and juristic persons.

¹¹⁴ See Åhman, K., *Egendomsbegreppet och människans rätt till sin egen kropp, Lika inför lagen? Rätten ur ett genusperspektiv*, 1999, p. 48.

¹¹⁵ Cf. supra, note 17.

¹¹⁶ To put this question further into perspective, it can be related to intangible rights. Artistic creations bearing the strong imprint of the author's individuality have been deemed by society to need the protection of copyright. Inventions, which in the true sense refer to information concerning the technical idea and are thus characterised by skill and knowledge, are protected by patent. The rights block use by others for a certain length of time, and the time limit has been established in an attempt to strike a balance between the proprietors and a third party in the light of community interest. The personal copyright lasts for the whole of the author's lifetime and for another 50-70 years after his death, whereas a patent is valid for 20 years.

¹¹⁷ The Uniform Anatomical Gift Act. E.g. the following: Vermont; STAT. ANN. § 5246, Utah; UT CODE ANN. § 26-28-2(2)(1998), Pennsylvania, PA STAT. ANN. § 3216(b)(1)-(2), Oklahoma; OK STAT. ANN. § 1-735(1997), North Dakota; ND CODE § 14-02.2-02(3)(1997), New York; NY LAWS ANN. § 4300.2(1997), New Hampshire; NH STAT. ANN. § 291-A:11(1996), Nevada; NV REV.STAT.ANN. § 451.015(1997). Minnesota permits compensation for reasonable expense associated with the intervention, MN STAT. ANN. § 145.422 (1997).

¹¹⁸ Compensation is payable in many cases, but the market is not left free.

¹¹⁹ See Åhman, K., *Egendomsbegreppet och människans rätt till sin egen kropp. Lika inför lagen? Rätten ur ett genusperspektiv*, 1999, p. 48.

¹²⁰ See the multidisciplinary research project "Att på ett etiskt godtagbart och effektivt sätt förvalta mänskligt vävnadsmaterial. – Etiska, sociala, näringspolitiska och legala aspekter kring utnyttjandet av svenska biobanker". (An ethically acceptable and efficient way of administering human biological material. – Ethical, social, industrial and legal aspects of the use of Swedish biobanks.)

Prohibitions against the transfer of human tissue and cells for profit¹

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Introduction

The human body is the single most venerated and protected subject matter in all civilized societies. It is protected from different angles by a huge body of law. One detail in this legal context, and one which so far has not attracted much attention, is the fact that some commercial transactions regarding human biological material are often prohibited. Societies especially shun the idea of selling body organs for transplantation. The legal position is usually based on the fear of poor people otherwise becoming providers of “spare parts” for wealthier people. Economically disadvantaged people could be compelled to sell organs and tissue for the profit involved. Material for transplantations is thus an example of objects that are not usually considered suitable for market transactions. Society is thought to be better served by a gift-based system of transplant material procurement and an egalitarian (non-financial) system of distribution of organs for donation.

However, in the past decade, as medical and scientific advances have proceeded at a rapid pace, several new uses have surfaced for human tissue. Human tissue and other forms of biological material can now in particular be used in research to develop new drugs and treatments. For example, routine blood samples are often used secondarily in research. Similarly, biopsy material or organs removed for therapeutic purposes may eventually be used in research. The surge in the biotech industry has therefore yielded a potential market for cells and by-products of cells. Research on this material can lead to valuable patents. Cell lines, developed from either healthy or cancerous human tissue, now serve as one of the most basic medical research tools. Where the research is directed towards the development of drugs and other useful biological substances, the commercial value of human tissue has become evident. The expanding range of possible uses may force some reconsiderations of the ethics of transactions in human material.

The purpose of this forthcoming article is to explore the legal situation regarding for-profit transfer of human biological material used in medical research. New developments in biotechnology have made it imperative to deal with this question. The key aspect is whether commercial transfer of human tissue for research purposes should be viewed with the same fear as the commercial transfer of biological material for transplantations is viewed at present. Is competitive bidding for research material of human origin allowed and perhaps even advantageous to society? It may be that research tolls deserve a different legal regime than transplantation material.

Clearly, the resolution of problems relating to commercial interests in non-integrated body parts will greatly affect the scientific and medical research community. For one thing,

transfer of human material for value consideration may speed up research. Preventing market-based solutions in this area of research could perhaps seriously impede essential research. But of course there are also important ethical considerations, especially for the patients or donors involved. Patients have an interest in having control over their bodies, and this interest may spill over into research on disintegrated parts of the same body. Opponents of for-profit transfer of human tissue often argue that the trade in human material is morally reprehensible and that such a schema would prey on the vulnerable, such as the poor and uneducated. A successful resolution of this dilemma must necessarily address all aspects of the debate, but in particular the effect on medical research and the ultimate cost to the public in economic and other terms.

The legal situation

Against the general backdrop presented above, the starting point for this legal study is Section 15 of the Swedish Transplantation Act (SFS 1995:831), which provides that someone who willfully and for profit, collects, donates, receives or acts as an intermediary in respect of, biological material from a living or a dead human or tissue from an aborted fetus, shall be fined or sentenced to imprisonment for up to two years. The same punishment shall be given to someone who wilfully uses such material knowing that the material previously has been collected, donated, received or handled by an intermediary, for profit. In the case of slight offences against the prohibition there should be no criminal liability. The provision is not applicable to transfer of blood, hair, mother's milk or teeth.²

Section 15 was introduced into Swedish law in 1995. Before that there was no specific prohibition against for-profit trade in human biological material. The legislative history of the provision explains that the aim of the provision is to prevent people in poor countries from giving up their organs for money. However, during the legislative process the provision was expanded to encompass much more than just trade in organs. It was formulated as a general provision that prevents all trade for profit in human tissue. It is not entirely clear from the preparatory works why the prohibition was expanded so greatly and what kinds of acts the expanded provision was designed to prevent. There are some examples, though, in the preparatory works. It is mentioned that procurement of human biological material for the manufacturing of cosmetics or for the purpose of a display at an exhibition is banned. Such procurements are not allowed, if they are for profit.

The preparatory works, however, have nothing to say concerning the procurement of human tissue for research purposes. Legislative history has traditionally been an important tool for legal interpretation in Sweden. One conclusion from this part of the study, therefore, is that not enough thought was directed to the way human biological material is used for commercial research at present. Nothing is said in the preparatory works about a situation where commercial enterprises procure human biological material for research or diagnostic purposes. It seems that this was never contemplated as an important use for human biological material. Thus at present there is some uncertainty in Sweden with regard to commercial actors handling biological material for research or diagnostic purposes.

The legal situation is further developed in the article, using traditional legal methods of interpretation. Firstly, the precise wording of the prohibition is analyzed in detail. It is concluded that the scope of the prohibition is very broadly formulated. It could, at least in theory, encompass many transactions that are actually carried out or at least contemplated at the moment in Sweden. Therefore if the language of the prohibition covers all transfers of human tissue for a profit purpose, it could seriously impede research by restricting access to research tools.

Secondly, an overview is presented of the present forms for commercial use of human biological material in research settings in Sweden. This part relies heavily on the study “The Industrial Use of Biobanks in Sweden: an overview” by Jens Laage-Hellman, which forms another part of this project. The case of Gemini Genomics AB, previously Euron Medical, and also the case of UmanGenomics, are discussed in particular detail as examples of commercial research uses for human biological material.

A third section of the article addresses the international legal context of prohibitions against the transfer of human tissue and cells for value consideration. The discussion in this part centers around the convention adopted by the Council of Europe: “Convention for the protection of human rights and dignity of the human being with regard to the application of biology and medicine: Convention on human rights and biomedicine”. The Convention came into force on December 1, 1999, after five ratifications had been deposited. Countries ratifying the convention thereby pledge themselves to adopt their national law to the requirements of the Conventions and to provide legal safeguards for persons in accordance with the Convention.

Article 21 of the Convention is headed “Prohibition of financial gain” and provides the following:

The human body and its parts shall not, as such, give rise to financial gain.

An official commentary on the Convention, an Explanatory Memorandum, is available. It limits the scope of the prohibition against financial gain, with respect to discarded tissue. It provides: “The provision does not refer to such products as hair and nails, which are discarded tissues, and the sale of which is not an affront to human dignity.”³ Discarded material, e.g. hair and nails, may be transferred for financial gain provided that the sale is not an affront to human dignity.

Tentative conclusions

A preliminary conclusion drawn in this legal study about the Convention adopted by the European Council is that human biological material in Swedish biobanks could probably be considered discarded tissue. Therefore for-profit transactions in human biobank-material must not necessarily be prohibited. The Convention offers leeway for signatory States with respect to commercial transactions in discarded tissue. The aim of the cited international prohibition is primarily to prevent trade in organs for transplant, not to prevent the procurement by commercial actors of research tools, such as material stored in Swedish biobanks.

Finally, some additional tentative conclusions from the study can be mentioned here. The author of the article argues that a clear legislative response is required to eliminate the surrounding uncertainty in the law, which currently threatens to prevent private actors and private/public cooperation in the use of human tissue. The present uncertainty is clearly unsatisfactory. Hopefully the initiative to introduce a Swedish Biobanks Act will improve this situation. But the author also argues that the reasoning that led to the formulation of Section 15 of the Swedish Transplantations Act of 1995 and also the reasoning in the new proposal for a similarly worded prohibition in the Biobanks Act, are not wholly convincing. Material in biobanks is not stored there for transplantation purposes, but mainly for research and diagnosis. Commercial considerations and private actors play a prominent role in these fields, especially in medical research. The Swedish legislation is designed with transplantation cases in mind and is not really appropriate for research tools. Profit motives cannot be excluded

from medical research, nor probably from the procurement of medical research tools such as tissue samples. The important ethical considerations might need to be of a more specific kind. The author therefore concludes the study by arguing that the prohibitions against the transfer of human tissue and cells for valuable consideration should be limited to material that is used in therapeutic treatment of some person other than the person from whom the material was taken. Outside the therapeutic situation, uses for human biological tissue are so diverse and rapidly changing, that more specific legal rules than prohibitions against all forms of transfer for profit are necessary in order for ethical needs to be safeguarded without, at the same time, impeding research.

References

¹ This is an English summary of the article *Humanbiologiskt material och vinningssyfte*, which will be published in the Swedish legal journal *Juridisk tidskrift*, either in issue 4, 2000-2001, or in issue 1, 2001-2002

² Section 15 of the Swedish Transplantation Act (1995:831) reads: “Den som med uppsåt och i vinningssyfte tar, överlämnar, tar emot eller förmedlar biologiskt material från en levande eller avliden människa eller vävnad från ett aborterat foster döms till böter eller fängelse i högst två år. Till samma straff döms den som med uppsåt använder eller tar till vara sådant material för transplantation eller annat ändamål trots insikt om att materialet tagits, överlämnats, tagits emot eller förmedlats i vinningssyfte. I ringa fall skall inte dömas till ansvar.

“Första stycket gäller inte blod, hår, modersmjölk och tänder.”

³ Point 133 of the Explanatory Memorandum.

The use of human biobanks – public law aspects

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Introduction

The public law part of the Biobank Project is primarily focused on issues concerning the legal protection of human rights concerning e.g. privacy, personal integrity, self-determination and non-discrimination. The study thus deals inter alia with the obligations of society, with regard to the provision of judicial protection for patients and research subjects from whom biological samples are obtained. A similar need for protection can also be perceived with regard to the genetic relatives of such donors, sometimes even to persons belonging to a group of people with a genetic make-up related to that of the donor. There are, however, other interests to consider as well, such as the interest of society in furthering good research and making effective use of valuable resources. The measures taken by public agencies in order to monitor, limit and control various activities concerning the use of human biobanks must always be governed by basic public law principles such as proportionality, legality and equality before the law. The recommendations that may be inferred from the study will thus be aimed at facilitating efficient management of Swedish biobanks, while also offering appropriate protection for the rights of individuals and groups concerned. The study involves the analysis of relevant areas of both Swedish and international public law, as well as comparative aspects regarding the internal law of certain other jurisdictions, primarily the Nordic countries.¹ This first report is limited to a short overview of some relevant sources of law and the legal issues that are being studied.

International aspects

As a member of the European Union, Sweden is obliged to observe the developments within EU law, also when it comes to designing our internal law in many areas. In one way, EU law should be considered an integral part of Swedish law, at least to the extent that it is directly binding. In another sense, however, EU law is still a part of the international law that in different ways governs or influences our domestic legal rules. Other important influences of international law are related to our membership of international organizations such as the Council of Europe and the United Nations, and to treaties signed or ratified by Sweden. EU legal documents of relevance to the public law study include the directives on the protection of personal data,² on in vitro diagnostic devices³ and the recently adopted directive on clinical trials.⁴ None of these directives deal directly with biobanking, but they regulate matters concerning the processing of personal information, the use of human biological material and some of the prerequisites for research involving humans. The Council of Europe has produced a number of documents relevant to the handling of biobank materials. A most important one is

the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine (1997),⁵ even though Sweden has not yet ratified this convention. In Article 22, it is thus prescribed that if any part of a human body has been removed in the course of an intervention, it may be stored and used for a purpose other than that for which it was removed only if this is done in conformity with appropriate information and consent procedures. An earlier recommendation specifically dealing with human tissue banks, No. R (94) 1,⁶ proposes inter alia that such banking activities should be carried out by non-profit-making institutions. It is also recommended that the distribution of banked materials “take place in such a way as to permit optimal use of the tissues on an equitable basis in accordance with national law, rules and practice and objective selection criteria”. In other documents, the Council of Europe has voiced the idea that human tissue should be considered as a source of information and be protected in the same way as other media carrying personal information.⁷ Other examples of international documents that must be considered in this context are the UNESCO Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights (1997)⁸ and the WHO Proposed international guidelines on ethical issues in medical genetics and genetic services (1997).⁹

Swedish law today

At present, there is no comprehensive Swedish legislation specifically regulating the use of biobanks. A proposal for a new Act concerning Biobanks in Medical Care etc. was presented in a report from the National Board of Health and Welfare in May 2000,¹⁰ and has been circulated for consideration. Until such an Act is passed by the Swedish Parliament – and without doubt even thereafter – certain issues related to biobanking are regulated by provisions scattered over a number other acts and statutory instruments. There are also non-binding ethical guidelines adopted by the Swedish Medical Research Council in 1999, specifically dealing with biobanks in medical research.¹¹

To a certain extent, the duties of the state and all public institutions in their relations with the citizens are laid down already in basic laws with constitutional status. Thus it is clear from the Instrument of Government (1974:152), Chapter 1 Section 2, that public institutions shall inter alia respect the human dignity and equal value of all human beings, and protect the privacy of individuals. Under Chapter 2 Section 6, all citizens shall be protected against any physical violation in their relations with the public administration, which would seem also to include protection against coercive blood tests etc. This right may only be restricted by a statute enacted by the Swedish Parliament, and only to the extent necessary for purposes acceptable in a democratic society; see the Instrument of Government, Chapter 2, Section 12. The Freedom of the Press Act (1949:105), Chapter 2 Sections 1-2, lays down the principle of public access to official documents, but also restrictions motivated e.g. by the need for protection of the privacy of individuals. Although constitutional rights are important, however, in order to be effective the basic principles often need to be transformed into clear and enforceable rules in ordinary legislation.

With regard to the taking of biological materials from humans, there are relevant provisions to be found in the Health and Medical Services Act (1982:763) and the Act (1998:531) on Professional Activity in Health and Medical Services, when the removal of the material is part of a medical treatment of the person concerned. If the material is removed for other medical purposes, the provisions of the Transplant Act (1995:831) or the Autopsy Act (1995:832) will normally apply, complemented by statutory instruments and general recommendations issued by the National Board of Health and Welfare.¹² For certain measures there is additional, specific regulation. When samples are taken as part of a clinical drug trial, the procedure will also fall under the requirements laid down in Sections 13-14 of the Medicinal Products Act (1992:859) and the Medical Products Agency’s provisions and

guidelines on the clinical trials of medicinal products.¹³ With very few exceptions, the provisions regulating the taking of human materials for different medical purposes require the free and informed consent of the individual concerned. This goes well with the constitutional protection offered in the Swedish Instrument of Government, Chapter 2, Section 6, for the bodily integrity of all citizens. When the person concerned is incompetent to give legally valid consent, however, the law is less clear, particularly regarding incompetent adults. Also, the legal rules mentioned above do not explicitly deal with issues concerning the further use of the biological material, once it has been removed from the human body. A somewhat broader perspective can be seen in some provisions, e.g. the regulation on in-vitro diagnostic medical devices, where the National Board of Health and Welfare prescribes that certain measures concerning the taking, collection and use of human tissue, cells and substances must be in keeping with the European Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine.¹⁴

Measures concerning the collection and storage of biological materials from humans are less regulated by Acts of Parliament than is the actual removal of such materials. Apart from the odd provision in the Act (1991:115) concerning Measures for Purposes of Research or Treatment Using Fertilized Human Ova. and the Insemination Act (1984:1140), there are also statutory instruments and general recommendations by the National Board of Health and Welfare, on matters such as the use of biological waste materials, storage of blood for transfusion purposes, storage of sperm for insemination, and routines for the preservation of samples at departments of pathology.¹⁵ At this stage, the provisions are mainly focused on issues of quality and safe preservation. The interests of the donors are not given nearly as much attention, but there are still some references made to the wishes of the persons concerned.

When it comes to provisions regulating the actual use of biological materials from humans, Swedish law is very sparse indeed, with the exception of the areas of assisted procreation and research on fertilised human ova. There is also an Act (1991:114) concerning the Use of Certain Genetic Technology in Medical Screening, specifically regulating DNA and RNA analyses, but the scope of this act is rather limited and it has never been applied so far. The transfer of human biological materials is regulated mainly with regard to the prohibition of financial gains; see section 15 of the Transplants Act (1995:831). In addition to this, there is also a provision in Section 6 of the Insemination Act (1984:1140), prohibiting import of frozen sperm without the authorisation of the National Board of Health and Welfare.

Out of the different issues related to biobanking, the handling of information concerning or derived from human materials would seem to be the area most thoroughly regulated, especially when the information can be related to identifiable individuals. The rather strict legal requirements for professional confidentiality and secrecy concerning health related information are thus laid down mainly in Chapter 7, Section 1 of the Secrecy Act (1980:100) and – with regard to the private health care sector – in Chapter 2, Section 8 of the Act (1998:531) on Professional Activity in Health and Medical Services. There are also relevant provisions in the Medical Records Act (1986:203). Should a private health care provider for any reason discontinue his or her business, the medical records will be taken care of in accordance with specific requirements in Sections 11-14 of this Act. Statutory provisions regarding the processing of personal information in databases or registers can be found in the Personal Data Act (1998:204), the Health Data Registers Act (1998:543) and the Medical Care Registers Act (1998:544). When sensitive personal information is processed for research purposes, whether in the private or the public sector, the consent of the individual concerned will normally be required. However, this requirement can be waived in certain cases where the interest of society in the research project “is manifestly greater than the risk of improper violation of the personal integrity of the individual”.¹⁶ Automated processing of personal data regarding hereditary disposition derived from genetic investigation is subject to

a particular requirement of mandatory prior notification to the Data Inspection Board, under Section 9 of the Personal Data Ordinance (1998:1191). There are also special provisions regulating DNA registers for criminal investigations, in the Police Data Act (1998:622).

When it comes to the monitoring or supervision of biobank activities, there are several public agencies with different responsibilities. The National Board of Health and Welfare thus monitors the areas of health care and clinical research in connection with the treatment of patients.¹⁷ The Board also monitors clinical trials regarding medical devices, whereas the Medical Products Agency monitors all clinical drug trials.¹⁸ The processing of personal data is monitored by the Swedish Data Inspection Board, which presented its first report on biobanks in the year 2000.¹⁹ All three of these agencies cover both the public and the private sector. Regarding biobank research that is not related to clinical trials or the treatment of patients, public universities and research institutions can be considered subject to some kind of monitoring on the part of the National Agency for Higher Education,²⁰ at least in theory. Sweden has no general legislation on research involving humans, a shortcoming that has repeatedly been pointed out.²¹ Some types of biomedical research that is conducted e.g. by private companies thus would seem to avoid any real monitoring, apart from personal data processing.

This short overview of Swedish law applicable to biobank activities shows that while we do have rules regulating the interventions required to remove samples of human material from a person or a body, and the processing of personal information related to such samples, the rules concerning collection, storage, use and transfer of the biological material itself are sparse. Quite obviously, there are gaps in the legal safety net aimed at protecting the autonomy, privacy and personal integrity of individuals. With regard to personal information in a more traditional form, individuals are offered protection against infringements of their privacy and integrity, and are also guaranteed almost unlimited access to the information available about their health, e.g. in their medical records.²² There are no similar rules concerning a person's access to biological materials removed from his or her body,²³ nor are there any clear rules on the right to decide about further use of such materials. Whereas the interests of society, with regard to the preservation of information in official documents and recordings, are protected by statutory rules, e.g. in the Archives Act (1990:782), the preservation of biological materials is mainly provided for by non-binding recommendations. The present legal situation does not only involve risks related to the rights of individuals, but can also constitute an actual impediment to the effective and justifiable use of valuable resources. The lack of appropriate regulation concerning the preservation, access and distribution of human materials may thus lead to unnecessary waste of such resources.

Developments in the Nordic countries

In all of the Nordic countries, the need for regulation concerning biobank activities has been given increased attention during the past few years. Iceland was the first to adopt an Act on Biobanks (110/2000),²⁴ which entered into force on 1 January 2001. In Finland, a new Act (101/2001) on the Use of Human Organs and Tissue for Medical Purposes was recently passed. The Finnish Act, which includes certain provisions on the taking, collection and further use of human tissue, will enter into force 1 September 2001. Although the legal issues related to biobanking were observed and debated in Denmark already in the mid-nineties,²⁵ no specific legislation regulating biobank activities has been adopted so far. Structured biobanks with samples from identifiable individuals do however fall under the Danish legislation on data registers,²⁶ and an inter-ministerial group is at present investigating the possible need for comprehensive legislation.²⁷ In Norway, a commission is preparing a report on the same subject.²⁸

The legislation suggested by the Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare is at present being considered and processed by the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs,²⁹ after having been circulated for comment. One prominent feature of the proposal, which is clearly influenced by the European Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, is the rather strict consent requirements with regard to measures involving biological material from living donors. It is also suggested that the establishment of biobanks for research purposes, as well as the use of biobank materials in research, should be subject to mandatory review by a research ethics committee. The National Board of Health and Welfare will monitor biobank activities and keep a register of the new and existing banks. One important limitation, however, is that the proposed legislation only applies to biobanks containing samples that originate from the health care sector. Certain biobanks that are independently set up by e.g. biotechnology companies or research institutions thus would not seem to be covered by the proposed Act concerning Biobanks in Medical Care etc.

The Icelandic biobank legislation does not require samples to originate from the health care sector, but on the other hand excludes banks that are only for temporary use and that will be destroyed within a period of five years. The new Finnish Act would seem to cover a broader scope of biobanks compared to the Icelandic and proposed Swedish legislation, but then it does not contain the same type of requirements concerning notification, authorisation and registration of biobank activities, nor any provisions on coding or depersonalisation of samples.

The public law study

As mentioned above, the study deals with public law issues related to the taking and gathering of human material for biobanking, the preservation, use and transfer of such material, as well as the processing of information related to it. Previous research in this area, with regard to Swedish law, has been very limited.³⁰ When analysing the national sources of law and the requirements laid down in international law, one important aspect concerns the degree of judicial protection that is offered individual autonomy, privacy and integrity in different contexts. Other aspects are related to the legal guarantees for the preservation of and access to information of considerable value to society.

One relevant question is thus to what extent the rules governing confidentiality and the processing of personal information vary, depending on the medium carrying the information (e.g. paper, audio/video tape, automated data base or human tissue), and whether the differences are justified. What do the different laws have to say, for example, about consent requirements, withdrawal of consent, anonymity and encoding of information? Important questions concern the very concept of personal data with regard to information obtainable from human material by genetic testing. On the one hand, it could be argued that even anonymous biological material can be traced back to the individual by means of genetic analysis, making complete anonymity virtually impossible in this context. On the other hand, one of the characteristics of genetic information is that it rarely concerns only the person from whom the sample is taken. How are the interests of relatives and other identifiable groups of people being taken into account? We also need to consider the particular vulnerability of minors and incompetent adults, for example.

The interests of individual donors and associated groups must be a primary consideration, but as mentioned above, valuable research should not be unnecessarily hindered. Furthermore, the need for protection of different parties may vary depending on how the biological material is used, e.g. as a source of information for different types of studies or as raw material for a product.³¹ Somewhat varying solutions to the biobank issues

are being presented or contemplated in different legal sources and jurisdictions. These examples bring both inspiration and complexity to the study.

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- ² Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. OJL 281, 23/11/1995 pp. 0031 – 0050.
- ³ Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 1998 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices. OJL 331, 07/12/1998 pp. 0001 – 0037.
- ⁴ See Common Position (EC) No 44/2000 of 20 July 2000 adopted by the Council, OJL 300, 20/10/2000 p. 32; and the European Parliament legislative Resolution of 12 December 2000 (information note 14041/00), regarding the Commission's amended proposal for a European Parliament and Council Directive on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use /COM/99/0193 final – COD 97/0197/. OJL 161, 08/06/1999 p. 0005.
- ⁵ Convention for the protection of human rights and dignity of the human being with regard to the application of biology and medicine: Convention on human rights and biomedicine (1997, ETS No. 164). The convention entered into force 1 December 1999. See also the Explanatory Report, CM (96) 175 final, and Rynning, *Mänskliga rättigheter och biomedicin – om Europarådets konvention och svensk rätt*. De lege. Juridiska fakulteten i Uppsala årsbok, årgång 7, Iustus Förlag 1997 pp. 311–350.
- ⁶ Recommendation No. R (94) 1 of the Committee of Ministers, on human tissue banks.
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- ⁸ At <http://www.unesco.org/ibc/uk/genome/projet/index.html>. (010201)
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- ¹⁰ *Biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.*, Socialstyrelsen 2000, at <http://www.sos.se/FULLTEXT/0077-011/0077-011.htm> (010201). For a summary in English, go to <http://www.sos.se/sos/publ/refereng/0077011e.htm> (010201).
- ¹¹ Research ethics guidelines for using biobanks, especially projects involving genome research. Adopted by the Swedish Medical Research Council (MFR) in June 1999, (Dnr 1999-570). English version at <http://194.52.62.221/SinglePage/SinglePage.asp?ItemID=670> (010201).
- ¹² Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter och allmänna råd (SOSFS 1997:4) *Organ- och vävnadstagning för transplantation eller för annat medicinskt ändamål* and Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter och allmänna råd (SOSFS 1996:28) *om kliniska obduktioner m.m.* It should be observed that general recommendations (allmänna råd) issued by Swedish public agencies are not formally binding in same way as statutory instruments in the form of regulations etc (föreskrifter).
- ¹³ Läkemedelsverkets föreskrifter och allmänna råd (LVFS 1996:17) *om klinisk läkemedelsprövning*.
- ¹⁴ Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter (SOSFS 1999:24) *om medicintekniska produkter för in vitro-diagnostik*.
- ¹⁵ Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter och allmänna råd (SOSFS 1997:4) *Organ- och vävnadstagning för transplantation eller för annat medicinskt ändamål*; Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter (SOSFS 1989:38) *om blodgivning, blodtransfusion m.m.*; Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter och allmänna råd (SOSFS 1987:6) om

inseminationer and Socialstyrelsens allmänna råd (SOSFS 1995:9) Rutiner för bevarande av provmaterial vid patologavdelningar m.m.

¹⁶ Section 19 of the Personal Data Act.

¹⁷ Chapter 6, section 1 of the Act (1998:531) on Professional Activity in Health and Medical Services.

¹⁸ Section 11 of the Medical Devices Ordinance (1993:876) and section 23 of the Medicinal Products Act (1992:859) respectively.

¹⁹ Biobankers behandling av personuppgifter. Datainspektionens rapport 2000:1 (at <http://www.datainspektionen.se/>) (010201).

²⁰ Section 3 of the Instruction Ordinance (1995:945) of the National Agency for Higher Education.

²¹ See e.g. the two official reports on research ethics (SOU 1989:74 and SOU 1999:4), the National Board of Health and Welfare report concerning Biobanks in Medical Care etc., the government bill 2000/2001:3 p. 92, and the final report of the Biotechnology Commission (SOU 2000:103) p. 299. See also Rynning, Etisk granskning av medicinsk humanforskning - lagstiftning behövs! *Läkartidningen*, 1997:1771-1774.

²² See e.g. Chapter 14, Section 4 and Chapter 15, Section 4 of the Secrecy Act (1980:100), Chapter 2, Section 12 of the Freedom of the Press Act and Section 16 of the Medical Records Act (1985:562).

²³ In the case RÅ 1994 note 465, the Supreme Administrative Court ruled that biological material in the form of a blood sample does not constitute a document, and is thus not covered by the right of access to official documents laid down in the Freedom of the Press Act.

²⁴ English version presented at <http://brunnur.stjr.is/interpro/htr/htr.nsf/pages/forsid-ensk> (010201).

²⁵ See Nielsen et. al., *Sundhedsvidenskabelige informationsbanker – biobanker*, Statens Sundhedsvidenskabelige Forskningsråd, Den Centrale Videnskabetiske Komité og Det Ethiske Råd 1996.

²⁶ See e.g. Blume, *Personregistrering*, 3 ed. 1996, pp. 29-34; Hartlev, *Den retlige regulering af biobanker – love og rekommandationer. Appendiks til rapporten Sundhedsvidenskabelige informationsbanker – biobanker*, Utg: Statens Sundhedsvidenskabelige Forskningsråd, Den Centrale Videnskabetiske Komité og Det Ethiske Råd 1996.

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²⁸ Offisielt fra statsråd 28.01.2000, at http://odin.dep.no/smk/norsk/aktuelt/off_statsraad/099005-994017/index-dok000-b-n-a.html (010201).

²⁹ February 2001.

³⁰ See e.g. *Human biobanks – ethical and social issues*, Nord 1997:9, The Nordic Committee on Bioethics 1997; Rynning, Biobankerna – hög tid för bankspektion? *Förvaltningsrättslig Tidskrift* 1998 pp. 303-333 and the National Board of Health and Welfare report Biobanks in Medical Care etc., 2000.

³¹ It should be noted that property rights are dealt with solely in the private law studies of this project, whereas general matters of access, consent etc. are analysed from both private and public law aspects.